

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Computational methods to study piano music in education context

Pedro Ramoneda

Supervisors:

Dr. Marius Mirón

Prof. Xavier Serra

Project Defence on June 28th, 2021

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Abstract

In the last decades, music students, teachers, and institutions are embracing online education in an accelerated way. In this context, this master thesis aims to carry out a computational exploratory analysis about Piano Music Education's new technologies from symbolic data. We propose technological approaches to various aspects of Piano Music Education in its most global view, from technique to accompaniment and composition. First, we suggest two automatic piano fingering systems. Second, we depart from one previous generative fingering system to explore the technical difficulty in the new Mikrokosmos dataset. Third, we model the relationship between a soloist and piano accompaniment suggesting descriptors in three dimensions: melodic, rhythmic, and harmonic. Lastly, we confirm that automatic composition systems can be biased to generate an individualised repertoire based on difficulty level. The presented work makes a step toward expanding current Music Information Retrieval approaches for Piano Music Education and opening new horizons and challenges for further research.

Keywords: Music Education; Piano Technique Modelling; Score Difficulty Analysis; Piano Accompaniment Analysis; Computational Musicology; Algorithmic Composition; Music Information Retrieval; Sound and Music Computing;

Resumen

En los últimos años, estudiantes de Música, Profesores e Instituciones docentes, han ido incorporando la educación On-line de forma creciente. En este contexto, este TFM pretende llevar a cabo un análisis mediante exploración computacional de las tecnologías de educación pianística a partir de datos simbólicos. Proponemos una aproximación tecnológica a varios aspectos de la formación pianística desde una visión muy global que va desde la técnica de interpretación, al acompañamiento o la composición. Primero sugerimos dos métodos de digitación automática. Segundo, partiendo de un sistema previo de digitación, exploramos la dificultad técnica sobre el dataset Mikrokosmos. Tercero, modelamos la relación entre un solista y su acompañamiento de piano, sugiriendo descriptores en tres dimensiones; melodía, ritmo y armonía. Finalmente, confirmamos que los sistemas de composición automáticos pueden ser configurados para crear un repertorio individualizado basado en dificultad. El trabajo presentado es un paso hacia la mejora del conocimiento actual sobre Recuperación de Información Musical para la educación pianística abriendo nuevos horizontes y retos para futuras investigaciones.

Resum

En els darrers anys tant estudiants de Música com Professors i Institucions Docents, han anat incorporant progressivament l'educació Online. En aquest context, aquest Treball de Final de Màster té per objectiu dur a terme una anàlisi a través de tècniques computacionals sobre dades simbòliques, de l'educació pianística. Proposem una aproximació tecnològica a diversos aspectes de la formació pianística des d'una visió molt global que va des de la tècnica interpretativa i l'acompanyament a la composició musical. Primer suggerim dos mètodes automàtics de digitació. En segon lloc i a partir d'un sistema previ de digitació, explorem la dificultat tècnica de la peça musical i ho fem sobre el Dataset Mikrokosmos. En tercer lloc, modelem la relació entre un solista i el seu acompanyament al Piano suggerint descriptors en tres dimensions; melodia, ritme i harmonia. Finalment confirmem que els sistemes de composició automàtics poden ser configurats per a crear un repertori personalitzat basat en el grau de dificultat. El treball presentat és un pas més endavant en els coneixements del camp de la Recuperació de Informació Musical per a l'educació pianística, eixamplant horitzons i proposant nous reptes per a futures investigacions.

Contributions

The list that follows seeks to provide an overview of the main contributions provided with the presented work.

- Redesign an existing automatic piano fingering proposal to work at the level of a human. It is not optimal but fulfils the comfortable fingering principle.
- Develop a reinforcement learning algorithm that can learn to be flexible like a human when generating piano fingering.
- Collect a progressive difficulty dataset grounded on Bela Bartók Mikrokosmos Sz 107. It is compiled in a sheet-music machine-readable format.
- Computationally validate that piano technique is an important feature to characterize difficulty.
- Create algorithms to detect the local difficulty of a musical piece through the global difficulty annotations.
- Design a series of descriptors to understand the relationship between the piano accompaniment and the soloist.
- Develop a prototype to show how current automatic composition systems can be biased to generate an individualised music repertoire for each student.
- The development of several preprocessing pipelines and web tools to visualise corpora and scores that will help us in future research.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Technology must be at the service of music, not the way around. This dissertation wants to be focused on creating **supportive technology for music performers**. In particular, it scopes potential applications from the Music Information Retrieval community to the **Music Education** field. E-learning Music Education has increased progressively since the 20th, from the first masterclasses recordings to the current industry. The last year, e-learning has been imposed by force on many music students due to the COVID19 pandemic, which has allowed us to observe that technology was not ready for the situation. The other main component of the present dissertation is **piano** music instrument, which has been chosen as a case study given the resources available. In addition, we want to get an overview of music education systems grounded on **symbolic music** data, an exploratory analysis for further research.

Therefore, the **main goal** of this master final project is contributing technologically to the different aspects of learning piano in its most global viewpoint, from technique to accompaniment and composition, grounded uniquely on symbolic data.

1.1 Motivation

Piano performance has been the central axis in my longstanding music studies. The background acquired with the courses of analysis and fundamentals of composition, among others, were of great help in my bachelor thesis pursuing research on harmony [1, 2, 3]. However, I did not fully exploit the core of my musical education in the research. I must note that before this master thesis, I was already satisfied and grateful for these last years of bringing together my two passions, music and technology. The complementary music courses can help me to conduct other research challenges. Nevertheless, in the presented master thesis, I want to use my training as a musician and engineer to the maximum, reaching the knowledge frontier.

In the last years, Music Education has had great convergence with technology in both industry and academia. On the one hand, the music education industry is turning to e-learning, with the modernisation of traditional companies and significant investments in start-ups. On the other hand, we can directly apply many of the advances of the last 20 years in Machine Learning and Music Information Retrieval to Music Education. However, as will be in Chapter 2, although some music technology communities such as New Interfaces for Musical Expression have invested notable efforts in Music Education, there are few research proposals from Music Information Retrieval. Research and development of data-driven technology is a must to improve the music education experience and democratise it.

1.2 Objectives

The main challenge of this master thesis is to explore the potential data-driven technologies to enhance Music Education from symbolic data. Music machine-readable symbolic data, such as sheet music, contains more accessible music semantic information than audio. Therefore, it can lead to multiple new applications. Aiming to improve current state-of-the-art methods for piano related technologies, we will follow five specific goals:

1. Create models to bring real supportive feedback to piano students.
2. Model the piano technique to describe sheet music.
3. Model the piano pieces difficulty from the technique perspective
4. Model the relationship between the lead-voice and the piano accompaniment.
5. Generate automatically individualised repertory with a particular difficulty.
6. Develop interfaces for exploring corpora based on points 3 and 4.
7. Discover new horizons for further research.

1.3 Approach

To meet the objective defined in Section 1.2, we establish a methodological path that covers the following steps.

To address the purpose, we will first limit the piano technique to hand and finger movements, which we can generate through piano fingering. To this end, we will explore the use of existing automatic fingering systems or the creation of new ones. We will create a meaningful learning representation from the fingering piano to model the difficulty. Besides, we will create a dataset to evaluate this difficulty because there is not public dataset available. The difficulty models shall be meaningful from a musical perspective. The models will have inference mechanisms for showing the local difficulty in a shorter-term view. Finally, we will create interfaces to show the local difficulty as feedback.

Another objective is to model the relationship between the soloist and the piano accompaniment. We will design descriptors to model piano support for accompaniment from three dimensions: melodic, rhythmic and harmonic. Besides, we will analyse the correlation between the mentioned relationship and a pedagogical-motivated difficulty corpus. Moreover, we will create web tools for exploring the corpus across the three dimensions.

Finally, we will use the technical difficulty model to create musical pieces automatically biased to a particular difficulty level.

To sum up, the conducted research seeks to find challenges and pitfalls in data-driven Music Education research, useful for further study.

1.4 Structure of the dissertation

The paragraphs that follow attempt to provide an overview of how this dissertation will be organised. Firstly, We have given a rough idea of why and how we're going to do it in this initial Chapter 1.

In Chapter 2, we will deal with several proposals that have been made in the field of the study of data-driven Music Education. In the next state-of-the-art chapter, Chapter 3, we will analyse all the piano technique previous proposals from a multi-disciplinary view, that is, music theory, piano theory, technological, musicological and cognitive point of view.

In Chapter 4, we will propose two-piano fingering generation systems. The first proposal will redesign an existing automatic piano fingering proposal, Pianoplayer. The second proposal will be a reinforcement learning algorithm that can be flexible like a human when it generates piano fingering.

In Chapter 5 we will research the relationship between piano technique and difficulty. We will propose a progressive difficulty dataset grounded on Béla Bartók Mikrokosmos Sz 107 in a sheet-music machine-readable format. Besides, we will validate computationally that piano technique is a vital feature to characterise difficulty. Moreover, we will design algorithms to detect the local difficulty of a musical piece, although global difficulty annotations are the unique ground-truth available.

In Chapter 6, we will study the relationship between the accompaniment and the lead melody on a symbolic corpus containing pedagogic-designed piano accompaniments for classical and Rock & Pop singing lessons. We will derive accompaniment support features on three dimensions: melody, rhythm, and harmony to accomplish the

challenge.

In Chapter 7 we will develop a prototype to show how current automatic composition systems can be biased to generate an individualised repertoire of music for each student.

To sum up, in Chapter 8 we will discuss the multiple challenges and future opportunities of applying data-driven technologies based on symbolic music data to Music Education. Finally, we will list in Chapter 9 the contributions and conclude this exploratory analysis about enhancing Piano Music Education with data-driven technologies from symbolic data.

Chapter 2

Computational Music Education Review

Learning to play music is as old as humanity itself, dating back to the dawn of time. Formal Music Education can be traced back to the Hebrews in Egypt or the ancient Greeks [4]. In the 10th and 11th centuries, educators and theorists like Odo of Cluny and Guido d'Arezzo investigated how to teach these newly developed music notations [5]. academic interest in Music Education was deprecated [6] when universities abandoned music as a part of their curriculum during the Renaissance. Music was added later to the curriculum of some universities following the Protestant Reformation [6]. The conservatory model emerged in the nineteenth century (outside of Italy), institutionalizing the education area. Music Education had a significant evolution in the XX century. Several approaches were developed or received refinement in the mentioned century, educators introduced many new music methods, and the Music Education industry emerged.

E-learning Music Education has increased a lot in the last years. We can see this in the increase of Music Education start-ups ¹ and big traditional Music Education companies also investing in this field ². Besides, research in this area is significant

¹[yousician.com](#) - [playlumi.com](#) - [flowkey.com](#) - [skoove.com](#)

²[rcmusic.com](#) - [trinitycollege.com/qualifications/music](#)

with many proposals in recent years from Music Technology. The New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME) community have had more than 100 papers in relation with Music Education, and the topic popularity has also been growing over the years [7]. In the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) community, there have also been some few proposals [8, 9]. All aforementioned demonstrates the social importance of creating technology for Music Education.

Many fields related to traditional music performance can benefit from the last years' symbolic domain advances in Music Information Retrieval and Computational Musicology. Music Education, the discipline that studies how music is learned and taught, can be benefited from automatic score analysis. However, other related fields, such as music libraries or music editorials, can also benefit from a detailed analysis of music scores and performance.

The remainder of this section is structured as follows. Section 2.1 details the previous proposals in Music Performance Assessment and in particular the Section 2.2 expose the proposals carried out at MTG. Section 2.3 addresses the previous proposed music education methods. Section 2.4 and Section 2.5 states other fields where difficulty and performance assessment can be beneficial. Finally, Section 2.6 draws the conclusions of this review about the relationship between Music Education and Music Technology.

2.1 Previous Proposals

Several computational technologies have been proposed in recent years to improve Music Education and Music Performance Assessment. The automatic evaluation of musical performance is crucial in these systems. However, human evaluation is often subjective, making the development of an automated evaluation system difficult. Assessment of Music Education can focus on many dimensions of music such as pitch and timing accuracy, musical expression or technique. However, the parameters sometimes are subjective [10]. Moreover, we can use cross-cutting technologies for evaluating performers to evaluate automatic composition systems in a

more expressive way [11].

All the research produced in the Music Performance Assessment area should be interpretable and explainable. Data-driven approaches to music are very subjective. They can be biased (due in some cases to the datasets' size or human errors and subjectivity). It is necessary to know clearly from traditional Music Education what the reasoning was for the decision making. The European Union introduced "the explanation right" in the General Data Protection Right (GDPR) to deal with future AI problems. Machines' decision making about humans must have a fair and transparent process. Therefore, explainability is a legal mandate to automatically assess music students without human supervision to obtain a diploma. Fully interpretable models would also be needed to filter participants in large music castings. For all these reasons, interpretability and explainability are vital concepts for Music Performance Assessment.

To sum up, the number of related proposals have increased in the last years. Nevertheless, most of the proposals could not operate currently on an industrial scale in Europe to get official certificates. It is because learned features, in the end-to-end music assessment systems, tend to be abstract and can not be understood [12]. However, other approaches try to combine low-level descriptors with music descriptors for music assessment [13, 9, 14]. Explainability can incorporate these types of algorithms into the music industry in Europe.

2.2 The MTG Previous Proposals

The previous MTG proposals share the motivation of having a constant dialogue with the student [13, 15, 16]. In the Music Critic project [13], it is not only essential to output a mark of how the students are playing, but it is also crucial to tell them which elements contribute to having a particular mark. The explainability challenge is followed in Eremenko et al. [9] where a Music Education Assessment prototype is developed, and the open challenges in the Music Education Assessment are presented. Similarly, the project derived from Morsi's master thesis [15] does

not want exclusively to classify a score by difficulty. The most important thing is to explain why the score is classified in that way. Recently Dalmazzo et al. [17] proposed a method to assess the student violin articulations quality with the gestures captured by a MYO.

Many proposals were made within the TELMI project related to Music Education ³. Most of them related to the assessment of string instruments or jazz guitar. The musical performance assessment is based on pitch and onset accuracy, but very few pay attention to other essential aspects of performance, such as sound quality or timbre. Giraldo et al. research [18] expose a violin music assessment system modelled with Machine Learning techniques and paying attention to the mentioned aspects and perception dimension. This another proposal also from Giraldo et al. [19] conduct research in modelling the musical expression in jazz guitar music.

Another MTG project related to performance assessment was PHENICX. In this project, academic researchers, music institutions, musicians and the music industry worked together. Their mission was to use all the modalities that classical music provide: sound, image, physical movements and symbolic scores. The aim was to analyse the characteristics of a piece and analyse the differences between multiple performances of the same piece and the way multiple audiences perceive the musical work. This project was very focused in the concert experience with multiple publications in source separation [20], score-informed source separation [21], melody and pitch recognition [22, 23], score following, score piano and violin expressiveness [24] and conductor gesture modelling [25].

There have also been researching works about analysing music performance in ensemble groups. The research is focused around two quartet datasets: EEP [26] and QUARTET [27]. Acquired data includes the audio, motion capture, ambient tracks and individual tracks acquired through contact microphones.

Most of the mentioned works were related to the creation and development of Repovizz [28], a web platform for supporting the performer experience. Before the cre-

³Available at: http://telmi.upf.edu/?page_id=507

ation of Repovizz, there were also several researchers working in Music Performance Assessment. The Esteban Maestre research lines focused on creating a mapping between the physical gestures and the audio domain. The research works were very focused on string instruments [29] and saxophone. At the same time, there were other performance assessment proposals focused on vocal and singing [30].

2.3 Music Education Methods

There are numerous corpora about Music Education, but the music data is often not digitalised. Most institutionalised teaching systems follow their curriculum guides, such as municipal, regional or national schools or conservatories. In addition, there are music methods designed by composers, teachers or organisations, such as examination boards. While the music teachers follow the music curriculum in their region or country to dictate soft instructional techniques, many teachers depend significantly on one of the numerous music method approaches that arose in the last century and grew fast throughout the later part of the 20th century. The challenge is that many of these collections are still copyrighted and require considerable effort to fix before transcribing with Optical Music Recognition software [31].

Classical composers and teachers were the first to create compositions with a pedagogical path. Many composers write studies focused on learning the technique, such as Czerny, Chopin, Vaccai, Paganini or Rachmaninoff studies. In addition, other composers have composed works that range progressively from easy to difficult difficulties, such as Béla Bartók's Mikrokosmos Sz. 107.

In the 20th century, several pedagogues composed and compiled collections of separate pieces of music at different levels of difficulty. Émile Jaques-Dalcroze created the Dalcroze method with copyright expired last year. We will review the Dalcroze method, the Carl Orff method and the Suzuki method. The Dalcroze approach is separated into three basic concepts: solfège, improvisation, and eurhythmics. Eurhythmics, often known as "rhythmic gymnastics," teaches principles of rhythm, structure, and musical expression via movement and is the concept for which Dal-

croze is most known. It focuses on giving students bodily awareness and experience with music through training involving all senses, especially the kinematic. Carl Orff method is a method that teaches the notions of melody and rhythm from the human body, then moves on to small percussion instruments, designed exclusively for this method, and finally begins to play a traditional classical-western instrument. Lastly, the Suzuki method is a music curriculum and teaching philosophy developed by Japanese violinist and pedagogue Shinichi Suzuki in the mid-20th century. The method seeks to establish a learning environment for music similar to the linguistic context of learning a native language.

Primary music examination boards, such as Trinity College London or ABRSM, have created other primary music curricula. The examination boards compile works composed in-house for their curricula or compiling music pieces written by other composers.

2.4 Digital libraries

Digital Libraries have traditionally included multimedia material in their content. The multiple types that musical data can take, the need for links between them, and the value of academic and historical context knowledge necessarily involve particular attention to promote substantive interaction with the musical content [32].

Computers cannot interpret images of sheet music directly. Computer scores must be in a machine-readable format such as Musicxml, Humdrum or Mei, among others, to be analysed by a computer. Although there have been many advances in the field of Optical Music Recognition to convert images into machine-readable formats [31], the current proposals are not as accurate as human performance. Moreover, other formats as Midi or piano-roll formats are machine-readable. However, these formats lost information, not encoding information such as articulations, hands, editor's fingers or others.

Extensive collections of sheet music are challenging to organise and to make accessible to users. Extensive collections such as IMSLP, for example, have a repertoire of

more than 500,000 musical works ⁴. Therefore there is a need for criteria to organise them. Some IMSLP community initiatives have carried out the construction of a scores ranking by instrument and difficulty ⁵. However, non-expert users carry out the classification, and there are only a tiny subset of scores ranked, less than 1000 scores in the piano case.

Other proprietary examples of digital libraries are Musescore ⁶ or Musicalion ⁷. The first one does not have a ranking for the scores. The second one has a hierarchy with three categories: low, medium and high. This ranking is provided by the users when uploading the score files to the webpage. Therefore it doesn't have an objective standard. However, It would be the most extensive digital score's collection with difficulty annotated.

Traditional libraries are advancing in their digitalisation in the last decades and, in particular, music libraries too. It is shown in the Europeana project foundation ⁸, a digital association of the major European libraries. Moreover, there is a increasing number of music collections in the internet archive ⁹ provided in part by traditional libraries or other research projects [32]. Furthermore, there is an extensive research community related to Digital Music Libraries, which meets at the Digital Libraries for Musicology conference (DfLM), growing over the last eight editions ¹⁰. This year 2021, the meeting will be held in association with the International Association of Music Libraries, Archives and Documentation Centres (IAML), the largest conference of music libraries, demonstrating traditional libraries' interest in researching the digitalisation of their archives.

⁴https://imslp.org/wiki/Main_Page

⁵<https://imslp.org/wiki/Special:DiffPage/DiffMain/1>

⁶<https://musescore.org>

⁷<https://www.musicalion.com>

⁸Available at: <https://www.europeana.eu/es>

⁹Available at: <https://archive.org/details/freemusicarchive>

¹⁰<https://dlfm.web.ox.ac.uk/>

2.5 Diversity in the repertoire

Sound and Music Computing technologies provides new ways to analyse and search unknown music repertory. Nowadays, most of the repertoires designed for Music Education are limited to a set of works [33]. Repertoires often fall in a problem of diversity and it does not allow students to explore alternative musical pieces [34]. Many students and teachers prefer to restrict their musical pieces chosen within the syllabus in many Music Education systems. Consequently, this prevents little-known musical pieces and composers from ever being performed by music students. Furthermore, It prevents local repertoires from being performed [35].

The piano repertoire is also limited in the Music Education pathway. For example, in Spain's case, the three great composers who receive the most attention from teachers are Granados, Albéniz and Falla. An example of this is that only these three authors are intensely analysed in the review of the history of piano technique [36] mentioned in Section 3.1.

Automatic analysis of extensive pedagogical corpus can derive in merging the entire jazz, classical, pop and rock repertoire of an instrument as a common study pathway. With this aim in mind, it is crucial to have clear the qualities and skills that a music student needs to know in each grade from an objective perspective. Besides, students can learn some instruments from very different classical traditions. For example in the violin case, it is an instrument present in Western tradition, but plays an important role in Makam Ottoman music, Andalusian music, Carnatic and Hindustan music. However, the western classical music examination boards ignore these traditions as repertoire source.

2.6 Conclusions

Although there have been several previous proposals, many questions remain open, such as the most important learning features or to create larger datasets with more detailed information. Most Music Education works are written on a physical medium, on scores, in classical music or with lead sheets, in jazz. Nevertheless,

this information does not play an essential role in the previous proposals. Moreover, in the European Union, end-to-end models cannot evaluate people if they are not explainable. For all these reasons, the area offers very attractive challenges in the coming years.

Chapter 3

Modelling Piano Technique

The study of the keyboard technique is as old as the keyboard instruments themselves [36]. There have been many attempts to conceptualise the piano technique over the years [37, 38]. Technique refers to how the piano is played physically. Piano technique is related to how a musician plays the piano at all levels. The technique can be analysed at a local structure resolution, individually on each note, or in more global structures, as pattern or designs, scale/arpeggio/broken chord [39]. The technique is learned progressively in most Piano Music Education methods, so it is a good descriptor of difficulty. This section aims to find methodologies, inside and outside Music Technology, to model piano technique computationally.

This section is divided into nine sections. Section 3.1 exposes the history of the piano technique according to Chiantore . Sections 3.2 3.3 3.4 review three of the most well-known classical piano technique books. Sections 3.5 3.6 detail several methods for modelling piano technique from a low-level perspective. Section 3.7 states some attempts to detect difficulty partially thanks to the piano technique. Finally, Section 3.8 draws the conclusions of this review about the relationship between score difficulty and the piano technique.

3.1 History of the piano technique (according to Luca Chiantore)

The book [36] is structured chronologically: from the earliest surviving documents about keyboard music through the Viennese school and the romantic piano to compositions from the end of the 20th century. There is a strong emphasis on the study of the historical repertoire. Finally, there is an extensive appendix full of ideas for this thesis about the history of the theoretic Piano Technique.

This work tries to answer the research question about whether the ideal technique exists. Luca Chiantore states that performance is valid as long as it reflects a precise aesthetic approach. But among the options, there is one of particular importance. The one that each composer had in mind when he was creating his works. Musicians perform earlier works with contemporary style when early music began to be revived at the end of the 18th century and until the 20th-century dawn. Pianists believed that musical works improved by exploiting the new modern pianos and new techniques. Gradually, musicians realise that playing with the era's piano technique improves the piece understanding. These ideas are relevant for this master thesis. First, they suggest that **not only difficulty is related to piano technique**, but also style. Second, they indicate we have to **stratify by music style or composer** to avoid biases.

Leaving aside the evolution of piano technique in this book, the most exciting part of this historical review for this master thesis is the appendix: technique from 1850 to the present day. Theoretical studies on technique were born in romanticism, and the two elements that piano theoreticians first analysed were hand position and fingering. The figure of **Theodor Leschetizsky stands out** as a master of masters on the teaching of piano technique. The two principles were that technique should be individualised for each student and born out of the score and fingering analysis score. Another crucial author is Tobias Augustus Matthay, a great theorist of piano technique, famous for his classifications in tables and footnotes of considerable size, which shows his work's detail. Another work analysed is the physician Steinhausen

work. It is the first approach to scientific the physiology of the piano technique and his analysis of the hand positions as tension and relaxation. On the other hand, it ends with a review of the XX century's great piano technique theorists, with multiple references. This appendix suggest that hand position and fingering are two fundamental elements of the piano technique.

Chiantore describes and analyses the changes that have taken place in piano performance, taking into account the writing, the physiological part of the technique and the more detailed aspects of interpretation. He builds his work on the systematic study of documentary sources of a diverse nature: scores, manuscripts, pedagogical methods (some of them little known or even unpublished), personal writings, iconographic material, concert reviews and recordings. This book can be considered a **large documentary corpus**, collecting data often difficult to access.

3.2 Heinrich Neuhaus: The art of piano playing

The book exposed in this section [40] is considered mandatory reading by many pianists. It is devoted to average piano teachers and their pupils. Heinrich Neuhaus was a musician, pianist, director of the Moscow Conservatoire and founder of the famous Moscow Central Music School for specially gifted children, devoting his life entirely to teaching. Amongst his pupils were famous pianists as Radu Lupu, Emil Gilels or Sviatoslav Richter. The book is divided into seven chapters focusing on many aspects related to piano performing. The first four chapters focus on internal pianistic elements from the music artistic image creation to piano fingering and technique. The fifth and sixth chapters are about external pianistic aspects, first the relationship between teacher and pupil and second the pianists as concert performers. In this section, we will review the four first chapters focusing on the technique one.

Heinrich Neuhaus dedicates the first chapter to understanding how a pianist transmits when he plays. The second one is about acquiring rhythm skills. The third one is about tone quality. Lastly, the fourth chapter is about piano technique with

an appendix on piano fingering. Neuhaus states **students learn the music skills progressively**, especially piano technique and musicality. Moreover, he writes **instrument technique is subordinated** to the rest of the musician skills.

He starts the piano fingering appendix by stating when people think about fingering comes to mind, "so many men, so many opinions" due to the multiple possible fingering good combinations. He writes fingering is good when rendering a composition allowing the most accurate version of the music. Moreover, Neuhaus states fingering has to be flexible for each music composition and pianist. Although his statements are reasonable, the examples are a bit poor. The first is about a scale with every two notes linked with a slur. It can not be fingered as a legato scale. It only means fingering has to consider articulations. The second states fingers annotated by composers have to be respected for all the hands. Even the other fingers of the composition are different depending on the hand. Fingering also has to consider the annotated fingers, more even if the score is an urtext edition.

To sum up, the primary learning of this book is that fingering **is always subordinate to the other aspects of a musical composition**. Moreover, the two statements: fingering has to follow all the elements of music and fingering is a flexible process; are significant for this master thesis.

3.3 Albert Nieto: La digitación pianística (1988)

Several key concepts of piano technique can be derived from this work [38]. From the prologue, it is emphasised that good fingering is directly related to the piece's difficulty. Chapter I also presented that most piano pedagogues agree that before starting to work on a piano music piece mechanically, the fingering should be established and noted down from the score. Besides, piano fingering should fulfil two fundamental properties (P1, P2) and be influenced by three factors (F1, F2, F3).

Protect the musical content (P1): The musical content of the work must be preserved in all its facets: articulation, tempo, dynamics, rhythm, style and character.

Comfortable to perform (P2): This rule is flexible since the facility of execution will depend on the habits of movement that the pianists have acquired, the hand size, the opening of the interdigital spaces and other anatomical characteristics of each hand.

Anticipation (F1): This factor consists of adjusting the fingering at each moment according to the subsequent fingering patterns' needs. Pianists should pay attention to openings, appoggiaturas, double notes, chords, arpeggios, mordents, and arpeggiated patterns. Naturally, they will also anticipate the necessary fingers to accommodate the maximum number of future notes and patterns.

Simultaneity (F2) It is crucial to finger both hands simultaneously to realise the effectiveness of some combinations with the other hand's notes. On the other hand, we will also have the opportunity to appreciate if there is symmetry or parallelism between the two hands. This symmetry is related to the difficulty.

Pedalling (F3). Both, the resonance pedal and the tonal pedal, give the hand greater action freedom, allowing it to adapt to new positions without the danger of losing legato or retaining a particular sonority.

These are the general principles that any automatic piano fingering system should consider and follow. Although it may seem obvious, Albert Nieto expresses them in a clear and concise way.

Chapter XI of the book introduces the concept of **handing** for piano fingering. "Handing" as opposed to fingering is the way of fingering proposed by Leschetizky. With this method, the unit is not the finger but the fingers' group (the hand). It is possible to think of group combinations that minimise the effort by placing the hands on the keyboard without playing (as if it were a flattened chord). The aim is to minimise the number of finger groups or hand positions for a piece of music. Handing is fundamental for any study of piano technique because, intuitively, this method can easily model computationally. In subsection 3.4 there is a further reading of this topic

In the third part of the book, from chapter XVIII to chapter XXI, the relationship between compositional elements and fingering is analysed. All these elements are closely related to the concept of difficulty. Albert Nieto states that passages with **polyphonic writing have additional difficulty in fingering and technique**. Repetitive patterns or progressions have to be fingered in the same way, so once a pattern has been learned, the work's difficulty decreases. On the other hand, the book highlights the importance of fingering to reduce the difficulty of playing in passages with **symmetry or parallelism between the hands**. Finally, piano pieces' difficulty increases when they are written with **the two hands very close together** or when the same design is interchanged between the right and left hand.

3.4 Malwine Bree: The groundwork of the Leschetizky method.

Theodor Leschetizky, one of the most famous piano teachers of the XIX century [36], writes nothing about his methodology. Many of his students later transcribed his lessons in one way or another [36]. However, the only person authorised (by Leschetizky) to explain his method was Malwine Bree [41, 42].

To my honored master

Professor Theodor Leschetizky

Twenty years ago I became your pupil, and for more than ten years you have considered me worthy to hold the office of your assistant. Let this be my justification for publishing, in this book, what you have taught me throughout this long period, and what I in turn have tested on hundreds of pupils.

I am well aware that a finished pianist can no more be formed by a theoretical method alone than a painter or sculptor can be trained by books on painting or sculpture ; nevertheless, my book may claim a certain right to exist, if only as a welcome reminder to many former

disciples of the Leschetizky School of their early instruction, and, for the later pupils, as affording a correct idea of the basis of that School.

Following the spirit of the latter, I have been at pains to avoid pedantry. My work does not aim at a slavish observance of rule, but is meant to be a guide to fine and correct piano-playing. I am rendered the more desirous of attaining this end by reason of the honorable distinction conferred upon my work by the illustrations of your own hand.

I thank you most sincerely for this distinction, and beg you to accept the dedication of this book. Thus it only returns to the fountain-head whence we all draw.

Vienna, February, 1902.

Malwine Bree

Fingering is a central theme throughout the work. Bree describes the types of fingerings for several piano designs: finger exercises, scales, octaves, chords, arpeggios, the glissando, embellishments, dynamics, the pedal, and other structures. These designs are the fundamental elements of the piano technique and can be learned separately from the musical works. However, one time the student learns a unit design, can generalise it in all the pieces and with similar fingering. After mentioning fingering rules throughout the book, always minimising hand positions, the fingering chapter is written at the end of the book. In this chapter, if the piece requires it, **pianists can break all the rules mentioned above.**

The fingering method described by Albert Nieto [38] and ascribed to Leschetizky is not defined in the book. However, this book highlights the relationship between difficulty and simple fingering in the fingering chapter. The mentioned association between difficulty and fingering is shown in the previous quotation. The absence of the piano fingering follows the idea that there is no generalisable method of technique for all people, as is shown the previous quotation. A Letter from T. Leschetizky in the prologue of *The groundwork of the Leschetizky method* book.

Fingering is good when easy; — provided that the effect is the same.

Only the easy player can also play confidently and finely.

The chord section points out that **fingering flat chords is the same as fingering broken chords**. This intuitive concept can be used in fingering systems where the chords are not fingered [43, 39]

Finally, one critical concept from Leschetizky’s teachings is that the **technique can be described from the score**. However, to carry out this challenge, all the possible data, especially the piece’s final tempo, should be considered.

3.5 Automatic Fingering Detection

Piano Fingering consists of selecting the successive or simultaneous order of the fingers to be played in a musical work by coding them on or under the corresponding notes [38]. Different approaches have been adopted to solve this task from the first Parncutt et al. proposal [44]. Moreover, musical methods have been created to make automatic fingering without computers in improvisations and piano sight reading [45, 46]. Piano fingering is a topic with a wide community. We can see this topic popularity in the thirty active projects are in GitHub ¹

The piano fingering proposals fall into two categories, expert systems and data-driven systems. In the expert systems, fingering is generated from constraints or rules [44], or cost functions [43]. On the other hand, several data-driven fingering techniques have also been tried, such as the Nakamura et al. [39, 47] proposals based on Hidden Markov Models and deep learning architectures.

The Parncutt et al. [44] research evaluates his method on a few excerpts with multiple piano fingering possibilities. Although it is one of the simplest methods, an expert system with several tens of rules, it matches more than the other no data-driven techniques with human annotations, as Nakamura et al. stated [47]. The Parncutt et al. method is improved by Balliauw et al. [48] with a variable neigh-

¹At: <https://github.com/search?q=piano+fingering&type=repositories>

bourhood search algorithm. In this research, they claim that their algorithm works correctly for polyphonic passages. However, although they show a few examples, they do not deliver a detailed evaluation to compare with other proposals. All these research projects do not have the code available.

In Hart et al. [49], the first cost-based attempt is made with a dynamic programming algorithm. However, it is a limited method, with hand-crafted costs for the transition between two states, only valid for monophonic musical pieces and not supporting all possible musical compositions. In Prisco et al. [50], another local search algorithm is developed with genetic programming techniques, and it learns the fitness function from the data.

There is an automatic piano fingering project based on a cost function with the code available: PianoPlayer [43]. The algorithm works by minimising the fingers speed needed to play a sequence of notes or chords by searching through feasible combinations of fingerings. It is based entirely on dynamic programming without the aid of rules, and the cost function can be used as a difficulty heuristic, even on scores fingered by other systems. Moreover, most of them before mentioned techniques ignore the editorial fingers. Marco Musy, the PianoPlayer author, affirms that his system [43] support this feature, but currently, due to integration problems, it does not work.

In the automatic fingering data-driven path, the proposals of Nakamura et al. stand out. The first proposal of 2014 [39] is based on the first data-driven system for piano fingering proposed by Yonebayashi et al. [51] and based on HMM models. However, Yonebayashi et al. analyses each hand separately, and in Nakamura et al., the statistical method use the two hands for fingering, as the technique book recommendations. Besides, in Nakamura et al. [39], the challenge is creating a piano reduction system constrained with the HMM piano fingering system. Although the piano reduction system is not finished in that research, two methods are exposed: a difficulty recognition system and a voice separator, both from piano fingering based. The first one extracts the piece difficulty of a heuristic obtained from an HMM piano fingering system. The voice separator is a related HMM model to calculate

which note belongs to which hand. This last system, the voice separation system, is exciting since there is no direct relation between the pentagram part, the voice and the hand that plays it. This voice separator system could be advantageous in many applications.

Finally, Nakamura et al. [47] in 2020 submit a much more mature proposal. They present a dataset of 150 works annotated by multiple annotators, new evaluation metrics, a refined HMM for piano fingering and the first neural networks proposal to carry out piano fingering. However, the results on such a small dataset finally qualify the HMM as the best model. Also, Nakamura et al. [47] analyse human and automatic piano fingering subjectivity. Another problem stated is that the state-space explodes with the length n of the note sequence analysed by the HMM, $88^n * 5^n$. So intuitively, to process a larger length of note sequences, in more massive datasets, neural networks can approximate a vast state-space.

The most advanced proposals are Nakamura et al. (data-driven) and PianoPlayer (local optimisation). Also, both proposals suggest methods to analyse difficulty from a local level to the note and finger. Even though there is still much scope for improvement, with the dataset presented by Nakamura et al., the different systems can be evaluated, even the data-driven ones, allowing simple entry to the field.

3.6 Hand Position Detection

There are no related studies on modelling musical tasks from hand positions on the symbolic domain. However, the piano technique books presented on the section 2.2 to highlight the importance of positions and position changes. However, there is a related research field based on the kinematics of piano performance [52, 53, 54]. This lines of research emphasise that the weight of the whole hand often resides on a single finger. The Furuya et al. [54] research highlights 64 different positions in which the weight can reside. But the lack of transparent results difficult to replicate the mentioned positions. In addition, other researches tries to detect the hand position with physical-computing [55] approaches.

3.7 Difficulty approach

The concept of musical difficulty itself causes ambiguity. The musical aspects that are difficult for one person are not necessarily difficult for another. Moreover, music performance difficulty has many dimensions. Musical pieces that have not very demanding technical performative requirements could require an extremely high sound sensitivity, e.g. the piano repertoire of Erik Satie. Many of the proposals for computationally measuring difficulty focus on specific dimensions of music. However, in the research of Nakamura et al. [39, 47] it is proposed to measure difficulty using only fingering. The rationale for this proposal is that if some fingers are more likely because they are very often, they have less difficulty.

The Nakamura difficulty analysis approach is not easy to evaluate. First, the dataset used is not pedagogically motivated because the data is very concert-oriented. Second, Although data-augmentation assumptions are suitable for a fingering piano system, they are not correct for assessing difficulty. For example, when fingering, each note in a note's sequence has the same finger if it is fingered from back to front as from front to back. However, this is meaningless when assessing difficulty. In the data-augmentation preprocessing, Nakamura et al. train with one sequence and the reverse sequence. Therefore, both series of notes will be equally frequent. However, the opposite note's pattern can not be present as frequently as the original, so it does not have the same difficulty. Lastly, the dataset has a limited size of 130 works not stratified by difficulty level. Nevertheless, the proof of concept has good results. So it is proved that fingering, one of the basics of piano technique, has an empirical correlation with difficulty.

Sebastian et al. [8], and Chen et al. [56] works propose different dimensional spaces for measuring difficulty in the piano repertoire. However, in both studies, the repertoire used by beginning students is not extensively represented. On the other hand, neither approach uses more than 100 scores.

Morsi master thesis [15] presents the concept of difficulty in the piano score and a set of descriptors related to it. In addition to the benchmark set, Morsi proposes

twenty additional descriptors and test their pros and cons by seeing how they can define complexity better than the benchmark set alone. Despite the positive effects of the new features, there is also more potential for growth. On the other hand, the proposal evaluates Nakamura's method on a new dataset. The mentioned dataset is designed to assess the difficulty more than the original Nakamura dataset and has third musical pieces for every nine grades. The results with Nakamura's proposal are the best, so it proves that piano technique is one of the relevant features to characterise difficulty.

3.8 Conclusions

The field of piano technique has been extensively studied over the last 200 years. We can extract the music piece's technique from sheet music, as stated by Theodor Leschetizsky [41]. Fingering a score allows us to know all the hand and finger movements of music work, fundamental descriptors to understand the technique. Therefore automatic piano fingering systems can let us describe the piano technique of extensive collections of scores. Moreover, the technique is not only directly related to difficulty, as Albert Nieto described [38], but all other dimensions of musical skills are related to technique as Neuhaus analysed [40]. Nowadays, there are already significant proposals about the relationship between piano fingering and the difficulty of a score [47, 15]. There are several open challenges in describing the piano technique and understanding the difficulty of a score, but this chapter has allowed us to review some of the work proposed from multiple disciplines in the last 200 years.

Chapter 4

Piano Fingering Generation

Piano fingering is a task extensively studied in Music Theory. In particular, from the theory of piano technique, as shown in Section 3.1. In addition, there have been multiple proposals on Music Technology, as stated in Section 3.5 from expert systems [44] to local search algorithms [49] through completely data driven [39, 47].

This chapter is the foundation of future chapters. The aim is to learn the basics of piano technique grounded on the generative models of fingering. We will use the piano technique concept later to understand the difficulty concept, Chapter 5, and automatically compose piano pieces, Chapter 7.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Section 4.1 details the motivations of this study. Section 4.2 addresses the challenges. Section 4.3 expose the data used to evaluate the two piano fingering algorithms detailed on Section 4.4 4.5. Finally, Section 4.6 draws the conclusions of the study.

4.1 Motivations

Specific problems are challenging from a supervised learning perspective. Piano fingering is one of these challenges, as will be explained in the remainder of this section.

The anatomy: there are certain positions not feasible for the human anatomy,

such as a 5-1 with the right hand in an ascending interval. Anatomical constraints are very detailed information but are difficult to encode in an statistical way [47]. Although a neural network can encode this information better, there is currently not enough data to achieve high accuracy, as Nakamura states [47].

The rules defined by the piano schools: rules are varying from one piano school to another, e.g. changing the finger in the same key as in organ technique. However, some rules prevail in all schools. For example, pianists cannot cross the hand from a black key with finger 1. The constraints encoding is the same problem as the previous point.

The size of the hand: pianists can not set certain fingering sequences or even conduct specific movements with small hands. There have been great pianists with large hands; see Franz Liszt and great pianists with small hands; see Vladimir Ashkenazy. The size of the hand does not matter for piano playing, but the technical strategies and, therefore, the fingering change enormously. We would require multiple annotations for different hands, but mentioned ground-truth currently do not exist.

The individual technique: two pianists may have different needs with the same hand size. For example, one pianist could have the left hand not as developed as another one, and the fingering should be different.

The solution space: Many combinations of fingering are proper. However, only certain combinations are optimal for a given human, and this distribution of fingers changes a lot from one pianist to another. The datadriven options with few data bias easily.

To sum up, there are two fundamental properties of piano technique, as presented by Albert Nieto and reviewed in Section 3.3: Protect the musical content and Comfortable to perform. If the system fulfils these two rules, the fingering is valid. The first fundamental property is binary, protect or does not protect. However, the second one varies over a wide range. A fingering piano system should give the most comfortable possible for a particular pianist. In contrast, supervised proposals are biased towards how particular individuals, the annotators, play. Perhaps annotat-

ing multiple pieces played by hundreds of pianists could be coded into an expert system, but this is expensive, time-consuming and costly to achieve. However, there are other options, as proposed in this chapter.

Finally, when the moment arises, any of the above rules can be violated for a more significant musicality benefit, as stated in Section 3.2. However, the mentioned flexibility is complicated to codify in an expert system but straightforwardly learnt in a supervised learning approach.

4.2 Challenges

The challenge of this chapter is to create systems on the borderline between expert systems and supervised learning. They should consider hand sizes, slurs (and other articulations) and editor's fingers. But at the same time, try to maximise the comfortable concept stated in Chapter 3 and embed this concept for using it in the following chapters. We expose the significant challenges in the following lines:

- Current Piano Fingering systems do not work at human level.
- Moreover, there are systems focused on polyphony [47] or systems focused on monophony [39], but not hybrid systems.
- It is very difficult to compare with other algorithms.
 - There are multiple optimal combinations and even a higher number “right”.
 - Most Previous proposals did not open sourced their code.

For all these reasons, we have decided to extend an existing piano fingering system: Pianoplayer. It seeks to minimise the speed of the fingers when changing from one key to another, i.e. to minimise the effort of moving the pianist's fingers. Moreover, we propose a reinforcement learning system that tries to minimise hand position changes.

Finally, we want to create models and algorithms for describing the piano technique, useful in the following chapters, in particular in Chapter 5 and Chapter 7.

4.3 Dataset

We have used two datasets to evaluate the output fingers quality. The first one, the Pianoplayer dataset, is composed of a limited collection of public musical pieces. The second one grounds on the first Paris conservatoire piano method authored by Louis Adam.

The Pianoplayer dataset includes ten musical pieces of a varying range of difficulty authored by Mozart, Bach, Couperin and Clayderman and three exercises about octaves, scales and chords. We use the Pianoplayer dataset to carry out a first perceptual models evaluation.

The Adam Method was the First Piano Method at the Conservatory of Paris. Louis Adam, the author, spent over four decades, from 1797 through 1842, as Professor of Pianoforte at the Conservatoire de Paris, retiring in 1842. The method includes several exercises or little pieces covering several technique patterns. Therefore, it is a good source for testing the quality of piano fingering. The dataset used has been transcribed by hand to music XML by musicologists linked to the IREMUS research group and the Bibliothèque Nationale de France.

4.4 Pianoplayer

Pianoplayer project ¹ [43] started in 2015 with Marco Musy as the primary contributor. Pianoplayer is based entirely on dynamic programming, and we can use the cost function as a difficulty heuristic, even on scores fingered by another fingering system.

Original Algorithm

Dynamic Programming is an algorithmic approach for addressing an optimisation problem. It breaks down the problem into simpler subproblems and makes use of the fact that the optimal solution to the overall problem depends on the optimal solution to its subproblems. Pianoplayer assumes optimising small subsequences of

¹The project source code is available at <https://github.com/marcomusy/pianoplayer>

a score, we can obtain the final fingering sequence. In particular, the Pianoplayer uses a max subsequence of nine notes.

Velocity is the cost function variable optimised by Pianoplayer. The cost heuristic is the speed of moving a finger from one key to another. Each time a note/key on the keyboard is played with the finger, the hand position is updated. It computes the speed of the following note according to the new hand position. In the first version, Pianoplayer is not considering the piece's tempo.

There are several subproblems of maximal sequence 9. In each subproblem, Pianoplayer performs a brute force combinatorial optimisation over each subproblem. The subproblem result is only the first fingered note of the sub-sequence. Later, the next subproblem starts with the following note. Therefore, for each music note of the musical work, there is a subproblem of maximum size 9. The size of each solution-space subproblem may seem enormous (5^9). Nevertheless, Pianoplayer cut-offs all non-possible states with fingering rules.

Figure 1: Pianoplayer original diagram.

Pianoplayer can handle polyphony, considering pianists cannot play physically two notes simultaneously (in a continuous space of time), so there will always be a fragment of time between each chord note. This assumption leads Pianoplayer to handle

any score as monophony, as is shown in Figure 1. Although the theory is sound and has been implemented by previous authors [39, 47], in practice, Pianoplayer does not work well for polyphonic or even chord music passages.

Contribution

We have invested a great effort in refactoring the code and fixing bugs as part of this master thesis. First, the code has been refactored to make it clean, always considering the cost in time. Besides, we have refactored it to be used as a python library and to evaluate other fingering systems. In addition to the algorithm's core, we have conducted significant changes to support input and output in PIG format, musicXML and MIDI formats natively.

Figure 2: Pianoplayer new release diagram.

Pianoplayer is a complicated system to debug because of its algorithmic scheme. The methodology for debugging the algorithm has been a white box testing technique from Music Theory view. We test Pianoplayer on each of the two datasets presented in section 4.3. We printed it, denoting the score output errors not considered by the algorithm. Finally, we debug each of these problems separately. A final version of Pianoplayer dataset fingered is shown in Appendix A.

We also redesign the algorithm to work with chords, polyphony, and monophony

simultaneously. After this contribution, the unit of the algorithm is not a sequence of monophonic notes but the sequence of simultaneously simultaneous notes, as shown in Figure 2. In other words, if there are two simultaneous notes, they count as one unit in the algorithm input. The contribution has changed the algorithm's structure, cost function, and pruning function above the non-possible states.

The following is an analysis of several fragments showing the evolution of Pianoplayer before and after this master thesis. First, we analyse an excerpt with chords, Figure 3. Consequently, we offer the contribution in polyphonic passages, exploring a section of a Bach fugue, Figure 6.

Figure 3: Chords section before the work scoped in this master thesis.

In the stave of the right hand in Figure 3, we can see how finger 1 is repeated several times, causing unnecessary position changes. In the left hand, this does not happen because the movement of the notes is parallel, but the technical movements are symmetrical due to the symmetrical anatomy of the hands. When Pianoplayer scores a 0 as a finger, it is not able to annotate the finger. We can see Pianoplayer cannot finger many chord notes in the second system in Figure 3. We solve all these problems with the contribution scoped in this master thesis, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Chords section after the work scoped in this master thesis.

Figure 5: Fugue section before the work scoped in this master thesis. Fugue No. 13 in 3 voices in F# Major.

We can see in Figure 6 polyphonic sections was not handled by Pianoplayer previously to this work. Currently, the system is capable of fingering polyphonic passages, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 6: Fugue section after the work scoped in this master thesis. Fugue No. 13 in 3 voices in F# Major.

Finally, Pianoplayer considers legatos and editor’s fingers in the new release. Editor’s finger improvement examines the fingers annotated by the editor as supportive. Therefore, if a musical work has the editor’s fingers annotated, the only fingering feasible state is the editor’s finger. Finally, in Figure 7, Pianoplayer can not finger some notes (annotated with 0s) in the left hand due to anatomy hand constraints.

Figure 7: Air on the G String, Suite No. 3, BWV 1068 fragment. Before editor’s fingering improvement.

Then, we can annotate the notes that can not be annotated by Pianoplayer, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Air on the G String, Suite No. 3, BWV 1068 fragment with some notes fingered by hand

Lastly, the new release of pianoplayer consider the annotated fingers, as shown in Figure 9.

If the note’s articulation is non-legato, the fingering is different than if it is legato. The Legato improvement refers to a change from one slur to another slur. Two notes, not slurred, are fingered, in the same way, as staccato and portato notes. Therefore, the fingering is much more flexible. It means feasible states are any finger, in the two sections between a legato note and another.

4.5 Deep Reinforcement Learning to improve Piano Fingering

The work of this section wants to merge all previous fingering proposals. Previous research is composed, as stated in Section 3.5 by expert systems [44], local search algorithms [43], statistical methods [39] and neural networks [47]. The reinforcement learning method proposed in this section aims to simulate the expert systems, codifying the expert knowledge in the reward function. This method seeks to optimize from note to note each action, the Markov decision process, as statistical proposals. It wants to optimize to a broader term, like the local search algorithms, thanks to the sparsity property of the reinforcement learning methods. Although optimizing in the Markov decision process, the past decisions influence the one-time reward. It considers everything that has already been fingered. Moreover, we will use neural networks to simulate the state space because it became too large in further reinforcement learning proposals. Piano fingering follows several rewards. It has to be easy. In particular, this proposal has to minimize the hand's position.

Figure 11: Deep Q neural network architecture.

This section is only a proof of concept for future piano research. Therefore, it focuses only on the right hand. The left hand can be generalised as the inverse of the right hand, as shown previous proposals [39]. Furthermore, we reduce the decision space considered at maximum. The input is the note played with the corresponding finger and the output the following music note, as shown in Figure 11. The more piano notes considered, the larger the solution space is, 88^n being n the number of deemed

music notes.

Figure 12: Reward function schema.

We divide the reward function into two categories: positive and negative, as shown in 12. The agent receives a favourable reinforcement when it keeps the same hand position and negative reinforcement the opposite. In addition, it is penalised when the agent performs a fingering in a not very comfortable way. The agent is more heavily penalised if the fingering is very uncomfortable or anatomically impossible.

Lastly, we conduct several improvements to improve the algorithm convergence, as shown in Figure 13. A replay buffer randomly takes past experiences in each episode for improving convergence. Double Q-learning improvement, the problem with the DQN algorithm is that it overestimates the real rewards; the Q-values it learns, the DQN thinks it will get a higher bonus than it actually will. Consequently, a simple solution is to separate the action selection and evaluation into two Q-value estimators, each updating the other. The soft update improvement does not update the target network at once but frequently and very little for improving convergence. Additionally, we reduce the Markov decision process to the melodic range of the melody in each scenario/score. Lastly, the learning function is diminished in a logarithmic fashion in each episode from 1 to 0.

We conduct several experiments to test the behaviour of the fingering algorithm with five experiments. In the first test, there is a sequence of notes with the same pitch and rhythmic figure. The aim is that the reinforcement learning network should learn to use the same finger in every note. There is a partial split scale of five ascending notes and the same five descending notes in the second test. The aim is

Figure 13: Reinforcement learning techniques used to improve the convergence

that the hand position does not have to change. The third test is a piece of music that does not change the hand throughout its length. The fourth test is a C major scale. Finally, the fifth test is a piece with the melodic range of the C major scale. All these experiments have been carried out with several improvements and with different numbers of episodes.

Convergence takes a long time because the neural network is not trained with prior information. The improvement increasing convergence the most is to reduce the melodic range. In Figure 15 we can see how test 1 takes 1000 episodes with the range of 88 notes, and test 3 only takes 100 episodes to achieve its expected result with the melodic range limited.

The evolution of reinforcement learning can be seen in test 4, shown in Figure 14. We expose three states of the scenario with 500, 2000 and 5000 episodes. The logarithmic learning function is very accentuated, allowing a high exploration in the first 500 episodes and exploiting the exploration knowledge in the following 4500 episodes. This strategy of quickly exploring and using the discoveries in a long-term span seems to bring the best results. However, the time cost associated with such

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 14: (a) Test 4 trained on 500 episodes. (b) Test 4 trained on 2000 episodes. (c) Test 4 trained on 5000 episodes. (d) Evolution of reward in 5000 episodes

a conservative learning strategy is very high. The reinforcement agent process of trial and error to achieve optimum fingering resembles the process carried out by a pianist. However, a pianist in every new piece of music has prior knowledge, and the proposed reinforcement learning algorithm always starts from zero.

The reward function is wildly oscillating when following a less conservative strategy and trying to explore for too long, as exposed in test 3 (Figure 16). In this case, test

Figure 15: (a) Test 1 trained on 1000 episodes. (b) test 2 trained on 100

Figure 16: (a) Test 3 trained on 200 episodes. (b) Episode/reward over time.

4 is trained with a linear learning function, trying to explore much longer than with an inverse logarithmic function. The reinforcement agent achieves a good result at the beginning, in episode 180. However, as shown in the episode/reward function, the system does not converge.

(a)

(b)

Figure 17: (a) Test 5 trained on 500 episodes. (b) Episode/reward over time.

In test 5, Figure 17, we can see the reward evolves little by little when the difficulty of the work increases due to the conservative learning strategy. However, the time cost is so significant that it is not helpful for the following chapters of this master thesis.

4.6 Conclusions

In this chapter, we have proposed two methods for piano fingering generation. These two proposals want to be the foundation of a piano technique model presented in the

next chapter. Pianoplayer, a local search algorithm grounded in dynamic programming and combinatorial optimisation, can generate feasible but not optimal fingers. Pianoplayer cost function can be used as a heuristic to model the technique difficulty. Given the inflexibility of Pianoplayer in certain situations, we also propose a method of deep reinforcement learning merging expert systems and data-driven approaches. Although the preliminary reinforcement results surpass our expectations, the system requires a long time to achieve the expected results. In addition, the reinforcement learning process is similar to the musician fingering process. However, pianists make fingering from an experienced background starting from that baggage to optimise the fingering of a new piece. The proposed reinforcement method has no prior knowledge and always has to learn from zero. The reinforcement algorithm proposed in the present chapter is currently in review [57].

Chapter 5

Difficulty Analysis In Piano Symbolic Data

The difficulty is a broad and subjective concept, as stated in Section 5. However, piano technique and learning to piano fingering is considered a fundamental performance skill [38, 36, 40, 42]. In this section, we analyse piano difficulty from a piano technique perspective, grounded on the movement of fingers and hands generated in Chapter 4. We will use the models created in this chapter for Music Generation in Chapter 7.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Section 5.1 details the motivations of the present study. Section 5.2 present the new compiled Mikrokosmos dataset. Section 5.3 expose the data evaluation strategy to assess the three proposals for classifying difficulty. The non-explainable baseline approach is presented in Section 5.4. The two following approaches, the windowed approach and attention approach, are exposed in Section 5.5 and Section 5.6 respectively, are explainable methods. Therefore, in Section 5.7 we show how we use the explainability of windowed and attention approaches to give useful music feedback to musicians. Finally, we write the chapter conclusions in Section 5.8.

5.1 Motivations

There are large shreds of evidence to suggest a direct relationship between piano technique with the difficulty of a piece, as exposed the state of the art 3 and the previous chapter 4. To sum up, the piano technique is progressively learned year by year, and the piano technique grounds on hands and fingers movement caused by the fingering decision. Therefore, we can model the piano technique from the fingering generation.

We aim to organise in levels a music library and create meaningful and helpful music-motivated local difficulty feedback. The descriptors generated in the fingering block are in the local level scope. However, current difficulty annotations are scoped in a global term. A local level inference could bring more musically meaningful data. Explainability could run the inference process and give us local difficulty's feedback about the musical piece.

5.2 Mikrokosmos dataset

Béla Bartók's Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 is a collection of 153 progressive piano works published in six volumes between 1926 and 1939. Individual compositions go from extremely simple and easy beginner exercises to challenging advanced technical musical works. According to Bartók, the piece "appears as a synthesis of all the musical and technical problems which were treated and in some cases only partially solved in the previous piano works". Bartók divides the musical pieces in three levels:

- Volumes I and II: Pieces 1–36 and 37–66, beginner level.
- Volumes III and IV: Pieces 67–96 and 97–121, moderate to advanced level.
- Volumes V and VI: 122–139 and 140–153, professional level.

Volumes one and two are dedicated to his son Péter, whereas volumes five and six are composed for professional concert performances. Bartók also mentioned that these works might be performed on different instruments.

We have scanned with Optical Music Recognition software the 153 musical works. Consequently, we have fixed the MusicXMLs generated by hand.

5.3 Evaluation

Mikrokosmos is a small dataset consisting of just 150 pieces of music with unbalanced classes. We will consider both challenges in the following approaches.

Cross-validation is a technique used to evaluate statistical analysis results to ensure that they are independent of training and test data partition. We use 5-fold cross-validation to tune the model's hyperparameters in the train data, the 80% of Mikrokosmos dataset samples. Later, we evaluate the trained model in the remaining data part. The results vary considerably depending on the split between train and test because the dataset is tiny. Therefore, we have made 50 different splits of the dataset on which we will evaluate the models to check the results are not overfitting to a specific train/test division. The 50 splits will allow us to ascertain the accuracy of the chosen models and whether they are generalisable in a fairer way.

The global classes, the global three difficulty levels, are slightly unbalanced. If we extract windows from each musical piece, it is even more unbalanced because the length of the music piece is proportional to the difficulty level of the work. Hence, we will use balanced accuracy in the methods proposed in all the following sections.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{FP + TN}$$

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity}}{2}$$

Finally, a recurrent problem in Machine Learning are the biases due to inadequate stratification. In this case, composer and style bias would be a problem if mikrokosmos had not been created by a single author. Furthermore, in approaches made

with windows, we must carry out a double stratification, even in the cross-validation training of the model.

5.4 Baseline Approach

Figure 18: Baseline approach algorithm architecture.

The first proposal to model the difficulty from the piano technique is based on the raw cost function generated by Pianoplayer. There is a cost function for each note fingered by the fingering algorithm. Pianoplayer outputs the best cost function after optimising each sequence of nine onsets, as exposed Section 4.4.

Figure 19: Overall result of baseline approach across 50 different splits.

Two-time series compose the algorithm input: left hand and right-hand cost function time series. In addition, the algorithm pipeline has two blocks, as shown in Figure 18. First, compute several statistics to summarise both time series: mean, median, standard deviation, interquartile range, skewness, kurtosis, etc. In the second step,

the features extracted from the time series are modelled to classify with a linear support vector machine the three Mikrokosmos difficulty levels.

We train and evaluate the dataset following the guidelines set out in Section 5.3. We train the model in the data for each split, tuning the support vector classifier hyper-parameters with a grid search. Later, we use the model trained to eval the test data. The results across the 50 Mikrokosmos dataset splits are presented in Figure 19. The x-axis represents the split number, and for each split, a red point and a blue point is stating the test and train balanced accuracy. There are two splits under-trained, the splits number 19 and 48, the two spurious points shown in Figure 20. We have considered the possibility that the musical works of these two splits caused some kind of bias and that the two splits were very similar. However, this is not the case. Only six musical works out of 30 coincide in the test set of splits 19 and 48. Another interesting fact is when the accuracy in the test set is very high in the train set, it decreases considerably due to over-fitting.

Figure 20: Boxplot distribution of balanced accuracy across all the splits. Baseline Approach.

The results distribution in the train and test sets over the 50 splits is shown in

Figure 21: Histogram of best hyper-parameter search per split. Baseline Approach.

Figure 20. Most models converge to a similar standard deviation in training, except for the two spurious points mentioned. The results above 87% balanced accuracy in the train set cause over-fitting in the test set when compared to those in Figure 19. We could have used more complex Machine Learning models with the best early stopping. However, we decided to keep the baseline approach as simple as possible. In the test set, the models trained oscillates between 56% and 88%. The results follow a uniform distribution, which indicates we can fairly consider the mean, 74%, as the general baseline approach balance accuracy.

Lastly, the best parameterisations obtained by training the models converge to very few hyper-parameter sets, as shown in 21. There are 36 possible parameterisations, tuning Gamma Kernel coefficient and C regularisation parameters, but all the models converge in only six hyper-parameter sets, with three parameterisations covering 39/50 final models.

To sum up, the baseline approach proposed in this section is a straightforward model

to demonstrate that it is possible to express the piano technique difficulty from piano fingering. In particular, we ascertain Pianoplayer cost function is a very significant embedding of piano fingering.

5.5 Windowed Approach

The second proposal to model the difficulty from the piano technique is also based on Pianoplayer Automatic Piano Fingering. Instead of having the entire scores as a Machine Learning basis, it has small excerpts or patches of the original scores.

Figure 22: Windowed approach algorithm architecture.

Therefore, the windowed approach is a two-step algorithm, the first step classifies the difficulty of each patch, and the second step classifies the global difficulty of the work, as shown in Figure 22. Two-step architecture allows local feedback of the

difficulty from the intermediate presentation between step 1 and step 2. Step 1 is an ensemble classifier (Xgboost), and step 2 is logistic regression.

Figure 23: Representation learning.

The windowed approach operates from a representation encoding the Pianoplayer cost function, the fingers and the keys physical distances, as is shown in Figure 23. We encode the time in the first dimension. The second dimension encodes the finger, which plays the note and dimension three have encoded the Pianoplayer cost function, the distance in cm and the distance type with previous work. Third dimension x is $x = (v, d, dt)$ with v the Pianoplayer cost function, d the distance between notes and dt the distance type.

Figure 24: Distance types.

We must differentiate the distance types from the absolute distance in cm because technique changes whether the distance is from white to white, from black to black from white to black or from black to black, or from black to white, as shown in 24. Therefore, we differentiate between the four types in which the distance can vary. Consequently, we train from this representation the two steps of the algorithm.

In the first step, we train an ensemble classifier (Xgboost). This type of algorithm is the best choice when there is a small amount of data, an imbalanced problem, and a lot of spurious data. There is a lot of spurious data because the difficulty piece level does not mean all the piece local parts have the same difficulty. We tune the first step hyperparameters with a randomised search due to the gradient descent slowness of Xgboost.

Figure 25: Overall result across 50 different splits. Windowed Approach

In the second step, departing from the first step patch results, we train a logistic regression with a high factor of regularisation. As we explained in the beginning, the aim of the windowed proposals is not to achieve perfect accuracy but an explainable representation, so we have built this second step in the simplest way.

In Figure 25 we can see an overall view of the split results. The test set results range

between 52% and 76% balanced accuracy in the first step local patches classification and from 56% to 82% balanced accuracy in the second step global output. The accuracy results are not better than the baseline, although they are explainable, as shown in the following sections. Besides, the results in the second step are bordering on over-fitting because train results have high balanced accuracy. In further work, we will consider other methods for describing the patches time series evolution.

Figure 26: Boxplot distribution of balanced accuracy across all the splits. Windowed Approach.

The results distribution in the train and test sets over the 50 splits is shown in Figure 20. In training, most models converge to a similar standard deviation. The split 33, we can view in Figure 19, has results higher than average in the first step. We have analysed the split 33 scores, and the test scores are of monotonous difficulty. In other words, all the patches have a similar difficulty. Finally, in step 1, we consider the test results mean as the general balanced accuracy, 59%, and in the second step, 70% a bit lower than the baseline.

We do not show the best tuning parametrisations of the ensemble classifier because

each split has a different one. Moreover, the test set results distribution of the second step have a higher standard deviation than the baseline, shown in 20. These two facts show that the algorithm is less stable than the baseline.

To sum up, the windowed approach proposed in this section is a patch-based algorithm to model difficulty. Although the windowed approach balanced accuracy is 5% worse than the baseline approach results, the results are explainable, as we will show in Section 5.7.

Figure 27: Attention approach algorithm architecture grounded on DeepGRU research proposal [58]

5.6 Attention Approach

The last approach tries to solve the problem of explainability using the architecture of attention. We can interpret Deep Learning attention heads as a vector of importance weights. Departing from representation exposed in Section 5.5, we use DeepGRU architecture [58] to model difficulty. The DeepGRU method lies in a set

of three stacked gated recurrent units (GRU), two fully connected layers and a novel global attention model, as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 28: Results variability across epochs and splits. Attention Approach.

We train and evaluate the dataset following the guidelines set out in Section 5.3. We prepare the DeepGRU model in the train data for each split and assess it in the test data. Moreover, we train the model with different epochs, between 0 and 200 iterations. The results have a high variability depending on the split, as we can see in Figure 28.

We use early stops to avoid over-fitting. We show in Figure 29 the epoch where the final result is achieved. Note although most of the splits have the early stop between splits 0 and 25, for avoiding overfitting, some splits have the best results after epoch 150.

We show the best early stopping results in Figure 30. The test results global/mean accuracy is 82% balanced accuracy, being the best results. Furthermore, the test

Figure 29: Histogram of best epoch early stop per split. Attention Approach.

results distribution is normal, indicating excellent DeepGRU stability.

Figure 30: Best test results distribution across the 50 splits.

To sum up, the attention approach proposed in this section is a deep learning method to model difficulty. The results surpass the other approaches, and it is an explainable model, as we will show in Section 5.7.

5.7 Local difficulty explainability feedback

The explainability of models in Music Education is fundamental. It is no longer only necessary to output the difficulty rating, but the reasoning for making the decision is even more inspiring. We aim to conduct an inference between the overall difficulty scores and the difficult sections not scored increases the musical value of the model. For two reasons: the local difficulty is very valuable, and speaking in the same language as the musicians increases the likelihood of Music Education community acceptance.

Students need to know where to focus their efforts . If we mark the local difficulty on scores from a pedagogy perspective, the student can start by studying the most difficult passages. Local difficulty explainable feedback allows students and teachers to know these difficult sections in advance.

We must sort the sheet music into categories to discover new music pieces in extensive score collections. The potential application of difficulty analysis is to structure and make score recommendations. Deep learning does not show by default very transparent reasoning, and this may decrease the acceptance by the Music Education community of this type of system. However, the musical explainability of the models can bridge the gap between Music Education and data-driven methods.

We have proposed two ways to give explainable music feedback: the windowed approach and the attention approach. Finally, we show our research can work both in musicXML and MIDI formats.

Explainable windowed approach feedback.

Section 5.5 presented an explainable method for difficulty classification. The windowed approach first step searches for similarities between score patches. We aim windowed approach to find similar patterns between scores of the same level. In the same score, not all patches have the same difficulty. Therefore, the windowed explainable should show the difficulty variation. In other words, which difficulty level is each little section of the score. We average the difficulty of all the windows

or patches containing the same note. Note that every note overlaps between different windows or patches. Consequently, each onset or note's group sounding at the same time has a different difficulty assigned. We visualized this difficulty with three colours, one per each Mikrokosmos level, over the score. We colour level 1 notes with green, level 2 notes with yellow and level 3 with red.

We have chosen a random split to visualize the test set. As we have no way to evaluate the results, to show that the model is generalizing, we have attached the whole test set visualization in Annex B. In the following paragraphs, we will analyze with tiny excerpts the explainable feedback proposed.

Figure 31: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 28 by Béla Bartók. Explainable windowed approach feedback.

Many scores have a monotonous difficulty progression, as shown in Appendix B. For example, pieces number 5, 11, 12, 16, 18 have a monotonous difficulty progression, as displayed with the colours. However, we can also see noise in some works due to the reduced dataset size.

Figure 32: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 27 by Béla Bartók. Explainable windowed approach feedback.

The exciting feedback is when the works are not difficulty monotonous. One case is the Mikrokosmos n. 28., most of the piece is from level 1, but the hand position changes, shown in Figure 31, are more complicated. Another straightforward exam-

ple is the Mikrokosmos n. 27, exposed in Figure 32. The algorithm classifies as level 2 this musical work due to its syncopation and the psychomotor skills between the two hands.

The excerpt of Mikrokosmos 142, Figure 33, shows the difficulty changes between different patches. The score difficulty comes to level three in bar 6 because the quickly and asymmetric melody changes between hands. However, in bar 8, the melody hands changes are a simple arpeggio, which is why it is coloured yellow. Later, local difficulty feedback still changing between level 2 to level 3.

Figure 33: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 142 by Béla Bartók. Explainable windowed approach feedback.

Results surpass our expectations giving exceptional music local difficulty feedback.

Explainable attention approach feedback

Section 5.6 exposed a deep learning explainable method for difficulty classification. This method grounds on attention for giving feedback about which notes the model is focusing. We aim attention approach focus only on the notes important to classify a certain level, discarding the rest. We extract the attention heads weight of each

note to give music feedback. We visualise the head's weight, ranging in a blue scale, being the darker coloured notes where the proposed method is focusing.

We have chosen the same split as the previous approach for a fair comparison. As we have no way to evaluate the results, to show that the model is generalising, we have attached the whole test set visualisation in Annex C. In the following paragraphs, we will analyse with little excerpts the explainable feedback proposed.

Figure 34: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 12 by Béla Bartók. Explainable attention approach feedback

Our idea to discard specific note patterns because they do not sufficiently characterise a level does not work. However, the most exciting aspect of attention is dealing with repetitions that occur in the short term. There are many examples shown in Appendix C. For instance, in Figure 36 there are three same pattern repetitions of notes going up and down. We can see how the second pattern is not as important as the second, but the third one is important because the fingering changes to allocate a better hand position to follow the score.

Figure 35: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 109 by Béla Bartók. Explainable attention approach feedback.

The excerpt of Mikrokosmos n. 109, Figure 35 is also very illustrative of how attention handles repetitions. In bar 15, beat 3, the right-hand technique pattern is

the same as bar 17, beat 3, but transposed. Therefore, as finger distances are the same, the Attention approach does not focus on the second one because the first is already characterising difficulty level. We expose another example about repetitive patterns discarding in Figure 36. The double notes repetitive movements do not add difficulty to the score classification.

The image displays two systems of musical notation for Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 71. The first system starts at measure 1 with a tempo marking of quarter note = 66. The second system starts at measure 6 with a forte (sf) dynamic marking. Each system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Attention feedback is shown as numerical values (e.g., -1, -2, -3, -4, -5) placed below the notes, indicating the model's focus on specific fingerings or intervals.

Figure 36: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 71 by Béla Bartók. Explainable attention approach feedback.

The image displays two systems of musical notation for Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 93=7. Both systems are in bass clef. The first system starts at measure 29 and the second at measure 33. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. Attention feedback is shown as numerical values (e.g., -2, -1, -4, -3, -1, -2, -3, -1, -2, -3, -4, -5) placed below the notes, indicating the model's focus on specific fingerings or intervals.

Figure 37: Excerpt of Mikrokosmos Sz. 107 n. 93=7 by Béla Bartók. Explainable attention approach feedback.

Finally, we show an example of the potential of attention reasoning to understand the temporal dimension of scores in Figure 37. In the right hand, the same pattern is played but slightly varying the notes. Attention manages to focus only on the changed notes of the sequence. Therefore, the model highlights repetitions in lighter

blue for each replication, and each time the same notes are played, the model gives less attention.

The attention approach does not provide the musical feedback we initially expected, but it shows the reasoning behind the attention architecture. If we compare the attention and windowed methods test sets, we can affirm the latter approach produces a more helpful local difficulty feedback from a Music Education view. Moreover, the attention approach is the method to classify difficulty presented in this section with better performance and with explainability can understand better its behaviour. Lastly, its explainability has allowed us to observe the crucial role of discarding repetitions in characterising difficulty.

Midi Visualizer

As discussed throughout the chapter, an ambiguous representation across all music symbolic data formats is crucial to lay the groundwork for further research. Therefore, our representation works in both midi formats and musicXML. In these paragraphs, we briefly analyse the visualisation of the difficulty in midi formats because, in the previous pages, we only visualise local difficulty from musicXML scores. Visualising in MIDI format has been a must because it will allow us to display technical difficulty in expressive performances, with the models trained in non-expressive versions.

We have modified an interface, Figure 38 to display fingers and midis in a similar way to a score originally built by Nakamura et al. [47].

The operation is the same as in musicXML. For a complete understanding of the visualisation, we propose to analyse the difficulty of "Por una cabeza" by Carlos Gardel. In Figure 39, we have marked the most challenging part of the piece. The darker red colours mean greater difficulty in the windowed approach, while in the attention approach, the darker colours mean that the model pays more attention. As shown in Figure 40 and Figure 41, the results are similar to those of the previous examples.

Difficulty Analysis Visualizer. Pedro Ramoneda Master Thesis.

Drop ground truth files here

Open files

Duration mode Transition mode
 bemols (selected) / sharps (not selected)

Time scale 1.0

Draw Clear

```

irinity corpus#classical#Piano#Z018#02
Sibelius files#Pieces#4#Adagio.txt
  
```

Figure 38: Interface for showing technique difficulty from MIDI format.

Figure 39: Por una cabeza, Carlos Gardel. The red line denotes the most difficult piece part.

Figure 40: Por una cabeza, Carlos Gardel. The red line denotes the most difficult piece part.

Figure 41: Por una cabeza, Carlos Gardel. Attention approach explainable feedback.

5.8 Conclusions

The results of this chapter go beyond our expectations. We have shown that difficulty is strongly related to piano technique. For this purpose, we have put together a dataset, Mikrokosmos, which is neither biased by style nor by artist because it has 153 works of progressive difficulty composed by a single author, Bela Bartók. We have created a non-explainable baseline that ranks difficulty with 74% balanced accuracy and two explainable proposals: windowed approach and attention approach, performing 70% and 82% respectively. Besides, we have analysed the two mechanisms to achieve local difficulty feedback. We have concluded that although attention manages the temporal dimension better, the windowed approach feedback is more valuable from a Music Education perspective.

The results are awe-inspiring because it is challenging to explain a subjective concept as challenging and multidimensional as difficulty from a single dimension. Nevertheless, we must admit that the Mikrokosmos dataset is a well-controlled scenario without composer and style biases and classes without overlapping. Therefore, in Chapter 8 we will discuss the potential path to make fully generalisable research across large music symbolic data corpora in further work.

The research conducted in this chapter is currently in review [59].

Chapter 6

Understanding piano as accompaniment

The education of singing and musical instruments in Western music traditions usually draws on piano accompaniment. In this chapter we study the relationship between this accompaniment and the lead melody on a symbolic corpus containing pedagogic-designed piano accompaniments for classical and Rock & Pop singing lessons. We derive accompaniment support features on three dimensions: melody, rhythm, and harmony. This allows us to understand the role of accompaniment throughout the different levels in which a formal syllabus of music education is structured. Our analysis shows that the support of accompaniment differs between the classical and Rock & Pop and confirms its variability when related to the structure of the syllabus. We develop a web-visualisation tool which allows us to explore how the pieces are distributed along the considered dimensions. We complement the discussion with a thorough analysis of a set of outlier songs selected using the web-based tool.

6.1 Introduction

Piano accompaniment for singing voice education helps the student to improve intonation, and enhance ensemble and relative listening skills [60]. Most of the pieces

used for singing education in Western traditions are provided with piano accompaniment [61] which consequently plays a key role in the learning process. To that extent, understanding the relationship between the voice and the accompaniment is fundamental from a pedagogical perspective.

In this chapter we aim at studying the relationship between voice and accompaniment in a corpus of music scores for singing voice education. Specifically, we look at how the accompaniment offers support to the lead melody by defining a list of hand-crafted descriptors that focus on the main musical dimensions: melody, rhythm and harmony. We describe these descriptors in Section 6.3. Even though we understand accompaniment support in terms of how different aspects of the lead melody are replicated by the piano, and therefore we draw on methods developed for similarity analysis, our research does not directly engage with this task. Instead, we aim at understanding how selected elements of the lead melody are reinforced by the piano accompaniment for educational purposes. In Section 6.4, we discuss the relation of our chapter with previous research.

In this chapter we study the syllabi developed by a well-known publisher for singing voice education which we describe in Section 6.2. Particularly, we focus on the Rock & Pop and Classical syllabi which contain 96 and 112 songs classified into 9 levels of difficulty by musical teachers at the well-known publisher. These levels are denoted as grades and we use them as a proxy for difficulty. The difficulty of performing a musical piece is a subjective notion since it may be perceived differently depending on a varied set of factors ranging from the pedagogical objective of the teacher to the experience and the cultural background of the student [15].

In Sections 6.6 and 6.7 we look at the relation between the proposed descriptors and the grade into which a given song is classified within the studied syllabi. With that we aim to contribute to the broader task of understanding the degree of difficulty for educational purposes and therefore to its empirical analysis for future automatic classification tasks. Disregarding subjective aspects, it should be noted that, besides the accompaniment support addressed in this chapter, there are many other factors that can be objectively measured from symbolic or audio data in order to assess the

difficulty level of a given piece. Without aiming at fully explaining grade or difficulty hence, this chapter offers a first study on how the piano accompaniment support contributes to the classification of music scores into a certain range of difficulty levels for educational purposes.

Because most of the music teaching syllabi consist of limited sets of works [33], a direct application of our methodology is to help expanding educational syllabi by contributing with descriptors for the accompaniment support.

6.2 The corpus

To the best of our knowledge there is no corpus currently used in formal music education containing sheet music in a machine-readable format that is publicly available. In this research we use proprietary data from the syllabi developed by a established major publisher, an examination board based in London which offers grade and diploma qualifications up to postgraduate level across a range of disciplines in the performing arts and English language learning and teaching.

For this first study, we focus on singing voice education in two different styles, namely Classical and Pop & Rock. To that aim, we put together a research corpus, containing two collections of machine readable scores, each of them corresponding to the syllabi of the two selected styles.

These collections contain 112 and 96 songs respectively and are categorized into nine grades, from zero to eight, according to the difficulty levels. Table 1 shows the description of the accompaniment per grade offered in the teaching material of the syllabus for Rock & Pop singing.

When studying how the publisher syllabi are structured, we take into account three particular ideas explained in the publisher books. First, the grade range is ubiquitous in all the disciplines, rather than being something particular for music or singing lessons. Second, while accompaniment support is important, publisher defines in the corresponding books additional factors used to differentiate between grades: the duration of the song, time signatures, rhythm figures, syncopation, dynamics, melodic

register, melodic intervals, improvisation, and other techniques such as legatos or pauses. Third, any machine learning and statistical analysis methods have to be used with care, considering the limited number of songs per grade.

Grade	Parameter description
Grade 0	Supportive backing with clear entries guided by accompaniment
Grade 1	Relatively supportive backing
Grade 2	Relatively supportive with some rhythmic independence
Grade 3	Relatively supportive with more independent vocal entries
Grade 4	Moderately supportive backing
Grade 5	Moderately supportive backing
Grade 6	Backing becoming independent
Grade 7	Almost fully independent backing
Grade 8	Backing can be fully independent within reason

Table 1: Accompaniment parameters in Rock & Pop private syllabus.

6.3 Methodology

Towards modelling accompaniment support, we capture the relation between the accompaniment and the lead melody using five descriptors related to three dimensions: rhythm (rhythm onset descriptor and rhythm pattern coincidence), melody (melody contour comparison and melody pattern coincidence), and harmony.

Note that melody, rhythm, and harmony are not isolated dimensions, and there may be some overlapping between the descriptors we propose.

6.3.1 Rhythm

Mastering rhythm is one of the essential skills in singing education. The accompaniment may help the singer by reinforcing beat and the rhythm patterns in the lead melody. To capture this relation we propose two descriptors: rhythm onset and rhythm pattern coincidence.

The image shows a musical score for 'The Skylark' by Eric Thiman. It consists of two staves: a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line is in the treble clef with a key signature of one sharp (F#) and a 2/4 time signature. The lyrics are: 'Have you heard the sky - lark sing - ing, Sing - ing in the Spring?-' The piano accompaniment is in the grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with the same key signature and time signature. The score shows four measures of music.

Figure 42: *The Skylark* (Eric Thiman), Classical, grade 2 (bars 3-6). Values for the four measures shown in the figure ($S = 7$): RO= 0.813, RPC = 0.58, MC= 0.93, MPC = 0.62, H= 0.47

Rhythm Onset (RO)

The events of a music piece are linked to a constant alternation of strong and weak beats at various hierarchical levels [62]. The Rhythm Onset descriptor captures whether the note onsets of the lead melody are reinforced by simultaneous ones in the accompaniment. If so, its metrical relevance is also considered by adding a weight corresponding to their position in the metrical hierarchy defined in [62].

We consider $o^v(i)$ to be the vector containing all the notes onsets times corresponding to the lead melody, where $i = \{1, \dots, I\}$ with I the total number of notes in the lead melody. In addition, we associate a weight $w(i)$ to each $o^v(i)$ according to the weight of the note in the metrical hierarchy. Furthermore, we consider $o^a(j)$ as the vector containing all the notes onsets times corresponding to the lead melody, where $j = \{1, \dots, J\}$ with J the total number of notes in the accompaniment.

We consider the coinciding onsets between the lead melody and the accompaniment as $o(i, j) = \delta(o^v(i), o^a(j))$, where δ denotes the Kronecker delta.

We compute the Rhythm Onset descriptor RO at each time frame i as

$$\text{RO}(i) = \frac{1}{J} \sum_j o(i, j) \circ w_i, \quad (6.1)$$

where δ denotes the Kronecker delta and $\circ$ the element-wise product.

We then summarize the RO_i across all common onsets i by computing the mean and the standard deviation. In the example presented in Figure 42 the value for this descriptor is 0.813.

Rhythm Pattern Coincidence (RPC)

In addition to the RO descriptor which is computed for the entire song as single instance, we are interested in matching short term rhythmic patterns between the lead melody and the accompaniment. We consider that a pattern in the lead melody is rhythmically supported by a pattern in the accompaniment if both the onsets and duration of their notes coincide. We do this for various pattern sizes $s = \{1, \dots, S\}$

A pattern of size s of consecutive note onsets times and duration for the lead melody starting at position i is a set of pairs of onset time and duration $\langle o_s^v(i, k), d_s^v(i, k) \rangle$ with $k = \{1, \dots, s\}$. Let $\langle o^a(j), d^a(j) \rangle$ be the pairs of note onsets times and duration for the accompaniment where $j = \{1, \dots, J\}$ with J the total number of notes in the accompaniment. We consider that a lead melody rhythm pattern of size s , $\langle o_s^v(i, k), d_s^v(i, k) \rangle$, is supported by the accompaniment if we find s notes with the same onset times and duration in the accompaniment, such as $o(i, k, j) = \delta(o^v(i, k), o^a(j)) = 1$ and $d(i, k, j) = \delta(d^v(i, k), d^a(j)) = 1$ for all $k = \{1, \dots, s\}$. Thus the Rhythm Pattern Coincidence (RPC) at each position i and for a sequence s is computed as

$$RPC^s(i) = \prod_k o(i, k, j) * d(i, k, j). \quad (6.2)$$

We then aggregate RPC for the whole piece by computing the mean and the standard deviation across all sequences s . For the example in Figure 42, the mean of RPC^s for S in range $[1, 7]$ is equal to 0.86, 0.78, 0.69, 0.58, 0.45, 0.40, 0.33 and the descriptor mean is 0.58.

6.3.2 Melody

We study melodic accompaniment support through two descriptors: melody contour and melody pattern coincidence.

Melody Contour (MC)

Melody contour describes how a melody moves between individual notes. We consider that there is more accompaniment support if the piano plays identical pitches to the lead melody. Because we want to model melody support regardless of the octave differences, we collapse the pitches of the accompaniment into pitch classes.

For a given time resolution τ which results in a total of R frames for a given piece, we construct the binary matrices M^v and M^a for the lead melody and the accompaniment by assigning 1 or 0 to each element depending on whether a pitch class is present at a given time-frame $r = \{1, \dots, R\}$.

Towards measuring the accompaniment support for the lead melody contour, we compare the pitch classes for melody and accompaniment at each time frame. Namely, we compute the Melody Contour (MC) feature at a given time frame r as:

$$\text{MC}(r) = \max_n \{M^a \circ M^v\} \quad (6.3)$$

where $n = \{1, \dots, 12\}$ is the pitch class.

We then aggregate MC for the whole piece by computing the mean and the standard deviation across all time frames r . For the example in Figure 42 the descriptor mean is 0.93.

Melody Pattern Coincidence (MPC)

Similarly to the RPC descriptor, we aim at analysing how accompaniment supports short term melodic patterns. We compute melodic pattern coincidences for various pattern sizes $s = \{1, \dots, S\}$. Because the singer may correct the pitch after the note onset, we weight the melodic coincidences with the related note duration, so that longer notes have more importance in the computation. Moreover, similarly to the MC descriptor, we compensate for octave differences by comparing patterns of pitch classes rather than pitches.

For the lead melody we take s of consecutive notes defined by onset times, pitch class,

and duration $\langle o_s^v(i, k), p_s^v(i, k), d_s^v(i, k) \rangle$ starting at position i with $k = \{1, \dots, s\}$. We find the notes in the accompaniment $\langle o^a(j), p^a(j), d^a(j) \rangle$ which have the same note onsets and pitch classes such that $o(i, k, j) = \delta(o^v(i, k), o^a(j)) = 1$ and $p(i, k, j) = \delta(p^v(i, k), p^a(j)) = 1$ for all $k = \{1, \dots, s\}$, where $j = \{1, \dots, J\}$ with J the total number of notes in the accompaniment. Thus the Melody Pattern Coincidence (MPC) value at each position i and for the sequence length s is defined as

$$\text{MPC}^s(i) = \prod_k o(i, k, j) * p(i, k, j) * d(i, k). \quad (6.4)$$

We then aggregate MPC for the whole piece by computing the mean and the standard deviation across all sequences s . For the example in Figure 42, the MPC^s for s in range $[1, 7]$ is equal to 0.86, 0.8, 0.72, 0.62, 0.49, 0.45, 0.40 and the descriptor mean is 0.62.

6.3.3 Harmony (H)

In recent years, several proposals have been made to mathematically structure music harmony. One of them is the Tonal Interval Space (TIS) [63]. TIS can be understood as a type of generalized tonnetz that models interval groups according to Western music theory. TIS allows measuring distances between different pitch groups, such as chords, keys or random pitch combinations. We apply the Harmonic Change Detection Function (HCDF) over the TIS representation which computes the harmonic boundaries, often coinciding with the chords for symbolic data.

Here we optimize the HCDF [1] algorithm in the symbolic domain to segment the accompaniment in several harmonic boundaries. Correspondingly, we depart from a symbolic chromagram to compute the 12-dimensional TIS, T , as defined in [63]. Then, we measure the distance between each vocal note pitch and the respective accompaniment harmonic boundary content. We compute the cosine distance to determine how well pitch profiles fit together [64].

Similarly to the MC descriptor we construct matrices containing the pitch classes

M^v and M^a for the lead melody and the accompaniment on a time resolution τ where $r = \{1, \dots, R\}$ are the time frames.

Then, we compute the harmonic descriptor H at each time frame r as the cosine similarity between the tonal interval spaces of M^v and M^a :

$$H(r) = \frac{\langle T(M^v), T(M^a) \rangle}{T(M^v)T(M^a)} \quad (6.5)$$

We then compute the mean and the standard deviation for this descriptor across all time frames. The value descriptor H is 0.47 for the example in Figure 42.

Figure 43: Box plots displaying mean, median and quartiles for the five descriptors of accompaniment support computed per grade over the whole corpus.

6.4 Relation with previous work

Since our research draws on methods for music similarity analysis, in this section we compare our proposed descriptors for characterizing accompaniment support with state of the art literature in that task.

A common practice is the use of methods such as the swap distance or the edit distance to calculate rhythmic pattern similarity. However, in our understanding of accompaniment support, rhythmic similarity between the singing line and the piano

accompaniment do not suffice to account for learning reinforcement. Our RO and RPC descriptors are based on [65]. This study analyses the onsets that fall in a beat and categorises if the beat is being enhanced, opposed or the effect is neutral. This approach has been successfully tested through perceptual experiments [66] and extended in the Pattern Coincidence and Awareness Distance (PAD) descriptor [67]. We extend the PAD descriptor to capture if the accompaniment helps the student to follow the beat with RO and to measure each pattern of the rhythmic figures in RPC. In contrast to [67], we focus on the note onsets, and we generalize the algorithm to work with various time signatures, given that the original descriptors are exclusively designed for 4/4. The RO also relies on the Metrical Structure [62], which states that the events of a piece are linked to a constant alternation of strong and weak beats at various hierarchical levels.

Melodic similarity in symbolic domain is a widely studied area. Some proposals disentangle the melody into several features [68], while others create geometric models to embed the features in a single point [69]. We consider the former approach from which we extract the use of melodic contours (for the MC) and motif similarity (for the MPC) to solve this problem. To the best of our knowledge, there is no music cognition approach suggesting a certain melody similarity voice-accompaniment to support the singer. Therefore, we have decided to consider only coincidence (perfect similarity) as a measure. Note that melodic similarity is commonly applied between monophonic sources [70], which is not our case since piano is polyphonic. In addition, our melodic descriptors consider octave equivalence. This assumption states that pitches that are one or two octaves apart are still identical in many musical aspects [71].

Harmonic similarity has been mainly approached from a long-term perspective, comparing chord sequences rather than single harmonic instances, as seen in [72]. The harmony dimension presented in Section 6.3.3 measures if each monophonic note of the lead melody fits well into the harmony underneath the voice. To that extent, long-term harmonic similarity that is designed for comparing pairs of polyphonic sources is not well suited to our task. Consequently, we consider tonal spaces that

allow us to compute short-term distances between a monophonic and a polyphonic source, similarly to Chew’s Spiral Array [73] and Harte et al.’s 6-D space [74]. We base the H descriptor in the TIS [63] which merges and extends the previously mentioned models and we use the HCDF among this tonal representation [1]. This method allows us to segment the harmony in pitch groups related to chords, outperforming symbolic chord recognition algorithms that do not provide enough confidence [75].

6.5 Experiments

6.5.1 Preprocessing

The original music scores are provided in *.sib* format, which is exclusively compatible with the proprietary score editor software Sibelius. Consequently, we convert the scores to either MusicXML or MIDI format to be able to compute the descriptors. The aforementioned conversion carries out some problems, leading to the discarding approximately the 30% of the scores. To avoid this loss of data, a Sibelius plugin is developed within the framework of this chapter. This plugin separates scores in three parts (lead voice, piano right hand, and piano left hand) and stores them in MIDI format. This plugin also removes fermattas, articulations and slurs for a clear descriptor computation in the next steps.

6.5.2 Experimental setup

We develop a complete framework to compute the descriptors for the educational scores. This framework consists of a Python implementation of the formulas detailed in the Section 6.3, in addition to several visualization functions to interactively navigate through the obtained results.

The metrical structure weights considered for the RO descriptor are computed using the midi toolbox [76], which is written in MATLAB. To compute the pattern-based descriptors RPC and MPC, we consider the following size range: $S = 7$. We normalize all descriptors across each collection to the range $[0 \dots 1]$.

We distribute five interactive plots, one per descriptor, using the Plotly library [77]. The visualizations consist of box plot representations of the descriptor values, setting the x-Axis to the publisher grades, and the y-Axis to the descriptor value of the scores. We also include the points representing each specific score in each collection. The interactive visualization allows the reader to inspect each song as a data point, along with the values for the descriptors.

Towards assessing the contribution of each descriptor to the grade structure we use the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test [78] on each pairs of grades for the five descriptors. We selected the KS, a non-parametric test, because our descriptors are not normally distributed across the songs and the variances between grades are different. The null hypothesis is that samples are drawn from the same distribution. To account for testing multiple hypotheses we apply the Holm-Bonferroni correction [79].

Figure 44: Hierarchical descriptor clusters for Classical and Rock & Pop repertoires.

6.6 Results

In this section we present the results obtained for the five proposed descriptors of accompaniment support computed per grade over the whole corpus, as shown in Figure 43.

We first focus on the Classical collection coloured in blue. Despite observing a negative correlation between grade and each descriptor, we notice the important overlap between the different grades. In the lower grades of this repertoire, the

Ab/Eb Eb Bb/D Cm7 F Bb Fm7/Bb C

f *mf* *ff*

I con-si-der it a chal-lenge_ be-fore the whole hu-man race, and I ain't gon-na lose, and I need to go on and on, and on and on.

Figure 45: *We Are The Champions* (Freddie Mercury, Queen), Rock & Pop, grade 6 (bars 55-60). Values for the whole piece ($S = 7$): RO= 0.55, RPC = 0.1, MC= 0.8, MPC = 0.29, H= 0.53

accompaniment tends to offer support across the three dimensions by simultaneously playing the entire lead melody line. However, as we advance along the grades the overlap between grades is more prominent which produces the distinction between contiguous grades to be not possible.

On the other hand, for the Rock & Pop collection we observe less variance. This may be because the accompaniment design for Rock & Pop is more consistent than for the Classical case, we cannot see any clear tendency along the grades. This is due to the fact that the accompaniments for this repertoire are mainly based on clustered chords or repeated simple patterns.

Rhythm, harmony and melody dimensions have a certain degree of correlation. We use hierarchical clustering to model the distance between descriptors. We represent through the dendrograms shown in Figure 6.5 the inter-correlations among the descriptors. Distance models are built using a square matrix that represents the absolute correlation distance between all descriptors. The full analysis can be found in the supporting material.

The KS tests we ran for the five descriptors and the 36 possible combinations of grades failed to reject the null hypothesis after applying the Holm-Bonferroni correction. We report the p -values in a table included in the supplementary materials. We note that for the grades 0 to 2 in classical Classical we obtain p -values lower than 0.05 which may indicate that accompaniment may be important at lower grades for this collection. However, although the five features used to model accompaniment

are important for some songs, these features alone cannot explain the difference in grades which we attribute to other features we do not study in this chapter and we describe in Section 6.2.

6.7 Discussion

The results are influenced by the limited number of songs for each grade, what produces larger standard deviation along each grade. However, we have manually analyzed the results using our online tool to further explore different strategies for arranging educational-based piano accompaniments. We observe that for the Classical collection the relationship between the lead melody and the accompaniment changes through the grades reducing the melodic, rhythmic and harmonic support, being the variation more notable in the first half of the scale of grades. Furthermore, for the Rock & Pop collection the accompaniment does not vary in the direction of the difficulty level. That suggests that the grades in this repertoire are organized taking into account additional variables from the scores which are not considered in our study.

When analyzing how the five descriptors relate to each other, we observe a difference between the two collections. In Rock & Pop, the rhythm descriptors are grouped together, while the melody and harmony form a different cluster. In contrast, the RPC descriptor is clustered together with the harmony and melody descriptors. We attribute this hierarchy to the fact that a significant rate of supported onsets in the Classical repertoire are found in weak metric positions. We noted an overlap between the grades that appears in a significant number of cases in the results. We discuss below this issue by analyzing two selected examples.

The piece *Hop Bird* from the Classical collection is classified as grade 1, but the descriptors of its accompaniment support are unexpectedly low, except for vocal onsets which is yet below the average in the grade (see Figure 46). According to the publisher books, the factors that may lead to this classification are the short length of the piece (only 23 measures, and a total of 28 notes for the vocal line),

The image shows a musical score for the piece 'Hop Bird' by Judith Exley. It is in 2/4 time and consists of four bars. The top staff is the vocal line with lyrics: 'Hop bird Hop a-cross new mown'. The bottom two staves are the piano accompaniment, starting with a piano (p) dynamic. The accompaniment features a repetitive rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and rests.

Figure 46: *Hop Bird* (Judith Exley), Classical, grade 1 (bars 1-4). Values for the whole piece ($S = 7$): RO= 0.49, RPC = 0.02, MC= 0.27, MPC = 0.06, H= 0.33

the reduced pitch set used for the melody, which only uses C4, E4, G4, B4, D5, and being composed using repetitive and simple rhythmic patterns.

The opposite case is represented by *We Are The Champions*, from Grade 6 of the Rock & Pop collection (Figure 45). When navigating through the interactive visualization, we observe that this score is surprisingly high in descriptor values given the grade it belongs to. Its classification might be explained by other factors, such as a pitch range of almost two octaves reaching C6, large leaps reaching an octave, fast passages with complicated syllabic articulation, an extreme dynamic range from *pp* to *fff*, and harmonic progressions with frequent four note chords (see Figure 45). These examples illustrate how accompaniment support is just one of the many factors that contribute to the classification of a particular piece into a difficulty level.

6.8 Conclusions and future work

In this work we propose five descriptors for characterizing piano accompaniment support in the context of music education. We implement a framework to compute the proposed descriptors on a corpus of copyrighted machine readable scores compiled from the syllabi developed by the anonymous publisher for teaching singing in Classical and Pop & Rock genres. In addition, we provide interactive visualizations to navigate through the results and we discuss how these descriptors can be used for further research on educational symbolic music data.

We discuss the influence of accompaniment support on how the corpus is structured

		Classical grades pairs																																		
feature	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.7	3.8	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.8	5.6	5.7	5.8	6.7	6.8	7.8
MC	.1	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	.94	**	.13	.13	.08	*	*	*	.27	.27	.17	*	.12	.54	.54	.92	.56	.6	1	.8	.07	.14	.8	*	.14	.42	.43	.16
MPC	.09	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	.68	*	.05	.05	.08	*	.07	*	.27	.27	.17	*	.12	.87	.87	.67	.71	.56	.87	.63	.92	.32	.8	.67	.14	.42	.2	.43
RO	.82	.4	*	.08	.15	.09	**	**	.68	.13	.73	.43	.46	*	.21	.05	.73	.38	.34	*	.21	.87	.87	.63	.86	.69	1	.92	.23	.69	.99	.63	.84	.42	.69	.69
RPC	.07	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	.68	.18	.38	.1	.17	*	.19	.38	.73	.22	.59	.08	.23	1	1	.36	.23	.67	.87	.36	.28	.36	.67	.56	.67	.05	.74	.39
H	.08	*	**	**	**	**	**	**	.18	*	*	.15	*	**	**	.05	.15	.56	.34	*	.06	1	.87	1	.56	.26	1	1	.56	.34	.86	.48	.4	.79	.23	.89
		Rock & pop grades pairs																																		
feature	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.7	3.8	4.5	4.6	4.7	4.8	5.6	5.7	5.8	6.7	6.8	7.8
MC	.28	*	.28	.14	.66	.24	.66	.13	.28	.66	.3	.66	.24	.66	.42	.28	.58	.09	.42	.24	.24	.82	1	.99	.99	.89	.76	.68	.6	.34	.66	.89	.66	.95	.72	.43
MPC	.66	.28	.28	.24	.98	.66	.42	.66	.09	.28	.58	.28	.42	.24	.42	.98	.64	.66	.66	.66	.66	.89	.66	.89	.66	.99	.24	.5	.15	.75	.99	.99	.89	1	.95	.72
RO	.28	.98	.66	.5	.66	.89	.89	.42	.09	.28	*	.66	.06	.06	**	.28	.89	.28	.66	.24	.42	.3	.98	.89	.89	.24	*	.41	.34	.86	.24	.13	.06	.72	.72	.43
RPC	.66	.98	.66	.86	.66	.99	.89	.66	.66	.66	.2	.28	.89	.66	.13	.98	.89	.98	.89	.99	.89	.89	.98	.66	.99	.89	.58	.78	.78	.91	.42	.42	.89	.95	.72	.72
H	.28	*	.66	.41	.66	.66	.42	.24	.28	.98	.64	.66	.42	.24	.66	.28	.08	.28	.06	*	.06	.94	.98	.42	.66	.42	.86	.68	.53	.68	.89	.89	.66	.72	.95	.43

Table 2: We report the p values computed with the KS test for each pair of grades, for the five features and for Classical and Rock & Pop. Marks * and ** denote p -values less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

in difficulty levels. As future research, this analysis may be extended by considering other variables which are used in structuring the corpus. Furthermore, studying the educational accompaniment arrangements through computational approaches contributes to the research on automatic accompaniment generation systems and may help designing personalized accompaniments.

Although we focus on the vocal repertoire, this study may be extended to the education of several different monophonic instruments.

The research of this chapter will be published in the future [80].

Chapter 7

Algorithmic Composition based on difficulty level

In the present chapter, we propose generative piano music composition techniques biased to certain levels of difficulty. The aim is to create a system capable of composing musical works performable by a musician with a particular skill level. In other words, we want to explore the composition of individualised musical works biased to a specific difficulty departing from the computational methods proposed in previous chapters. Bearing this in mind, we have made the system grounded on an existing model for generating piano music with transformers [81] and the technique difficulty models proposed in Section 5. It is the first proof of concept to demonstrate this personalised composition for enhancing Music Education.

7.1 Motivations

Throughout the history of Music technology, the idea of creating a full music teacher, a full-fledged musician or a full composer has been present. However, with the rise of computational creativity [82], the concept of "human in the loop" is considered more seriously. It is perhaps the best optimistic vision of the music and musicians tomorrow. The mentioned vision is not to replace the human with a machine but to extend the human's capabilities to be a super-human. In the future, a teacher could

detect a student’s technical difficulties. From there, idiomatic piano pieces could be composed to meet the students needs.

Music pieces covering some aspects of technique are not a new concept. Technical studies are focused mainly to cover a particular technical music skill. However, each student is different, and technical studies are often too generalised to every piano student. Furthermore, some piano editions contain exercises or even studies to improve the necessary technique of some musical compositions. For example, the Cortot - Chopin etudes present several piano exercises to develop the technical demands that each Chopin etude contains.

7.2 Challenges

The system developed in the context of this chapter wants to be a proof of concept. We have created heuristics to measure difficulty and others for measuring fundamental aspects of piano compositions, proposed in Section 5.4. We want to use the heuristics as constraints or control mechanisms over the transformer-based generative piano music system [81].

We have decided to use midi as base representation because the concept of Automatic Music Composition has mutated to Automatic Music Generation in the last years. Therefore, the current state of the art models does not work over a score representation because they focus only on the music’s expressive sound generation (MIDI), not on creating music scores capable of being performed by a human. For time constraints, we assume this fact. However, we are clear that to make this system operate on an industry level, it would be needed to generate scores, not MIDI files.

Another big challenge is the evaluation. The best way for evaluating this system would be a perceptual survey of experts. We can not evaluate some MIR tasks with a ground truth approach. In particular, this chapter requires experts with experience teaching and outstanding ear skills (the output is in midi format). Due to the exploratory character of this chapter, we only survey a single expert, the

master thesis author. The complete and not biased evaluation of this system would take more time than the development of the system itself.

7.3 Dataset

Mikrokosmos, by Béla Bartók, was one of the first full-fledged music education methods and one of the greatest pedagogical works. It consists of six volumes containing 153 progressive piano pieces composed between 1926 and 1939. Individual pieces range from simple beginner études to complex, covering broad technical and musical aspects with a modern musical language. Mikrokosmos "appears as a synthesis of all the musical and technical problems which were treated and in some cases only partially solved in the previous piano works," according to Bartók. Volumes one and two are devoted to his son Péter, while volumes five and six are designed to be performed in concerts. Bartók also indicated that piano students could also play these pieces on other keyboard instruments.

Not all the Mikrokosmos pieces are available in a machine-readable format, such as MIDI or MusicXML. Therefore, to transcribe all the parts, this youtube video ¹ has been downloaded. An amateur pianist performs the Mikrokosmos recorded pieces. In the youtube description are the beginnings of each of the 153 works. Therefore, this timing present in the description allows us to split the Mikrokosmos specific pieces. Later, we transcribe each musical composition with the music transcription model "onsets and frames" [83] authored by the Magenta team. The Mikrokosmos pieces are the reminiscence seed on the system instance.

7.4 Algorithmic Composition Pipeline

In this section, we expose the pipeline created for generating music biased to a difficulty level, as shown in Figure 47.

The Transformer Architecture as generative music system.

¹Available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uJXnj55_BzI

Figure 47: Difficulty biased music generation pipeline.

Long pieces of music are difficult to compose because they contain musical form at various timescales, ranging from millisecond timings to motifs to phrases to section repetition. Music Transformer [81] is an attention-based neural network developed by the magenta team to produce music with enhanced long-term coherence. We start with this method and fine-tune it based on difficulty and playability constraints.

Two hands midi source separation

Music Transformer generates the musical piece in MIDI format. However, the output MIDI files are encoded only in one channel, not divided for each hand. To our knowledge, only one proposal has attempted to make two hands source separation of MIDIs, the system proposed by Nakamura et al. [39], but stating only a 50%

accuracy.

The two hands source separation algorithm proposed in this chapter is based on agglomerative clustering. The centres of each cluster/hand are the lowest and highest midi notes, and the music notes are assigned to the closest cluster. Moreover, an octave filter is applied when the two human hands cannot perform the notes.

Playability feature

A piano piece is playable if and only if we can finger it for a particular hand. For this purpose, the automatic fingering system Pianoplayer has been used [43]. It is based on a dynamic programming algorithm guided by a cost function that measures the hand's effort, described in Section 4.4. We consider a piece not playable if there are more than ten notes that cannot be fingered or have a depth of more than ten notes (very complex composition writing).

Measuring fingering difficulty

The concept of musical difficulty itself causes ambiguity, as is stated in Section 5. The musical aspects that are difficult for one person are not necessarily difficult for another. Moreover, music performance difficulty has many dimensions. Musical pieces that have not very demanding technical performative requirements could require an extremely high sound sensitivity, e.g. the piano repertoire of Erik Satie. Many of the proposals for computationally measuring difficulty focus on specific dimensions of music. However, piano students in the first years give special attention to the piano technique, which is progressively learned, as is stated on the state of the art 3. For this reason, the model for detecting difficulty focuses on piano technique.

The Pianoplayer algorithm, exposed in Section 4.4, is based on the cost function, interpreted as the effort the hand has to make for playing. In other words, the objective state of the algorithm is to minimise the effort the hand has to make when playing the musical work.

To calculate the difficulty, we summarise each hand's time series's effort in the musical work with statistics, in the same way that Section 5.4. We trained a support

vector machine. The model correlates the Mikrokosmos difficulty with the piano technique. The balanced accuracy score in the test set is 75%.

7.5 Results

We have developed an interface to select the Mikrokosmos book to recall as reminiscence (6 books) and the required difficulty level by the user (3 levels), as shown in Figure 48. We can generate music with reminiscence in any of the six books and at the three difficulty levels.

Figure 48: Difficulty biased music generation user interface.

The two study examples work from Book 1 with the lowest difficulty level, as shown in Figure 49, and work from Book VI with the highest level of difficulty, as shown in Figure 50. The results surpassed our expectations. The system demonstrates that it is possible to generate an individualised repertoire for a particular piano level. However, it would be challenging to evaluate without an extensive experts survey. Moreover, many biases can arise, for example, if the method generates only a specific part of the repertoire or if some technical aspects are unrepresented.

7.6 Conclusions

This chapter shows that it is possible to make individualised works for each piano music student. It is a minimal prototype, but it could be an active research line in the data-driven Music Education area with more data.

Figure 49: Music generated reminiscence of the the easiest book and the easiest technical level.

Figure 50: Music generated reminiscence of the the most difficult book and the most difficult technical level.

Chapter 8

Further Work

In the present chapter, we want to analyse future horizons and challenges while writing the rest of the chapters. This chapter can be considered as the zero year PhD proposal.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Section 8.1 details the primary future research line about the music difficulty search and the creation of related data collections. Section 8.2 and Section 8.3 addresses the new horizons in automatic fingering and composition. Section 8.4 and Section 8.5 expose we do not want to limit our research uniquely to the symbolic domain and Section 8.6 states we want to explore data-driven Music Education in other music instruments. Moreover, In Sections 8.7 8.8 8.9 we identify Machine Learning techniques that we want to explore in the near future. Finally, Section 8.10 draws the further work chapter conclusions.

8.1 Difficulty Analysis: Data First

The understanding of music difficulty might be the mainline in further research. Firstly, we want to create a ecosystem of corpora and datasets at least as representative as other Music Technology fields, to conduct research with state-of-the-art data-driven methods. We want develop a sustainable and constructive ecosystem for studying difficulty and linking Music Information Retrieval with Music Education

from music symbolic data.

The Internet is full of noisy and uncategorised symbolic music data. The multitude of different formats, copyright issues, and lack of methods to assess the quality of the data generate this chaotic scenario. There are two families of machine-readable formats, the score representation and the piano roll family.

There score representation formats encode all the information of the original score. Among them, we can find MEI, humdrum or musicXML. It is not easy to find sheet music available for piano in the first two formats. However, there are web sites like Musescore or Musicalion with large amounts of musicXML piano scores. Musescore ¹ has more than 50000 piano scores and Musicalion ² more than 7000. Although many scores are public domain, these websites have restrictive policies to get the scores in bulk. Besides, many scores are copyrighted because these websites are not interested in creating an open community. However, both webs rely on a community to transcribe the scores from pdfs/paper to machine-readable formats. Musescore, until 2017, had an open data policy. Therefore, there are several copies of Musescore data from before the terms of use changes, as Musescore dataset ³. In the particular case of piano scores, the Musescore dataset has 50,000 works, but only 2000 authored by very well-known composers, defining "very well-known" as the composers analysed by Weiss in his doctoral thesis [84]. Finally, another challenge is the quality of the data. People transcribe the scores into machine-readable formats with a varying range of quality. It is not easy to evaluate the score's quality and, above all, the quality of the details, such as the editor's fingers, articulations, etc.

The piano-roll formats, such as midi, encodes explicitly only musical pitch and dynamic across time. On the one hand, some formats have metadata, adding other semantic music notation to the piano-roll, for example midi format also encodes time signature. On the other hand, it is possible to extract non semantically encoded information with algorithms [76] such as time signatures, rhythmic figures or articulations, although with some errors. There are numerous midis resources in the

¹Available at: musescore.com

²Available at: musicalion.com

³Available at: <https://github.com/Xmader/musescore-downloader>

piano case ⁴ because silent pianos and electronic keyboards can record it. The main problem is that the two hands are not semantically coded. In other words, we do not know which hand has played which note. Therefore, two hands source separation from midi data should be the first challenge to surpass for further research. The copyright is often not explicit, but we can use this data privately and distribute only the models. We cannot quickly assess the quality of the data. The two problematic cases are if the performance is low quality or if the file is midi transcribed from audio directly, both instances would generate a massive amount of noise.

Finally, there are non-machine-readable formats, such as images and, in particular, PDFs. The open community is enormous, with IMSLP ⁵ as the leader project. IMSLP community has contributed with more than 40,000 piano pdf public license scores. It is essential to distinguish between scanned scores and scores transcribed and converted from a score editor; the latter is clean while the former can have a lot of noise from the scanner. We can convert scores into a machine-readable format with Optical Music Recognition (OMR) software. Although OMR has come a long way in recent years, transcriptions still have a lot of noise. OMR transcription errors is a very time-consuming task, it was experienced transcribing Mikrokosmos Dataset. The tools to perform these transcriptions are not time optimised, and this is also a possible research niche. Moreover, another line of research is to work with uncorrected transcribed scores, even if it is a very noisy scenario. However, a first step is required to sort the scores and divide the books' pieces. Consequently, we must select by hand before transcribing the scores. For example, the alternative measures of the scores have to be deselected, which produce errors and noise when transcribed.

To sum up, we might expose a path to create a sustainable corpora and datasets ecosystem, allowing further research.

First of all, we might try to link the metadata difficulty available from the major publishers and major examination boards with public domain symbolic data. Fol-

⁴Available in web communities such as: freemidi.com, mideworld.com, midisfree.com or bit-midi.com

⁵Available at: ismlp.org

lowing two principles, ambiguity and balanced data. We might create an ambiguous representation to profit any good quality resource, whether in score representation format, piano-roll or both. We might balance underrepresented classes by OMR [31] transcribing and hand-fixing scores belonging to those classes. Therefore, we might create a representative dataset to evaluate the models.

In addition, we might create a public corpus with metadata linked to noisy resources. The biggest challenge might be transcribing with OMR methods part of the IMSLP collection. This task might require considerable effort to minimise noise. We might use noisy label classification techniques [85] to increase the knowledge to later classifying the primary no-noisy dataset.

Another challenge might be to use all the symbolic music data even if it has no labels thanks to semi-supervised learning [86]. There are several methods to conduct semi-supervised learning as: (1) create pseudo labels and transfer knowledge to the problem to be solved, (2) use a related task, such as Music Generation, Piano Fingering or Style Recognition, to train on the unlabeled dataset and transfer learning to the main task or (3) use Autoencoders to summarise representations in embeddings. We can use these embeddings to train the model in the main problem.

Finally, another line of research is to generate symbolic data to improve the feature extractors. One technique is contrastive learning [87], based on creating extensive synthesised data from a simple problem, train a model on that simple problem and transfer knowledge to the more complex task.

8.2 Automatic Fingering

We also want to develop tools to create finger corpora to evaluate our algorithms. We can collect data in more agile ways than hand-crafted, such as recording pianists and extracting the fingers with computer vision. In the future, we want to consider Pianoplayer to generate fingering for both hands simultaneously, performing two hands source separation [39]. We also want to create corpora to evaluate two hands source separation and create specialised models only for this task. Besides, we

might improve the reinforcement learning approach from offline learning [88] and with reinforcement learning multi-scenario methods. In the future, we can expand the automatic fingering methods to string instruments, such as violin.

8.3 Automatic Composition Algorithms

We think generating a personalised repertoire for the particular needs of a music student is a challenging long-term goal for data-driven Music Education. We expose a first approach in Chapter 7. In the future, we would like to extend this system with style [3] as a mechanism of control. In addition, it is fundamental to improve the piano voice/hand source separation model and design a descriptor to measure readability. Finally, we would like to finetuning the Music Transformer with reinforcement learning, with the difficulty constraints as reward function [89, 90].

8.4 Audio for Music Education

We want to make minor incursions into the other representations of music, especially in the audio domain. In particular, we want to work in audio tasks score-informed such as pitch recognition score-informed, audio-score alignment, etc. We want to conduct small audio research projects related to the research lines at MTG. For example, we are improving the existing models for tone quality assessment. In addition, we want to collaborate with all colleagues in the MTG with Music Education-related research to have a more global perspective on data-driven Music Education.

8.5 Computer Vision for Music Education

Another challenge is to explore Computer Vision techniques. First, to examine the use of OMR or to create better tools to annotate symbolic music data. Second, to extract extended information from videos, for example, the piano fingering [91].

8.6 Other instruments

In this dissertation, we chose piano as the study case because of the large available data, especially in score representation and MIDI formats. However, other monophonic instruments might be easier to transcribe from sheet music with Optical Music Recognition methods and audio with music transcription methods. Due to the number of resources available, the two natural target instruments would be violin and vocal.

8.7 Explainable Machine Learning

Explainable Machine Learning has been a challenge already considered in this master thesis, especially in Section 5. Computational methods have to have a dialogue with the musician to have a direct relationship with the musician. To say what is right or wrong does not add much from a Music Education perspective to the user. However, explaining why a Music Education model makes a particular decision has more musical richness than the decision itself. Explainable Machine Learning is a growing field, and we want all our research follows the new state-of-the-art explainable methods.

8.8 Graph Neural Networks

The score representation as a graph is the most musically complete and obvious representation from my perspective as a musician. Although there has been little research on this topic [92] from the Music Information Retrieval community, there has been a breakthrough in Graph Neural Networks [93] in the last few years. Therefore, we might consider this representation of symbolic music in further research.

8.9 Natural Language Processing

Music can be considered as a grammar [72, 62]. Therefore, we could consider several Natural Language Processing techniques in future symbolic music research. For

example, transfer learning from extensive deep learning models over score representation grounded problems.

8.10 Conclusions

Future work might probably be focused on discovering what is the difficulty in piano symbolic data. In addition, we want to expand this research to other instruments, in particular, voice and strings. Moreover, we want to explore different domains of Music Education technology with small and closed projects and collaborating with other colleagues. But above all I want my research to be practical helping real musicians, and multi-disciplinary between Musicology, Music Education and Music Technology.

Chapter 9

The last chapter

The present chapter is intended to close the exploratory analysis on applying computational methods in symbolic music data for Music Education. The first Section 9.1 will repeat the contributions of this dissertation. Finally, we will conclude this master thesis with the overall conclusions exposed in Section 9.2.

9.1 Contributions report

We repeat the list of "Computational methods to study piano music in education context" main contributions for attempting to provide a global overview.

- Redesign an existing automatic piano fingering proposal to work at the level of a human. It is not optimal but fulfils the comfortable fingering principle.
- Develop a reinforcement learning algorithm that can learn to be flexible like a human when generating piano fingering.
- Collect a progressive difficulty dataset grounded on Béla Bartók Mikrokosmos Sz 107. It is compiled in a sheet-music machine-readable format.
- Computationally validate that piano technique is an important feature to characterize difficulty.

- Create algorithms to detect the local difficulty of a musical piece through the global difficulty annotations.
- Design a series of descriptors to understand the relationship between the piano accompaniment and the soloist.
- Develop a prototype to show how current automatic composition systems can be biased to generate an individualised music repertoire for each student.
- The development of several preprocessing pipelines and web tools to visualise corpora and scores that will help us in future research.

9.2 Global conclusions

"Computational methods to study piano music in education context" master thesis proposes technological approaches to various aspects of Piano Music Education in its most global view, from technique to accompaniment and composition. The results surpassed all our expectations. We have shown that it is possible to create feasible and even optimal personal piano fingering, model the difficulty from the piano technique, generate personalised pieces of music, and understand the relationship between lead-voice and the piano accompaniment. In addition, we have realised how visualising the results in a meaningful way for the musicians is as important as the computational methods involved. Finally, we want to highlight sheet-music is a much richer entity semantically than working with audios from a musical perspective. However, the score resources available are more limited than expected. Therefore, for further sustainable research, we must consider invest effort in creating new Music Education symbolic corpora.

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Appendix A

Fingering Appendix

Air on the G String

Suite No. 3, BWV 1068

J. S. Bach

Measures 1-5 of the piece. The treble clef staff features a melodic line with a triplet of eighth notes (3) in measure 1, followed by a half note (5) in measure 2, and a quarter note (5) in measure 3. The bass clef staff provides a harmonic accompaniment with notes 5, 2, 1, 4, 5, 1, 2, 5, 5, 1, 2, #4, 5, 2, 1, 4, 5, 2, 1, 4.

Measures 6-9. The treble clef staff continues the melodic line with eighth notes (4, 2, 1, 3, 2, 5, 4) and a half note (5) in measure 6, followed by quarter notes (4, 2, 1, 3, 1, 4, 3) and a dotted quarter note (3) in measure 7. The bass clef staff accompaniment includes notes #5, 2, 5, 1, 5, 2, 1, #4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 4.

Measures 10-13. The treble clef staff features a sequence of eighth notes (3, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 1) and a half note (1) in measure 10, followed by quarter notes (1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1) and a half note (1) in measure 11. The bass clef staff accompaniment includes notes 5, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 5.

Measures 14-16. The treble clef staff begins with a repeat sign, followed by eighth notes (3, 4, 3, 2, 3, 1) and a half note (5) in measure 14, followed by quarter notes (2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2) in measure 15. The bass clef staff accompaniment includes notes 5, 2, 1, 4, 5, 2, 1, 4, #0, 0, 0, 0.

Measures 17-20. The treble clef staff features a sequence of eighth notes (4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4) and a half note (3) in measure 17, followed by quarter notes (2, 1, 3, 2, 3, 4, 5, 2) in measure 18. The bass clef staff accompaniment includes notes 5, 2, 1, 4, 5, 2, 1, 4, #5, 4, 3, #5, 4, 1, 3, 2.

21

Musical notation for measures 21-24. The piece is in D major (two sharps). Measure 21: Treble clef has a whole note D4 with finger 1; Bass clef has a whole note D3 with finger 0. Measure 22: Treble clef has a half note D4 (finger 2) and a half note E4 (finger 4) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 0). Measure 23: Treble clef has a half note F#4 (finger 3) and a half note G4 (finger 1) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 24: Treble clef has a half note A4 (finger 2) and a half note B4 (finger 5) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5).

25

Musical notation for measures 25-28. Measure 25: Treble clef has a quarter note D4 (finger 3), a quarter note E4 (finger 2), and a quarter note F#4 (finger 1); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 26: Treble clef has a half note D4 (finger 2) and a half note E4 (finger 3) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 27: Treble clef has a half note F#4 (finger 4) and a half note G4 (finger 3) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 4). Measure 28: Treble clef has a half note A4 (finger 5) and a half note B4 (finger 4) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 0).

29

Musical notation for measures 29-31. Measure 29: Treble clef has a whole note D4 (finger 5); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 30: Treble clef has a half note D4 (finger 1) and a half note E4 (finger 2) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 31: Treble clef has a half note F#4 (finger 4) and a half note G4 (finger 2) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 4).

32

Musical notation for measures 32-35. Measure 32: Treble clef has a half note D4 (finger 1) and a half note E4 (finger 2) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 1). Measure 33: Treble clef has a half note F#4 (finger 3) and a half note G4 (finger 5) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 4). Measure 34: Treble clef has a half note A4 (finger 1) and a half note B4 (finger 2) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 35: Treble clef has a half note D5 (finger 2) and a half note E5 (finger 3) beamed together; Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 4).

36

Musical notation for measures 36-39. Measure 36: Treble clef has a quarter note D4 (finger 1), a quarter note E4 (finger 2), and a quarter note F#4 (finger 1); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 1). Measure 37: Treble clef has a quarter note G4 (finger 2), a quarter note A4 (finger 3), and a quarter note B4 (finger 2); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 5). Measure 38: Treble clef has a quarter note D5 (finger 3), a quarter note E5 (finger 2), and a quarter note F#5 (finger 3); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 0). Measure 39: Treble clef has a whole note D5 (finger 0); Bass clef has a whole note D3 (finger 0).

Invention No 4 in D minor

BWV 775

Allegro

J.S. Bach

The musical score is presented in five systems, each with a treble and bass staff. The key signature is D minor (two flats). The time signature is 3/8. The piece is marked 'Allegro'. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, ties, and dynamic markings like 'w' (pizzicato) and 'b' (basso continuo). The piece concludes with a final cadence in the bass staff.

Invention # 4 by J.S. Bach (BWV 775) for Piano

Mike Magatagan (magataganm@cox.net or MMagatagan on <http://www.MuseScore.com>)

Musical score for measures 35-41. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure numbers 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, and 41 are indicated at the beginning of each measure. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The key signature has one flat (B-flat).

Musical score for measures 42-47. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure numbers 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, and 47 are indicated at the beginning of each measure. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The key signature has one flat (B-flat).

Musical score for measures 48-53. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure numbers 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, and 53 are indicated at the beginning of each measure. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The key signature has one flat (B-flat). Measure 53 ends with a fermata over a whole note.

Invention # 4 by J.S. Bach (BWV 775) for PianoMike Magatagan (magataganm@cox.net or MMagatagan on <http://www.MuseScore.com>)

Jesu, Joy of Man's Desiring

Cantata 147 - "Herz und Mund und Tat und Leben"

J.S. Bach

Sintetizador de Cuerdas

Measures 1-4 of the piece. The treble clef staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 3, 3 5 4 5 4 2 1 2 1, 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 5 3, 2 3 4 1 2 3 4 3 2. The bass clef staff contains a harmonic accompaniment with fingerings: 2 5, 2 4, 1 4, 3 5, 4 5, 2 4, 2 5, 1 4, 1 4, 1 5, 2.

Measures 5-8 of the piece. The treble clef staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 4 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 3, 3 5 4 5 4 3 2 3 4, 1 4 3 2 1 3 1 3 2, 1 2 3 5 4 2 1 3 5, 4 2 1 3 2 1. The bass clef staff contains a harmonic accompaniment with fingerings: 2 5, 1 4, 1 4, 3 5, 3 5, 1 3, 0 4, 0 0, 0 0, 0 0, 2 3 4.

Measures 9-15 of the piece. The treble clef staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 5 3 1, 4, 5 3 1, 5 4 1 2 3 4 2 3 4 3, 5 3 2 1 2 3 5 4 3, 5, 5 3 2, 4 2 1. The bass clef staff contains a harmonic accompaniment with fingerings: 3 4 5, 4 3 2, 2 5, 1 2, 3 4 5, 4 4 2.

Measures 16-20 of the piece. The treble clef staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 3 4 5 4 3, 2 3 2 1 3 1 2 4 3, 3 5 4 5 4 2 1 2 1, 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 5 3, 2 3 4 1 2 3 4 3 2. The bass clef staff contains a harmonic accompaniment with fingerings: 3 2, 2 5, 1 4, 1 4, 3 5, 4 5, 2 4, 2 5, 1 4, 1 4, 1 5, 2.

Measures 21-24 of the piece. The treble clef staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 4 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 3, 3 5 4 5 4 3 2 3 4, 1 4 3 2 1 3 1 3 2, 1 2 3 5 4 3 2, 4 1 3 2 1. The bass clef staff contains a harmonic accompaniment with fingerings: 2 5, 1 4, 1 4, 3 5, 3 5, 1 3, 2 5, 3 4 5, 2 4 5, 5 4 3, 1 2 1.

26

Musical notation for measures 26-29. Treble clef has chords and a melodic line. Bass clef has a bass line. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5.

30

Musical notation for measures 30-31. Treble clef has a descending melodic line. Bass clef has a simple bass line.

31

Musical notation for measures 32-35. Treble clef has chords and a melodic line. Bass clef has a bass line. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5.

36

Musical notation for measures 36-41. Treble clef has a complex melodic line with many slurs. Bass clef has a bass line with some slurs.

42

Musical notation for measures 42-47. Treble clef has chords and a melodic line. Bass clef has a bass line. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5.

48

Musical notation for measures 48-53. Treble clef has a complex melodic line with many slurs. Bass clef has a bass line with some slurs.

53

4 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 3 3 5 4 5 4 3 2 3 4 1 4 3 2 1 2 1 3 2 0 2 1

2 5 1 4 1 4 3 5 2 5 1 2 2 5 0

Prelude no. 13

BWV 858, in F Major

J. S. Bach

$\text{♩} = 65$

4

7

10

13

15

Musical notation for measures 15-17. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 15: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4, 2, 1, #4. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 4, 3, 2. Measure 16: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings #4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 5, 2, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 3, 4, 3, 1. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 3, 2, 3, 5, 1, 1, 2. Measure 17: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 5, 2, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 3, 4, 3, 1. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 3, 2, 4.

18

Musical notation for measures 18-20. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 18: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4, 2, 1, 2. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 2, 5. Measure 19: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 4, 2, 1, 3, 5, 2, 5, 4. Measure 20: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 2, 3, 5, 4. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 5, 3.

21

Musical notation for measures 21-23. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 21: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 4, 5, 4, 5, 2, 4, 5, 3, 5, 3, 4, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 1, 2, 1. Measure 22: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 3, 4, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 4, 5, 1, 2, 3, 1, 3. Measure 23: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 2. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 3, 1, 3.

24

Musical notation for measures 24-26. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 24: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 5, 4, 3, 5. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 1, 4, 2, 1, 2, 4, 1. Measure 25: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 2, 4, 5, 2, 4, 1, 2, 1, 2. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 2, 3, 4, 1. Measure 26: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 5, 3, 1, 5. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 4, 2, 3, 4, 1, 5.

27

Musical notation for measures 27-28. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 27: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 2, 4, 1, 3, 5, 1, 4, 5, 1, 2, 3. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 5, 1. Measure 28: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 2, 4, 1, 2, 1, 4, 2, 5. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 5, 1, 2, 1.

29

Musical notation for measures 29-31. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 29: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 4, 1, 4, 5, 3, 4, 1, 3, 3, 5, 4, 3. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 3, 5, 3, 5. Measure 30: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 4, 5, 3, 4, 2, 1, 0. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 4, 3, 0. Measure 31: Treble clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 4, 5, 3, 4, 2, 1, 0. Bass clef has a sequence of eighth notes with fingerings 4, 3, 0.

Lady "Di"

Allegretto

Richard Clayderman

The musical score for "Lady Di" is presented in a grand staff format, consisting of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is common time (C). The piece is marked "Allegretto" and begins with a dynamic of *mf* (mezzo-forte). The score is divided into four systems, each containing two measures. The first system (measures 1-2) features a treble staff with a quarter note G4 (fingered 4), followed by eighth notes A4-B4 (fingered 3-2), C5-B4 (fingered 1-3), and a quarter note D5 (fingered 1). The bass staff has a quarter note G3 (fingered 5), followed by eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 4-1), C4-B3 (fingered 5-3), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The second system (measures 3-4) continues the melodic line in the treble with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The third system (measures 5-6) features a treble staff with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The fourth system (measures 7-8) features a treble staff with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The fifth system (measures 9-10) features a treble staff with a quarter note G4 (fingered 5), followed by eighth notes A4-B4 (fingered 3-2), C5-B4 (fingered 1-3), and a quarter note D5 (fingered 1). The bass staff has a quarter note G3 (fingered 5), followed by eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 4-1), C4-B3 (fingered 5-3), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The sixth system (measures 11-12) features a treble staff with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The seventh system (measures 13-14) features a treble staff with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The eighth system (measures 15-16) features a treble staff with eighth notes E5-D5 (fingered 3-4), F5-E5 (fingered 5-5), G5-F5 (fingered 4-3), and a quarter note G5 (fingered 2). The bass staff has eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 5-3), C4-B3 (fingered 4-1), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The ninth system (measures 17-18) features a treble staff with a quarter note G4 (fingered 5), followed by eighth notes A4-B4 (fingered 1-2), C5-B4 (fingered 1-2), and a quarter note D5 (fingered 1). The bass staff has a quarter note G3 (fingered 5), followed by eighth notes A3-B3 (fingered 3-2), C4-B3 (fingered 1-2), and a quarter note D4 (fingered 2). The piece concludes with a final chord in the bass staff consisting of G3, B3, and D4.

20

Musical notation for measures 20-22. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with various fingerings (5, 1, 5, 2, 5, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 2) and slurs. The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 5, 4, 1, 2, 5, 2, 5, 4, 3, 1, 2, 1, 5, 0, 0, 0).

23

Musical notation for measures 23-26. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains chords and arpeggios with fingerings (3, 2, 5, 3, 5, 4, 4, 2, 4, 2, 2, 3, 3, 2, 2, 1, 1, 4, 5, 5, 5, 0, 0, 0, 1). The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 1, 2, 4, 5, 2, 1, 5, 2, 5, 1, 5, 4, 1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 1, 2, 5, 4, 1, 2, 1, 2, 3, 1).

27

Musical notation for measures 27-30. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff has a fermata over measure 27, followed by a dynamic marking *f* and a melodic line with fingerings (5, 3, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 4, 2, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3). The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (5, 2, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1, 2, 5, 4, 1, 5, 3, 1, 2, 3, 5, 3, 1, 2, 5, 1, 3, 1, 5, 4, 1, 5, 3, 1, 2, 3).

31

Musical notation for measures 31-34. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with fingerings (1, 3, 4, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 4, 3, 4, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 2). The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (5, 3, 1, 2, 5, 2, 1, 2, 5, 4, 1, 3, 5, 2, 1, 3, 5, 4, 1, 2, 5, 1, 2, 1, 5, 4, 1, 4, 5, 1, 2, 1).

35

Musical notation for measures 35-38. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with fingerings (3, 4, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 4, 3, 4, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 2, 2). The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (5, 4, 1, 5, 1, 2, 3, 1, 5, 4, 1, 3, 5, 2, 1, 3, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 5, 4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0).

39

Musical notation for measures 39-42. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with fingerings (4, 1, 5, 1, 4, 5, 5, 1, 4, 5, 5, 1, 4, 1, 1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 5, 5, 1, 4, 5, 4, 5, 4, 1, 1, 2, 4, 5, 0). The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings (0, 0, 1, 2, 4, 5, 5, 0, 2, 4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 4, 5, 5, 5, 5, 1, 2, 4, 5, 5, 5, 1, 2, 3, 0, 4).

Les Baricades Mystérieuses"from Pièces de Clavecin (Book 2

Vivement

1 2 1 2 4 1 2 4 2 3 5 3 4 5 3 1 3 2 1 2 4 1 2 4 3 4 3 1 2 1 2 1 2 4 1

6 2 4 2 3 5 3 4 5 3 2 4 3 2 3 4 1 1 3 2 3 2 1 4 2 3 5 2 3 1 2 5 3 2 4 2

11 3 5 3 2 4 2 3 5 4 3 5 3 2 5 2 2 5 4 2 2 5 3 2 4 2 3 5 3 1 3 1

16 2 5 2 2 5 3 3 5 2 3 1 3 2 4 2 4 1 2 1 2 5 3 1 5 2 3 4 2 1 5 2

20 1 4 1 1 4 1 2 5 2 3 5 3 4 3 2 1 2 1 2 4 1 2 4 2 3 5 3 4 5 3 1 3 2

25 1 2 4 1 2 4 3 4 3 1 2 1 2 1 4 1 2 4 2 5 3 4 5 3 2 4 3 2 3 4 1 1 3 2

Franois Couperin, 1716-17

♩ = 125 ♩ = 100

30

3 2 1 2 1 4 5 3 3 4 2 2 3 2 1 2 5 4 4 5 3 3 4 2 2 3 2

Stringendo

34

3 1 5 2 1 4 1 3 4 3 2 1 3 1 3 4 2 1 2 1 2 4 1 2 4 2 3 5 3 4 5 3 1 3 2

con rubato
Tempo 1

39

1 2 4 1 2 4 3 4 3 1 2 1 2 1 4 1 2 4 2 5 3 4 5 3 2 4 3 2 3 4 1 1 3 2

44

3 2 3 5 3 3 5 3 3 4 1 2 3 1 3 4 2 2 4 2 3 5 4 2 5 2

Stringendo

48

2 1 2 3 5 3 5 2 5 2 2 5 2 2 5 2 2 5 2 1 5 2 2 5 4

52

2 5 2 2 5 2 1 5 2 2 5 4 2 5 2 2 5 2 1 5 2 2 5 4 2 5 2 2 5 2

57

62

Meno mosso *

67

72

Fugue No. 13 in 3 voices in F# Major

from "Das Wohltemperierte Klavier" Book I BWV 858
Johann Sebastian Bach (1685 - 1750)

The musical score is presented in five systems, each with a treble and bass staff. The key signature is F# major (three sharps) and the time signature is common time (C). The piece is in 3/4 time. The notation includes various musical symbols such as notes, rests, slurs, and fingerings. The first system starts with a treble clef and a common time signature. The second system begins with a measure number '3' above the treble staff. The third system begins with a measure number '4' above the treble staff. The fourth system begins with a measure number '6' above the treble staff. The fifth system begins with a measure number '7' above the treble staff. The score includes various musical notations such as notes, rests, slurs, and fingerings. The piece is in 3/4 time. The notation includes various musical symbols such as notes, rests, slurs, and fingerings. The first system starts with a treble clef and a common time signature. The second system begins with a measure number '3' above the treble staff. The third system begins with a measure number '4' above the treble staff. The fourth system begins with a measure number '6' above the treble staff. The fifth system begins with a measure number '7' above the treble staff. The score includes various musical notations such as notes, rests, slurs, and fingerings.

9

Musical notation for measures 9-10. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Measure 9 features a treble clef with a melodic line starting on G#4, moving to A4, B4, and C5, with a slur over the last two notes. The bass clef has a bass line starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, and D2. Measure 10 continues the melodic line in the treble and the bass line in the bass. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. A '7' is written below the treble staff in measure 9, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 9.

10

Musical notation for measures 11-12. Measure 11 continues the melodic line in the treble and the bass line in the bass. Measure 12 features a treble clef with a melodic line starting on G#4, moving to A4, B4, and C5, with a slur over the last two notes. The bass clef has a bass line starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, and D2. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. A '7' is written below the treble staff in measure 11, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 11.

12

Musical notation for measures 13-14. Measure 13 continues the melodic line in the treble and the bass line in the bass. Measure 14 features a treble clef with a melodic line starting on G#4, moving to A4, B4, and C5, with a slur over the last two notes. The bass clef has a bass line starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, and D2. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. A '7' is written below the treble staff in measure 13, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 13.

13

Musical notation for measures 15-16. Measure 15 continues the melodic line in the treble and the bass line in the bass. Measure 16 features a treble clef with a melodic line starting on G#4, moving to A4, B4, and C5, with a slur over the last two notes. The bass clef has a bass line starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, and D2. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. A '7' is written below the treble staff in measure 15, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 15.

15

Musical notation for measures 17-18. Measure 17 continues the melodic line in the treble and the bass line in the bass. Measure 18 features a treble clef with a melodic line starting on G#4, moving to A4, B4, and C5, with a slur over the last two notes. The bass clef has a bass line starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, and D2. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. A '7' is written below the treble staff in measure 17, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 17. A 'wavy' symbol is written above the treble staff in measure 18, and a '3' is written below the bass staff in measure 18.

16

Musical notation for measures 16 and 17. The piece is in A major (three sharps). Measure 16 features a complex right-hand part with triplets and sixteenth notes, and a left-hand part with a descending eighth-note pattern. Measure 17 continues with similar textures, including a triplet in the right hand and a descending eighth-note pattern in the left hand. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

18

Musical notation for measures 18 and 19. Measure 18 shows a right-hand part with a triplet and a descending eighth-note pattern, and a left-hand part with a descending eighth-note pattern. Measure 19 continues with similar textures, including a triplet in the right hand and a descending eighth-note pattern in the left hand. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

19

Musical notation for measures 20 and 21. Measure 20 features a right-hand part with a triplet and a descending eighth-note pattern, and a left-hand part with a descending eighth-note pattern. Measure 21 continues with similar textures, including a triplet in the right hand and a descending eighth-note pattern in the left hand. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

21

Musical notation for measures 22 and 23. Measure 22 shows a right-hand part with a triplet and a descending eighth-note pattern, and a left-hand part with a descending eighth-note pattern. Measure 23 continues with similar textures, including a triplet in the right hand and a descending eighth-note pattern in the left hand. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

22

Musical notation for measures 24 and 25. Measure 24 features a right-hand part with a triplet and a descending eighth-note pattern, and a left-hand part with a descending eighth-note pattern. Measure 25 continues with similar textures, including a triplet in the right hand and a descending eighth-note pattern in the left hand. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

24

Musical notation for measures 24-25. The system consists of a treble and bass clef. Measure 24 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 3), a quarter note A4 (finger 2), a quarter note B4 (finger 4), and a quarter note C5 (finger 3), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 3), a quarter note A3 (finger 1), a quarter note B3 (finger 1), and a quarter note C4 (finger 2). Measure 25 continues with a treble clef half note G4 (finger 4), a quarter note A4 (finger 1), a quarter note B4 (finger 3), and a quarter note C5 (finger 5), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 4), a quarter note A3 (finger 1), a quarter note B3 (finger 1), and a quarter note C4 (finger 2).

25

Musical notation for measures 25-26. Measure 25 continues from the previous system. Measure 26 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 3), a quarter note A4 (finger 5), a quarter note B4 (finger 5), and a quarter note C5 (finger 4), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 4), a quarter note A3 (finger 1), a quarter note B3 (finger 1), and a quarter note C4 (finger 2).

27

Musical notation for measures 27-28. Measure 27 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 5), a quarter note A4 (finger 3), a quarter note B4 (finger 2), and a quarter note C5 (finger 4), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 2), a quarter note A3 (finger 4), a quarter note B3 (finger 2), and a quarter note C4 (finger 3). Measure 28 continues with a treble clef half note G4 (finger 3), a quarter note A4 (finger 2), a quarter note B4 (finger 2), and a quarter note C5 (finger 3), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 2), a quarter note A3 (finger 4), a quarter note B3 (finger 2), and a quarter note C4 (finger 3).

28

Musical notation for measures 28-29. Measure 28 continues from the previous system. Measure 29 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 2), a quarter note A4 (finger 3), a quarter note B4 (finger 4), and a quarter note C5 (finger 5), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 2), a quarter note A3 (finger 1), a quarter note B3 (finger 1), and a quarter note C4 (finger 2). Measure 30 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 5), a quarter note A4 (finger 4), a quarter note B4 (finger 4), and a quarter note C5 (finger 5), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 2), a quarter note A3 (finger 4), a quarter note B3 (finger 2), and a quarter note C4 (finger 3).

30

Musical notation for measures 30-31. Measure 30 features a treble clef with a half note G4 (finger 5), a quarter note A4 (finger 3), a quarter note B4 (finger 5), and a quarter note C5 (finger 4), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 1), a quarter note A3 (finger 1), a quarter note B3 (finger 2), and a quarter note C4 (finger 1). Measure 31 continues with a treble clef half note G4 (finger 3), a quarter note A4 (finger 5), a quarter note B4 (finger 4), and a quarter note C5 (finger 2), all under a slur. The bass clef has a half note G3 (finger 2), a quarter note A3 (finger 3), a quarter note B3 (finger 4), and a quarter note C4 (finger 2).

31

Musical score for measures 31-32. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Measure 31 features a right-hand melody with notes G#4, A4, B4, C5, and a left-hand accompaniment with notes G#3, A3, B3, C4. Measure 32 includes a fermata over the first two notes of the right hand and a bracketed eighth-note figure in the left hand. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Dynamic markings include accents and hairpins.

33

Musical score for measures 33-34. Measure 33 continues the right-hand melody with notes D5, E5, F#5, G5 and left-hand accompaniment with notes G#3, A3, B3, C4. Measure 34 features a right-hand melody with notes G#4, A4, B4, C5 and a left-hand accompaniment with notes G#3, A3, B3, C4. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Dynamic markings include accents and hairpins.

Sonata "Facile" in Do Maggiore

K343

W.A. Mozart

Piano

♩ = 100

Musical notation for measures 5-8. The right hand features a complex melodic line with many slurs and ties. The left hand provides a simple harmonic accompaniment with chords and single notes.

Musical notation for measures 9-11. The right hand continues with a melodic line, including a trill in measure 11. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and moving lines.

Musical notation for measures 12-14. The right hand has a melodic line with a trill in measure 14. The left hand features a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in the bass.

Musical notation for measures 15-16. The right hand has a melodic line with a trill in measure 16. The left hand continues with a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.

Musical notation for measures 17-18. The right hand has a melodic line with a trill in measure 18. The left hand continues with a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes.

33

Musical score for measures 33-35. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 33 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 1, 3 1 2 3, 4 3 2 4, 5 4 3 5, 4, 1 2 1 2, 4 2 1 4, 5 3 1 2, 1 2 1, 2 1 2 3, 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 34 continues the treble staff sequence: 1, 2 1 2, 3 4 5, 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 3, 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 35 continues the treble staff sequence: 1, 2 1 2, 3 4 5, 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 3, 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

36

Musical score for measures 36-37. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 36 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 1 2 3, 1 2 3 4 5, 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 37 continues the treble staff sequence: 1 2 3, 4 5, 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

38

Musical score for measures 38-39. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 38 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 39 continues the treble staff sequence: 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1, 2 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

40

Musical score for measures 40-42. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 40 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 2 5 4 3 2 1, 4 1, 3 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1 2 1 2 3 1 2 1, 2, 3 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 41 continues the treble staff sequence: 3 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1 2 1 2 3 1 2 1, 2, 3 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 42 continues the treble staff sequence: 3 5 4 3 2 1, 2 1 2 1 2 3 1 2 1, 2, 3 4. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

43

Musical score for measures 43-46. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 43 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 1, 2 3 1, 4, 3, 4, 3 2 4 3, 1 2 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 44 continues the treble staff sequence: 1, 2 3 1, 4, 3, 4, 3 2 4 3, 1 2 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 45 continues the treble staff sequence: 1, 2 3 1, 4, 3, 4, 3 2 4 3, 1 2 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 46 continues the treble staff sequence: 1, 2 3 1, 4, 3, 4, 3 2 4 3, 1 2 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

47

Musical score for measures 47-50. The system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Measure 47 features a treble staff with a sequence of eighth notes: 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 48 continues the treble staff sequence: 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 49 continues the treble staff sequence: 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests. Measure 50 continues the treble staff sequence: 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2, 1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1. The bass staff has a whole note chord of G2 and B2, followed by rests.

50

50

52

52

55

55

58

58

61

61

64

64

67

1 1 1 3 3 3 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2 1 3

1 2 2 2 1 2 2 2 1 3 5 1 3 5 1 3 5 1 3 5 1 2 5 4 1 2 1 4 1 2 1 4 1 2 1 4 1 2 1

70

4 3 3 1 2 3 4 2 1 4 5 4 3 5 4 1 2 1 2 4 0 0 0 0 0 0

5 1 2 1 5 1 2 1 5 1 2 1 1 2 2 3 5

73

0 0 0 3 4 1 5 0 5

Canon in D Major

Pachelbel

Piano

Musical notation for measures 1-4. The piece is in D major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 80. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Measure 1: Treble clef has a half note D4 with a triplet of three eighth notes (E4, F#4, G4) above it. Bass clef has a half note D3 with a triplet of three eighth notes (E3, F#3, G3) below it. Measure 2: Treble clef has a half note E4. Bass clef has a half note E3. Measure 3: Treble clef has a half note F#4. Bass clef has a half note F#3. Measure 4: Treble clef has a half note G4. Bass clef has a half note G3.

Musical notation for measures 5-8. Measure 5: Treble clef has a half note A4 with a triplet of three eighth notes (B4, C5, D5) above it. Bass clef has a half note A3 with a triplet of three eighth notes (B3, C4, D4) below it. Measure 6: Treble clef has a half note B4. Bass clef has a half note B3. Measure 7: Treble clef has a half note C5. Bass clef has a half note C4. Measure 8: Treble clef has a half note D5. Bass clef has a half note D4.

Musical notation for measures 9-12. Measure 9: Treble clef has a half note E5 with a triplet of three eighth notes (F#5, G5, A5) above it. Bass clef has a half note E4 with a triplet of three eighth notes (F#4, G4, A4) below it. Measure 10: Treble clef has a half note F#5. Bass clef has a half note F#4. Measure 11: Treble clef has a half note G5. Bass clef has a half note G4. Measure 12: Treble clef has a half note A5. Bass clef has a half note A4.

Musical notation for measures 13-15. Measure 13: Treble clef has a half note B5 with a triplet of three eighth notes (C6, D6, E6) above it. Bass clef has a half note B4 with a triplet of three eighth notes (C5, D5, E5) below it. Measure 14: Treble clef has a half note C6. Bass clef has a half note C5. Measure 15: Treble clef has a half note D6. Bass clef has a half note D5.

Musical notation for measures 16-19. Measure 16: Treble clef has a half note E6 with a triplet of three eighth notes (F#6, G6, A6) above it. Bass clef has a half note E5 with a triplet of three eighth notes (F#5, G5, A5) below it. Measure 17: Treble clef has a half note F#6. Bass clef has a half note F#5. Measure 18: Treble clef has a half note G6. Bass clef has a half note G5. Measure 19: Treble clef has a half note A6. Bass clef has a half note A5.

18

Musical notation for measures 18 and 19. The treble clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 4, 3, 4, 5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 2, 1, 2, 5, 3, 5, 3, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 5. The bass clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2.

20

Musical notation for measures 20, 21, and 22. The treble clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 2, 4, 3, 4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 5, 4, 3, 5, 4, 5, 5, 3, 2, 5, 3, 1, 5, 3, 1, 5, 3, 1, 5, 4, 2, 5, 4, 3, 1. The bass clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1.

23

Musical notation for measures 23, 24, and 25. The treble clef staff contains chords with fingerings: 5, 3, 2, 4, 2, 1, 3, 2, 1, 3, 2, 1, 4, 3, 5, 4. The bass clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1.

26

Musical notation for measures 26, 27, 28, and 29. The treble clef staff contains chords with fingerings: 5, 3, 5, 3, 4, 2, 3, 2, 4, 2, 5, 3, 1, 0, 3, 2, 1. The bass clef staff contains eighth notes with fingerings: 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2, 5, 4, 3, 1, 5, 3, 2, 1, 0, 5.

test_octaves

This musical score, titled "test_octaves", is written in 4/4 time and consists of four systems of piano accompaniment. Each system includes a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff, with fingerings indicated by numbers 1 through 5. The piece is characterized by a steady eighth-note accompaniment in the bass and a melody in the treble that moves in octaves. The key signature changes from C major to G major (one sharp) at the beginning of the third system, and then to F major (one flat) at the beginning of the fourth system. The score is divided into measures by vertical bar lines, and the systems are numbered 1, 5, 7, and 9 at the start of their respective treble staves.

2

10

Musical score for guitar, consisting of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The score is divided into three measures. The first measure contains a sequence of chords, each with a fret number above it: 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 5, 0. The second and third measures are empty. The tablature below the bass staff shows the fret numbers for each string: 1/4, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 1/5, 0/5.

test_scales

Musical score for the first system (measures 1-4) in 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 60. The key signature is C major. The score consists of two staves: a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Measure 1: Treble (1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1). Measure 2: Treble (1 2 1 2 1 3 4 5), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 4 2 1). Measure 3: Treble (5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2), Bass (1 2 1 2 1 2 1 2). Measure 4: Treble (1 2 1 2 1 2 1 2), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2).

Musical score for the second system (measures 5-7) in 4/4 time. The key signature is C major. The score consists of two staves. Measure 5: Treble (1 2 1 2 3 4 5 4), Bass (1 4 3 2 1 2 1 2). Measure 6: Treble (3 2 1 4 3 2), Bass (1 2 1 2 3 4). Measure 7: Treble (rest), Bass (rest). The system concludes with a double bar line and a key signature change to D major (two sharps).

Musical score for the third system (measures 8-11) in 4/4 time. The key signature is D major (two sharps). The score consists of two staves. Measure 8: Treble (1 2 3 1 2 3 4 5), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1). Measure 9: Treble (1 2 3 1 2 3 4 5), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1). Measure 10: Treble (5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2), Bass (1 2 3 4 1 2 3 1). Measure 11: Treble (1 2 3 1 2 3 4 1), Bass (5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2).

Musical score for the fourth system (measures 12-14) in 4/4 time. The key signature is D major (two sharps). The score consists of two staves. Measure 12: Treble (2 3 1 2 3 4 5 4), Bass (1 3 2 1 3 2 1 2). Measure 13: Treble (3 2 1 4 3 2), Bass (3 4 1 3 4 5). Measure 14: Treble (rest), Bass (rest). The system concludes with a double bar line and a key signature change to E major (three sharps).

15

Musical notation for measures 15-18. Treble clef with key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Bass clef with key signature of three sharps. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes.

Measure 15: Treble clef notes: 1 2 3 1 2 3 4 5. Bass clef notes: 4 3 1 3 2 1 2 1.

Measure 16: Treble clef notes: 1 2 3 1 2 3 4 5. Bass clef notes: 5 4 3 2 1 3 2 1.

Measure 17: Treble clef notes: 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2. Bass clef notes: 1 2 3 1 2 3 4 1.

Measure 18: Treble clef notes: 1 2 3 1 2 3 4 1. Bass clef notes: 5 4 3 1 4 3 1 4.

19

Musical notation for measures 19-20. Treble clef with key signature of three sharps (F#, C#, G#). Bass clef with key signature of three sharps. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 and 0 above or below notes.

Measure 19: Treble clef notes: 2 3 1 2 3 4 5 4. Bass clef notes: 3 1 3 2 1 2 1 2.

Measure 20: Treble clef notes: 3 2 1 3 2 0. Bass clef notes: 3 1 2 3 4 0.

Appendix B

Windowed Appendix

5.xml

Béla Bartók

S.

7

14

S.

S.

18

S.

S.

11.xml

Béla Bartók

II

♩ = 140

II

II

9

II

II

16.xml

Béla Bartók

8

4 5 4 3 2 3 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 4 3 2 1 2

$J = 104$

-2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4

8

1 4 5 4 3 2 4 5 4 3 2 4 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 2

-3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3

15

S.

3 2 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 5 4 3 2 3 0

-4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 0

S.

18.xml

Béla Bartók

S.
S.
♩ = 120

6
S.
S.

22.xml

Béla Bartók

22°
J = 136
f

The image displays a musical score for guitar, consisting of two staves. The top staff is in treble clef with a 4/4 time signature. It begins with a tempo marking of quarter note = 136 and a dynamic marking of *f*. The score is divided into measures by vertical bar lines. Fingering numbers (1-5) are placed above the notes. A large slur covers the first 10 measures, and another slur covers the final 10 measures. The bottom staff is also in treble clef and contains fret numbers (0-5) and fingerings (1-5) placed below the notes. A large slur covers the first 10 measures, and another slur covers the final 10 measures. The score is divided into two systems of 10 measures each. The first system starts with a measure number '8' at the beginning. The notes are primarily natural notes, with some accidentals (sharps and naturals) and a few chromatic alterations (flats and naturals) indicated by the fret numbers and note heads.

26.xml

Béla Bartók

f

$\text{♩} = 100$

2 3 4 5 5 5 5 5 4 4 3 2 1 2 4 4 4 4 4 3 1 2 4 5 5

9

5 4 3 5 4 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 5 5 5 4 3 2 3 0

-1 -1 -1 -2 -3 -2 -3 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 0

27.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays two systems of musical notation for a piece by Béla Bartók. Each system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff, both in 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as $J = 96$ and the dynamics as f (forte). The first system includes a large slur over the first four measures of the treble staff. The second system includes a large slur over the first five measures of the treble staff. The notation includes various notes, rests, and accidentals, with specific fretting and fingering instructions indicated by numbers and signs below the notes. The bass staff shows a consistent pattern of notes with corresponding fretting and fingering. The second system concludes with a sharp sign (#) on the bass staff.

System 1:

- Treble Staff: Notes with fretting and fingering: 1 (1), 2 (2), 3 (3), 4 (4), 5 (5), 4 (4), 3 (3), 2 (2), 1 (1), 2 (2), 3 (3), 4 (4), 3 (3).
- Bass Staff: Notes with fretting: -3, -4, -5, -4, -4, -5, -4, -3, -4, -3.

System 2:

- Treble Staff: Notes with fretting and fingering: 2 (2), 3 (3), 4 (4), 3 (3), 2 (2), 3 (3), 2 (2), 3 (3), 4 (4), 5 (5), 4 (4), 5 (5), 4 (4), 3 (3), 2 (2), 1 (1), 2 (2), 3 (3), 4 (4), 3 (3), 2 (2), 0 (0).
- Bass Staff: Notes with fretting: -2, -2, -2, -3, -4, -2, 1, -2, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -4, -5, -4, -3, 0.

28.xml

Béla Bartók

2810

2810

p

$\text{♩} = 112$

2811

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for measures 2810 and 2811. It features a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 112. The dynamics are marked as piano (*p*). The notation includes various note values (quarter, eighth, sixteenth notes), rests, and slurs. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Some notes are highlighted in yellow and green. The bass clef part shows a simple accompaniment with rests and a few notes.

281.

281.

282.

7

1 2 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 4 3 4 3 2 0

-3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 0

[30sec.]

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for measures 281 and 282. It features a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. The notation includes various note values, rests, and slurs. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Some notes are highlighted in yellow and green. The bass clef part shows a simple accompaniment with rests and a few notes. A bracket indicates a duration of [30sec.] for the final part of the piece.

31.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays a musical score for Béla Bartók's piece 31.xml, consisting of two staves: a piano (treble clef) and a bass (bass clef). The music is in 4/4 time and marked with a tempo of $J = 160$. The score is divided into measures, with measure numbers 9, 31, and 31 appearing at the beginning of sections. The piano part features a series of notes with fingerings (1-5) and accents (>). The bass part features a series of notes with fingerings (-1 to -5) and accents (>). The score is marked with a forte dynamic (*f*) and includes various musical notations such as slurs, accents, and dynamic markings.

6/8
p
♩ = 44

5

9

46.xml

Béla Bartók

Musical score for measures 1-8. The piece is in 4/4 time with a tempo of 120. The score consists of two staves: a treble staff and a bass staff. The treble staff begins with a whole rest in measure 1, followed by quarter notes in measures 2-8. The bass staff begins with a whole note in measure 1, followed by quarter notes in measures 2-8. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Dynamics include *mp*, *p*, and *mf*. A crescendo hairpin is present in measure 7.

Musical score for measures 9-14. The treble staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, starting with a half note in measure 9 and ending with a quarter note in measure 14. The bass staff provides a rhythmic accompaniment with quarter notes. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Dynamics include *f* and *mf*.

Musical score for measures 15-19. The treble staff continues the melodic line with slurs and accents, ending with a half note in measure 19. The bass staff continues the accompaniment. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Dynamics include *mf*.

Musical score for measures 20-24. The treble staff features a melodic line with slurs and accents, ending with a half note in measure 24. The bass staff continues the accompaniment. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Dynamics include *p* and *pp*.

52.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays two systems of musical notation for a piece by Béla Bartók. Each system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff, both in 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as $J = 112$ and the dynamics as f . The first system features a treble staff with a melodic line and a bass staff with a bass line. A large slur covers the first two measures of the treble staff, with a guitar fretboard diagram below it showing fingerings: 2, 3, 4, 4, 1, 1, 2. The second system continues the piece, with a treble staff featuring a melodic line and a bass staff with a bass line. A large slur covers the first two measures of the treble staff, with a guitar fretboard diagram below it showing fingerings: 4, 2, 1, 5. The bass staff in both systems includes various fretboard diagrams and fingerings, such as -1, -2, -1, -2, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, and accents (>).

67.xml

Béla Bartók

p

4/2 3 3 1 3 2 3 1 3 2 3 1 3 1 4 1

♩ = 110

-1 -3 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3

5

3 2 4 2 3 2 4 2 3 3 1 5 1 4 2 4 2

-2 -3 -1 -5 -2 -1 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2

10

3 2 3 4 5 4 5 3 4 3 0

-1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -2 -3 -1 -2 -2 -3 -3 0

21

mf *f*

25

p *f* *p* *mp*

30

0

35

f

85.xml

Béla Bartók

f
5 4 3 2 4 5 4 3 2
♩. = 88

6
p
♩. = 108
1 2 4 3 5 1 2 3 4 3 5 1 1 2 5

12

18

25

31

2 1 5 1 2 3 1 2 3 1 2 4 1 2 4 1 3 5

-2 -1 -3 -5 -4 -3 -5 -4 -3 -4 -2 -1 *mf* -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2

38

3 5 2 4 2 1 4 2 1 4 2 5 4 1 3

-1 -2 -4 -3 -5 -1 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 1 -2 -3 2 -1 -4

44

5 1 4 5 1 3 *p* 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5

-2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 5 -1 -2 -3 5 -1 -2 -3 5

50

1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 4 2 1 2 3 5 4 2 1 2 4 4 2 1 2 3

-5 -1 -2 -3 -5 -1 -2 -3 -5 -4 -2 1 -2 -3 5 -4 -2 1 -2 -4

56

5 4 2 1 2 1 *f* 5 5 5

♩ = 88

-4 -2 -1 -2 -1 2 -1 -2 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 0

92.xml

Béla Bartók

f
♩ = 138

5

8

11

14

17

mf *f* *mf* *ff*

The musical score is presented in two staves, Treble and Bass clef, in 4/4 time. It features a variety of musical notations including slurs, ties, and dynamic markings. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The score is divided into measures, with measure numbers 5, 8, 11, 14, and 17 marked at the beginning of their respective systems. The dynamics range from *f* (forte) to *ff* (fortissimo). The key signature is one sharp (F#).

2

21

Musical notation for measures 21-23. Treble clef has notes with fingerings 0, 0, 0, #0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 5, 4, 3, 1, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3. Bass clef has notes with fingerings -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2.

24

Musical notation for measures 24-26. Treble clef has notes with fingerings 0, 0, #0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2, #0, 0, 0, #0, 0, 0. Bass clef has notes with fingerings -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2.

27

Musical notation for measures 27-29. Treble clef has notes with fingerings 0, 2, 1, 5, 1, 4, 3, 5, 4, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 1, 4. Bass clef has notes with fingerings -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, 0, 0, 0, #0, 0, 0, 0, -2.

30

Musical notation for measures 30-32. Treble clef has notes with fingerings 2, 4, 2, 3, 2, 3, 4, 2, 4, 3, 4, 3, 4, 3, 4, 1, 2, 1, 0. Bass clef has notes with fingerings -3, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -2, -3, -2, -3, -2, -1, -2, -4, 0.

93.xml

Béla Bartók

f
♩ = 66

5

9

12

Detailed description: This is a guitar score for measures 1 through 12. The music is written in two staves: a treble staff (top) and a bass staff (bottom). The piece begins with a forte (*f*) dynamic and a tempo marking of quarter note = 66. The time signature starts as 2/4, changes to 3/4 at measure 2, and returns to 2/4 at measure 4. The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, ties, and triplets. Fingering is indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. The bass staff features many notes with negative fingering numbers (e.g., -2, -3, -4, -5), indicating natural harmonics. Measure 8 contains a double bar line with a repeat sign. Measure 12 ends with a double bar line and repeat dots.

97.xml

Béla Bartók

♩. = 48
p

5

9

13

mf

17

21

25

Musical notation for measures 25-28. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of one sharp (F#). It begins with a long note marked with a '3' above it, followed by a quarter note marked with a '1' above it, and then two rests. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. It contains a sequence of notes with fingerings: -5, -4, -2, -1, -2, -3, -5, -4, -2, #1, -2, -3, and a dynamic marking 'p' above a note with fingerings -5, -3, -1. The system concludes with a long note marked with '-5' and '-3' below it.

29

Musical notation for measures 29-32. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in bass clef with a key signature of one sharp (F#). It contains a sequence of notes with fingerings: 1, 2, 4, #5, #4, 2, 1, 2, 4, #5, #4, 2, 1, 2, 4, #5, #4, 2, 1, 2, 4, #5, #4, 2. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. It contains notes with fingerings: -2, -1, -4, -3, -1, -2, -3, -1, -2, -3, -4, -5.

33

Musical notation for measures 33-36. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in bass clef with a key signature of one sharp (F#). It contains notes with fingerings: 1, 2, 4, #5, #4, 2, 1, 2, 4, #5, 4, 2, followed by a treble clef and notes with fingerings: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 0. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. It contains notes with fingerings: -1, -2, -3, -4, -4, -2, 2, -3, 0.

100.xml

Béla Bartók

1

♩ = 152

6

$\hat{>$

10

$\hat{>$

15

$\hat{>$

20

$\hat{>$, p, $\hat{>$

3

$\text{♩} = 112$

sf

f

p

5

sf

sf

sf

sf

9

sf

sf

sf

sf

13

sf

sf

sf

sf

17

sf

sf

sf

sf

21

sf

sf

25 *sf*

Musical notation for measures 25-28. The score is in treble and bass clefs with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). Measure 25 starts with a forte (*sf*) dynamic. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Measure 26 features a triplet of eighth notes. Measure 27 includes a slur over a group of notes. Measure 28 ends with a triplet of eighth notes. The bass line has a long slur spanning measures 25-28.

29 *ff*

Musical notation for measures 29-32. The score continues in treble and bass clefs with the same key signature. Measure 29 starts with a fortissimo (*ff*) dynamic. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5. Measure 30 features a triplet of eighth notes. Measure 31 includes a slur over a group of notes. Measure 32 ends with a triplet of eighth notes. The bass line has a long slur spanning measures 29-32.

109.xml

Béla Bartók

This musical score is for a piece by Béla Bartók, identified as 109.xml. It is written for two staves, likely for a piano or guitar. The tempo is marked as $\text{♩} = 134$. The score is divided into systems, with measure numbers 5, 9, 14, 18, and 22 indicated at the beginning of each system. The music is characterized by intricate fingering, often involving multiple fingers (1-5) and accidentals (sharps, flats, naturals). Dynamics such as *f* (forte) and *ff* (fortissimo) are used. The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, ties, and articulation marks. The key signature and time signature are not explicitly stated but can be inferred from the notes and accidentals. The piece concludes with a final measure in the second system.

Musical notation for measures 26-30. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with various note values and slurs. The bass staff contains a bass line with similar note values and slurs. Fingering numbers (1-5) are written above the treble staff notes, and fret numbers (-5, -4, -3, -2, -1) are written below the bass staff notes. The key signature has one flat (Bb). The time signature is 6/8. Measure 30 ends with a double bar line.

Musical notation for measures 31-35. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff begins with a dynamic marking of *p* and contains a melodic line with slurs and ties. The bass staff contains a bass line with slurs and ties. Fingering numbers (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) are written above the treble staff notes, and fret numbers (-5, -4, -3, -2, -1) are written below the bass staff notes. The key signature has one flat (Bb). The time signature is 6/8. Measure 35 ends with a double bar line.

Musical notation for measures 36-40. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff begins with a dynamic marking of *pp* and contains a melodic line with slurs and ties. The bass staff contains a bass line with slurs and ties. Fingering numbers (1, 2, 4, 5) are written above the treble staff notes, and fret numbers (-4, -3, -2, -1, 0) are written below the bass staff notes. The key signature has one flat (Bb). The time signature is 6/8. Measure 40 ends with a double bar line.

113.xml

Béla Bartók

mf

3 2 3 3 2 3 3 2 3

$\text{♩} = 343$

4

f

mf *pp*

7

10

13

16

129.xml

Béla Bartók

This musical score is for a piece by Béla Bartók, identified as 129.xml. It is written for two staves, likely piano and a second instrument or voice. The time signature is 2/4, and the tempo is marked as $\text{♩} = 160$. The score is divided into measures, with measure numbers 7, 13, 19, 25, and 31 indicated at the beginning of their respective systems. The music features a variety of dynamics, including *f* (forte), *mf* (mezzo-forte), *mp* (mezzo-piano), and *p* (piano). Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above or below notes. Articulation marks such as accents and slurs are used throughout. The score includes a key signature change to two sharps (F# and C#) starting at measure 31. The notation is a mix of eighth and sixteenth notes, often beamed together in pairs or groups.

37

$\text{♩} = 150$

p

42

$\text{♩} = 150$

48

$\text{♩} = 150$

54

$\text{♩} = 160$

pp

2
26

Musical notation for measures 26-29. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (2, 1, 5, 2, 1, 3, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2). The bass staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (-2, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -4, -3, -2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0). A dynamic marking *f* is present in the bass staff. A *p* marking is at the end of the system.

30

Musical notation for measures 30-33. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (5, 4, 3, 1, 2, 4, 2, 3, 2, 4, 5, 2, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 5, 3, 4, 5, 2). The bass staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (-2, -3, -4, -5, -3, -4, -5, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -3, -1, -3, -4, -5, -2, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -3). A dynamic marking *f* is present in the bass staff.

34

Musical notation for measures 34-37. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 2, 4, 2, 3, 4, 3, 4, 5, 3, 5, 4, 3, 5, 2, 3, 0). The bass staff contains notes with accidentals (bb) and fingerings (-1, -4, -5, -1, -4, -5, -1, -4, -5, -1, -3, -5, -3, -4, -2, 0). A dynamic marking *f* is present in the bass staff.

139.xml

Béla Bartók

mf

$\text{♩} = 120$

1 2 4 1 2 4 1 3 5 2 1 1 2 1 4 1 2 3

0 -2 -4 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

5 4 2 1 2 1 *p* 5 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 4 *f* 4 5

f -5 -1 -5 -5 -5 -2 -2 -2 -1 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -5

5 5 5 5 5 4 3 2 5 3 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 5 4 5 4 5

-4 -2 -1 -1 2/3 -3 -4 -2 -1 -2 -1 -5 -2 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -5 -4 -2 -1 -1/2

3 2 3 4 5 3 3 1 2 3 1 2 3 2 1 4 3 5 4 5 4 5

-4 -2 -1 -2 -1 -3 -5 -5 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2

mp 4 5 4 5 3 4 2 3 1 2 5 4 2 1 2 3 4 5 1 3 0 0 0 0 0 0

2 5 4 2 5 3 5 3 5 1 3 5 2 3 5 1 5 4 2 1

-2/5 -1/4 -1/4 -1/4 -1/5

2

33

p *f*

39

mf *f*

44

f

48

p *f*

This musical score is for guitar, consisting of 40 measures. It is written in a key with one flat (B-flat) and a 3/4 time signature. The tempo is marked as *mp* (mezzo-piano) with a metronome marking of 146. The score is divided into systems of two staves each. The first system (measures 1-5) includes a tempo marking of *mp* and a metronome marking of 146. The second system (measures 6-11) includes a dynamic marking of *p* (piano). The third system (measures 12-18) continues the piece. The fourth system (measures 19-25) includes a dynamic marking of *mp*. The fifth system (measures 26-30) includes a dynamic marking of *mp*. The sixth system (measures 31-35) includes a dynamic marking of *mp*. The seventh system (measures 36-40) includes a dynamic marking of *mp*. The score features complex rhythmic patterns, including triplets and sixteenth notes, and extensive use of fingerings (numbers 1-5) and accidentals (sharps and flats). The piece concludes with a final chord in the seventh system.

6

Musical score for measures 6-10. The piece is in 2/4 time with a tempo of 88. The key signature has two flats. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is in bass clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. Measure numbers 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 are indicated above the staves.

11

Musical score for measures 11-15. The piece continues in 2/4 time. The key signature changes to one flat. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. Measure numbers 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 are indicated above the staves.

16

Musical score for measures 16-20. The piece continues in 2/4 time. The key signature has one flat. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. Measure numbers 16, 17, 18, 19, and 20 are indicated above the staves.

20

Musical score for measures 20-24. The piece continues in 2/4 time. The key signature has one flat. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. Measure numbers 20, 21, 22, 23, and 24 are indicated above the staves.

Musical score for measures 24-28. The piece continues in 2/4 time. The key signature has one flat. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and the lower staff is in bass clef. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. Measure numbers 24, 25, 26, 27, and 28 are indicated above the staves.

24

Musical score for measures 24-25. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 24 and 25, featuring notes with fingerings 4, 2, and 5. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 24 and 25, featuring notes with fingerings 0, 3, 3, and 0. A dynamic marking *f* is present in measure 25. A chord symbol $\sharp\sharp$ is written below the bass staff in measure 25.

26

Musical score for measures 26-27. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 26 and 27, featuring notes with fingerings 1, 5, 4, and 2. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 26 and 27, featuring notes with fingerings -2, -5, -1, -2, -1, -2, -1, -2, -3, -1, -5, -1, -2, -4. A dynamic marking *f* is present in measure 26.

32

Musical score for measures 32-36. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 32-36, featuring notes with fingerings 4, 2, 1, 5, 2, 4, 1, 5, 5, 4, 2, 1, 5, 2, 4, 1, 5, 5, 1, 5, 2, 4, 1. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 32-36, featuring notes with fingerings -5, -2, -4, -1, -5, -1, -2, -3, -5, -1, -2, -4, -1, -5, -5, -2, -4, 3, -1, -4, -5, -2, -5, -1, -5.

37

Musical score for measures 37-40. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 37-40, featuring notes with fingerings 5, 2, 4, 1, 5, 2, 4, 1, 1, 2, 4, 5, 5, 4, 2, 1. A dynamic marking *p* is present in measure 37. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 37-40, featuring notes with fingerings -4, -5, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, -5, 0, 0. A dynamic marking *poco* is present in measure 40.

41

Musical score for measures 41-42. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 41 and 42, featuring notes with fingerings 5, 1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2, 1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 4, 1, 4, 1, 0. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 41 and 42, featuring notes with fingerings 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, -5, -2, -1, -1, -5, -1, -4, -1, -4, 0, 0, 0, 0.

42

Musical score for measures 42-43. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with a slur over measures 42 and 43, featuring notes with fingerings 2, 1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2, 1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 4, 1, 4, 1, 0. The lower staff (bass clef) contains a bass line with a slur over measures 42 and 43, featuring notes with fingerings 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, -5, -2, -1, -1, -5, -1, -4, -1, -4, -1, -4, 0, 0, 0, 0. A dynamic marking *f* is present in measure 43.

48

mf

54

58

59

63

mf

p

69

p

Musical score for guitar, consisting of two staves. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. The music is written in a key with one flat (F major or D minor) and a 4/4 time signature. The score includes various guitar-specific notations such as fret numbers, accidentals, and dynamic markings.

Staff 1 (Treble Clef):

- Measure 1: Rest.
- Measure 2: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (4, 5).
- Measure 3: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (4, 5).
- Measure 4: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (0, 0, 0, 0).
- Measure 5: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (0, 0, 0, 0).
- Measure 6: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (0, 0, 0, 0).
- Measure 7: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (0, 0, 0, 0).
- Measure 8: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (0, 0, 0, 0).

Staff 2 (Bass Clef):

- Measure 1: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-1, -3, -2, -1).
- Measure 2: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 3: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 4: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 5: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 6: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 7: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).
- Measure 8: Fretted notes with accidentals (b, b) and fret numbers (-3, -1).

Annotations:

- Accidentals: flats (b) and naturals (♮).
- Fret numbers: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.
- Dynamic markings: < (crescendo).
- Other markings: # (sharp), - (dash).

0

$\text{♩} = 168$

p

sf

6

0

mf

sf

12

sf

sf

17

f

f

23

sf

f

28

mf

33

Musical score for measures 33-38. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music features a complex melodic line in the upper staff with many slurs and fingerings (1-5). The lower staff provides a harmonic accompaniment with chords and moving lines, also including fingerings. Measure numbers 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, and 38 are indicated above the upper staff.

39

Musical score for measures 39-44. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music continues with complex melodic and harmonic textures. Dynamic markings *sf* (sforzando) are present above measures 40 and 44. Measure numbers 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, and 44 are indicated above the upper staff.

45

Musical score for measures 45-49. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music features intricate melodic patterns and harmonic support. Measure numbers 45, 46, 47, 48, and 49 are indicated above the upper staff.

50

Musical score for measures 50-55. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music includes dynamic markings *sf* (sforzando) above measures 50, 52, 54, and 55. Measure numbers 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, and 55 are indicated above the upper staff.

56

Musical score for measures 56-61. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music features dynamic markings *f* (forte) above measures 56 and 57. Measure numbers 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, and 61 are indicated above the upper staff.

62

Musical score for measures 62-67. The system consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps. The lower staff is in bass clef with the same key signature. The music includes dynamic markings *p* (piano) above measures 62 and 63. Measure numbers 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, and 67 are indicated above the upper staff.

68

Musical notation for measures 68-73. Treble clef contains sixteenth-note runs with fingerings 3, 5, 3, 1, 3, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 3, 1, 3, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 4, 5. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -5, -3, -4, -2, -4, -2, -4, -2, -4, -2, -4, -2, -4, -3, -4, -3.

74

Musical notation for measures 74-80. Treble clef contains quarter notes with fingerings 5, 5, 5, 0, 0, 0, 1. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -5, -3, -4, -3, -5, -3, -5, -2, -5, -3, -5, 0, -5, 0, 0, -2.

81

$\text{♩} = 81$

Musical notation for measures 81-85. Treble clef contains sixteenth-note runs with fingerings 5, 3, 2, 1, 4, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5.

86

Musical notation for measures 86-90. Treble clef contains sixteenth-note runs with fingerings 3, 5, 2, 1, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3, 2, 4, 3, 4, 3, 4, 1, 5, 4. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5.

91

Musical notation for measures 91-97. Treble clef contains sixteenth-note runs with fingerings 3, 1, 3, 5, 3, 2, 1, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -3, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5.

98

Musical notation for measures 98-102. Treble clef contains sixteenth-note runs with fingerings 4, 3, 3, 4, 4, 3, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 4, 2, 2, 3, 2, 1, 2, 0, 0, 0, 0. Bass clef contains sustained chords.

103

Musical notation for measures 103-107. Treble clef contains chords with fingerings 3, 2, 3, 3, 2, 3, 2, 3, 4, 4, 3, 4, 4, 3. Bass clef contains chords with fingerings -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -2, -4, -5.

142

5

147

sf

152

$\text{♩} = 168$

sf

sf

157

162

166

p

f

sf

Appendix C

Attention Appendix

5.xml

Béla Bartók

First system of musical notation. It consists of two staves: a treble staff (top) and a bass staff (bottom). The time signature is 4/4. A tempo marking $\text{♩} = 104$ is present. The treble staff contains notes with fingerings: 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3. The bass staff contains notes with fingerings: -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -3. A slur covers the first five notes of each staff.

Second system of musical notation. It consists of two staves: a treble staff (top) and a bass staff (bottom). The time signature is 4/4. The treble staff contains notes with fingerings: 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 3, 4, 5, 3, 2, 1, 2. The bass staff contains notes with fingerings: -2, -3, -4, -5, -4, 3, -2, -1, -2, -3, -4, 5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -4. A slur covers the first five notes of each staff. The system concludes with a measure rest in the treble staff and a double bar line.

14

1 2 3 2 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 4 3 4 5 4

S.

-3 -2 -1 -5 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3

S.

18

5 4 3 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 4

S.

-1 -2 -3 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -4 0 -3

S.

11.xml

Béla Bartók

II

♩ = 140

II

II

9

II

II

12.xml

Béla Bartók

S.
♩ = 100

S.

7

S.

13

S.

16.xml

Béla Bartók

8

♩ = 104

4 5 4 3 2 3 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 2

-2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4

8

1 4 5 4 3 2 4 5 4 3 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2 1 4

-3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4

15

S.

3 2 5 4 3 2 1 2 3 5 4 3 2 3 0

-4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 0

S.

18.xml

Béla Bartók

6

S.

$J = 120$

S.

6

S.

S.

22.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays a musical score for guitar, consisting of two staves. The top staff is in treble clef with a 4/4 time signature. It begins with a tempo marking of $\text{♩} = 136$ and a dynamic marking of f . The score is divided into measures by vertical bar lines. Fingering numbers (1-5) are placed above notes, and fret numbers (0-5) are placed below the notes. The notes are primarily eighth and quarter notes, with some beamed eighth notes. The bottom staff is also in treble clef and contains a series of notes, some of which are beamed together. Fingering numbers are placed below these notes, and fret numbers are placed above them. The score concludes with a double bar line at the end of the second staff.

26.xml

Béla Bartók

f

$\text{♩} = 100$

2 3 4 5 5 5 5 4 3 2 1 2 4 4 4 4 4 3 1 2 4 5 5

9

5 4 3 5 4 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 5 5 5 4 3 2 3

27.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays two systems of musical notation for a piece by Béla Bartók. Each system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff, both in 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 96 (♩ = 96) and the dynamics are marked as *f* (forte). The notation includes various musical symbols such as notes, rests, and slurs. The guitar fretting is indicated by numbers below the notes, with negative signs (e.g., -2, -3, -4, -5) representing frets below the nut. The first system covers measures 1 through 5, and the second system covers measures 6 through 10. The piece concludes with a sharp sign (#) on the bass staff in the final measure.

28.xml

Béla Bartók

2810

2810

p

$J = 112$

2811

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for measures 2810 and 2811. It features a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 112 (J = 112). The dynamics are marked as piano (p). The melody consists of dotted quarter notes. Measure 2810 contains notes with fingerings 5, 4, 3, 5, 4, 3, 2. Measure 2811 contains notes with fingerings 5, 4, 3, 5, 4, 3, 2. A slur covers the first six notes of measure 2811. The bass line consists of whole notes with fingerings 1, 2, 3, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2.

2811

2811

2812

7

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for measures 2811 and 2812. It features a treble clef and a 4/4 time signature. Measure 2811 contains notes with fingerings 1, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 5, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2. A slur covers the first six notes of measure 2811. Measure 2812 contains notes with fingerings 4, 3, 4, 3, 2, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2, 3, 4, 3, 2. A slur covers the first six notes of measure 2812. The bass line consists of whole notes with fingerings -3, -4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -3, -2, -1, -2, -3, -2, 0.

[30sec.]

31.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays two systems of musical notation for a piece by Béla Bartók. Each system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff, both in 4/4 time. The first system includes a tempo marking of $J = 160$ and a dynamic marking of f . The notation features a sequence of notes with various articulations, including accents and slurs. Below the notes, guitar fretting diagrams are provided, showing fingerings (1-5) and barre positions (indicated by negative numbers like -1, -2, -3, -4, -5). The second system continues the piece, ending with a double bar line and repeat signs. The page number '31' is visible at the top of both systems.

6/8
p
♩ = 44

5

9

46.xml

Béla Bartók

mp 2 3 2 p 2 3 2 mf 2 4

$\text{♩} = 120$
mp

mp *p* *mf*

9

f

f

15

mf

mf

20

p 2 3 4 2 3 4 *pp* 4 3 0

p *pp*

52.xml

Béla Bartók

The image displays a musical score for a piano piece by Béla Bartók. The score is written in 4/4 time and features a tempo marking of $J = 112$ and a dynamic marking of f (forte). The notation is presented in two systems, each with a treble clef staff on top and a bass clef staff on the bottom. The right hand (treble clef) plays a melodic line with various fingerings (e.g., 2, 3, 4, 1, 2, 4, 2, 1, 5, 0, 0, 0, 0) and includes a large slur over the first two measures. The left hand (bass clef) provides harmonic support with chords and single notes, often marked with fingerings (e.g., -1, -2, -1, -2, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5) and accents (>). The score concludes with a final chord in the right hand and a fermata in the left hand.

5

0 0 0 0 0

0 0 0 0

0 0 0 0

0 5 2 1

5 1 4 3

2 1 # 5

0

f

-2 -1 0

> >

67.xml

Béla Bartók

p

4/2 3 3 1 3 2 3 1 3 2 3 1 3 1 4 1

♩ = 110

-1 -3 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3

5

3 4 3 4 3 3 5 4 4 2

-2 -3 -1 -5 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2

10

3 2 3 4 5 4 5 3 4 3 0

-1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -1 -2 -2 -3 -1 -2 -2 -3 -3 0

69.xml

Béla Bartók

mf

$\text{♩} = 84$

p

1 2 3 4

5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12

13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20

5

1 2 3 4

5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12

13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20

9

1 2 3 4

5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12

13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20

13

1 2 3 4

5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12

13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20

17

1 2 3 4

5 6 7 8

9 10 11 12

13 14 15 16

17 18 19 20

21

Musical score for measures 21-24. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains complex chordal textures with fingerings such as 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, and 3 2 1. The bass staff features a melodic line with notes on the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd strings, indicated by fret numbers -1, -2, and -3. Dynamic markings include *mf* and *f*. A slur spans across the bass staff from measure 21 to 24.

25

Musical score for measures 25-28. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains complex chordal textures with fingerings such as 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, and 3 2 1. The bass staff features a melodic line with notes on the 4th, 3rd, and 2nd strings, indicated by fret numbers -4, -3, and -1. Dynamic markings include *p*, *f*, and *mp*. A slur spans across the bass staff from measure 25 to 28.

30

Musical score for measures 30-34. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains complex chordal textures with fingerings such as 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 5 3 2, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1. The bass staff features a melodic line with notes on the 0th fret, indicated by fret number 0. Dynamic markings include *f*. A slur spans across the bass staff from measure 30 to 34.

35

Musical score for measures 35-38. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains complex chordal textures with fingerings such as 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 4 2 1, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 3 2 1, 5 3 2, 4 2 1, 3 2 1, 0. The bass staff features a melodic line with notes on the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th strings, indicated by fret numbers -1, -2, -4, -5, -4, -4, -2, -3, -3, 0, -2, -3. Dynamic markings include *f*. A slur spans across the bass staff from measure 35 to 38.

71.xml

Béla Bartók

5 3 5 4 3 3 4 3 5 3 3 2 1 3 4 3 5 4 4

$\text{♩} = 66$

6 *sf* 4 4 4 3 3 4 4 4 4 3 3 3 5 5 4 2 4 5 4

12 *ff* 2 3 4 3 2 2 1 4 3 2 1 3 3 2 1

19 4 4 3 3 3 3 5 4 4 5 3 3 3 5 4 4 3 2 3

25 *ff* 4 4 4 3 3 5 4 4 4 4 3 3

85.xml

Béla Bartók

f
5 4 3 2 4 5 4 3 2
♩. = 88

6
♩. = 108
p

12

18

25

31

2 1 5 1 2 3 1 2 3 1 2 4 1 2 4 1 3 5

-2 -1 -3 -5 -4 -3 -5 -4 -3 -4 -2 -1 *mf* -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2

38

3 5 2 4 2 1 4 2 1 4 2 5 4 1 3

-1 -2 -4 -3 -5 -1 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -2 -1 -4

44

5 1 4 5 1 3 *p* 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5

-2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 5 -1 -2 -3 5 -1 -2 3

50

1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 1 2 3 5 4 2 1 2 3 5 4 2 1 2 4 4 2 1 2 3

-5 -1 -2 -3 -5 -1 -2 -3 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -4

56

5 4 2 1 2 1 *f* 5 5 5 5

$\text{quarter note} = 88$ 5 4 2 3 4 3 2 1 2 2 2 2

-4 -2 -1 -2 -1 5 4 2 3 4 3 2 1

92.xml

Béla Bartók

f
♩ = 138

5

8

11

14

17

mf *f* *mf* *ff*

1 2 3 4 1 2 4 5 4 3 2 5 4 3 1 2 3 4 1 4 2 1 2 3
-5 -4 -3 -2 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -2 -3 -4 -5 -4 -3 -1 -3 -1 -2 -4 -3 -2
1 2 1 2 3 1 2 3 2 4 5 4 3 2 5 4 3 2 3 2
-1 -3 -5 -4 -3 -5 -4 -2 -3 -2 -1 -2 -1 -3 -1 -2 -3 -4 -2 -3
3 2 4 3 5 4 3 5 3 1 2 3 4 3 2 4 5 3 5
-2 -3 -2 -4 -2 -3 -4 -2 -4 -5 -1 -3 -2 -3 -4 -3 -2 -3
4 3 2 4 4 3 2 3 4 3 2 3 4 3 2 3 5 4 3 4 5 4
-4 -3 -2 -3 -4 -3 -1 -2 -4 -3 -1 4 -2 -3 -4 -5 -2 -2
3 2 3 4 5 4 3 2 3 4 1 2 3 1 2 3 1 3 4 3
-5 -3 -2 -3 -5 -3 -2 -3 -5 -3 -2 -3 -4 -2 -3 -2 -3 -4 5
1 3 4 3 2 3 4 5 2 3 4 2 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 *ff*
-3 -2 -5 -4 -3 -5 -4 -3 -5 4 -1 -3 -2 -4 -3 -2 -4 -3 -2 -5 -4 -3 -5 -4

2

21

Musical score for measures 21-23. The piece is in G major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. Measure 21 features a melodic line in the treble clef with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Measure 22 continues the bass line with notes G1, F1, E1, D1, C1, B0, A0, G0. Measure 23 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Fingering numbers are provided for all notes.

24

Musical score for measures 24-26. Measure 24 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Measure 25 continues the bass line with notes G1, F1, E1, D1, C1, B0, A0, G0. Measure 26 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Fingering numbers are provided for all notes.

27

Musical score for measures 27-29. Measure 27 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Measure 28 continues the bass line with notes G1, F1, E1, D1, C1, B0, A0, G0. Measure 29 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Fingering numbers are provided for all notes. A dynamic marking *p* is present at the end of measure 29.

30

Musical score for measures 30-32. Measure 30 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Measure 31 continues the bass line with notes G1, F1, E1, D1, C1, B0, A0, G0. Measure 32 has a melodic line with notes G4, A4, B4, C5, D5, E5, F5, G5 and a bass line with notes G2, F2, E2, D2, C2, B1, A1, G1. Fingering numbers are provided for all notes.

93.xml

Béla Bartók

f

Measures 1-4 of the piece. The music is in 2/4 time, with a tempo marking of quarter note = 66. The key signature has one sharp (F#). The first staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with a dynamic marking of *f* and includes a triplet of eighth notes. The second staff (bass clef) provides a bass line with various fingering numbers (e.g., -3, -2, -4, -1, -2, -4) and includes a triplet of eighth notes. The time signature changes from 2/4 to 3/4 and back to 2/4.

5

Measures 5-8 of the piece. The music continues in 2/4, 3/4, and 2/4 time signatures. The first staff (treble clef) shows melodic development with a triplet and various fingering numbers. The second staff (bass clef) continues the bass line with complex fingering patterns (e.g., -3, -2, -4, -5, -3, -4, -3, -5, -2, -4, -3, -4, -5). The time signature changes from 2/4 to 3/4 and back to 2/4.

9

Measures 9-11 of the piece. The music is in 3/4 time. The first staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with a triplet and various fingering numbers. The second staff (bass clef) continues the bass line with complex fingering patterns (e.g., -5, -2, -4, -3, -2, -4, -3, -5, -2, -4, -3, -5). The time signature changes from 3/4 to 2/4 and back to 3/4.

12

Measures 12-14 of the piece. The music is in 2/4 time. The first staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with a triplet and various fingering numbers. The second staff (bass clef) continues the bass line with complex fingering patterns (e.g., -4, -3, -2, -4, -5, -4, -5, -4). The time signature changes from 2/4 to 3/4 and back to 2/4.

97.xml

Béla Bartók

♩. = 48
p

5

9

13

mf

17

21

25

Musical notation for measures 25-28. Measure 25 features a long melodic line in the treble clef starting with a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5) and a bass line with a descending eighth-note scale (-5, -4, -2, -1, -2, -3). Measure 26 continues the treble line with a triplet (4, 3, 2) and the bass line with a descending eighth-note scale (-5, -4, -2, -1, -2, -3). Measure 27 includes a dynamic marking *p* and a triplet (5, 3, 1) in the bass line. Measure 28 concludes with a descending eighth-note scale (-5, -3).

29

Musical notation for measures 29-32. Measure 29 has a treble line with a descending eighth-note scale (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and a bass line with a descending eighth-note scale (-2, -1). Measure 30 continues the treble line (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and the bass line (-4, -3, -1, -2, -3). Measure 31 has a treble line (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and a bass line (-1, -2, -3, -4, -5). Measure 32 concludes with a treble line (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and a bass line (-1, -2, -3, -4, -5).

33

Musical notation for measures 33-36. Measure 33 has a treble line (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and a bass line (-1). Measure 34 continues the treble line (1, 2, 4, 5, 4, 2) and the bass line (-2, -3, -4). Measure 35 has a treble line (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 0) and a bass line (-4, -2, 2, -3, 0). Measure 36 concludes with a treble line (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 0) and a bass line (-4, -2, 2, -3, 0).

100.xml

Béla Bartók

1 = 152

6

10

15

20

3

$\text{♩} = 112$

sf

f

p

5

sf

sf

sf

sf

9

sf

sf

sf

sf

13

sf

sf

sf

sf

17

sf

sf

sf

sf

21

sf

sf

25 *sf*

Musical score for measures 25-28. The piece is in D major (one sharp). The notation is in treble and bass clefs. Measure 25 starts with a forte (*sf*) dynamic. The bass line features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 26 continues with a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 27 features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 28 features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5).

29 *ff*

Musical score for measures 29-32. The piece is in D major (one sharp). The notation is in treble and bass clefs. Measure 29 starts with a fortissimo (*ff*) dynamic. The bass line features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 30 continues with a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 31 features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5). Measure 32 features a triplet of eighth notes (3, 1, 2) and a triplet of eighth notes (3, 4, 5).

109.xml

Béla Bartók

This musical score is for a piece by Béla Bartók, identified as 109.xml. It is written for two staves, likely piano and bass, in a 6/8 time signature. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 134. The score is divided into systems, with measures 1, 5, 9, 14, 18, and 22 explicitly labeled. The music is characterized by intricate fingering, often involving multiple fingers on a single hand, and a variety of dynamic markings including *f* (forte) and *ff* (fortissimo). The key signature is complex, featuring several flats and sharps. The notation includes many slurs, ties, and accents, indicating a highly technical and expressive piece.

Measures 1-4: *♩* = 134. Treble clef: 1 2 4 5 4 2 1 5 3 1 2 1. Bass clef: *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻².

Measures 5-8: Treble clef: *b*⁵ 4 2 1 2 3 *b*⁵. Bass clef: *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹.

Measures 9-13: Treble clef: 1 2 *b*⁴ 3 1 2 *b*⁴ 3 2 1 4. Bass clef: *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁵. *f* *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻² *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻².

Measures 14-17: Treble clef: 3 1 *b*⁴ 1 2 3 *b*⁴ *b*⁵ 4 3 2 5 4 2 1. Bass clef: *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻².

Measures 18-21: Treble clef: 4 2 *b*⁵ 1 3 1 2 2 1 3 4 3 1 2 3 5 3 2 5 3 2 5 3 2 5. Bass clef: *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻² *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹.

Measures 22-25: Treble clef: 3 2 5 3 2 5 1 2 4 5 5 5 4 3 5 4 2 4 5 4 3. Bass clef: *ff* *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻¹ *b*⁻² *b*⁻⁴ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁵ *b*⁻³ *b*⁻² *b*⁻³ *b*⁻⁴.

Musical notation for measures 26-30. The treble staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 5 4 3 1, 1 2 4, 5 5 4 1 3, 1 3 4 2 4 5 4, 5 3 2 3 5. The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings: -2 -1 -2 -1, -5 -4 -3 -2 -2 -3 -5 -3, -5 -4 -3 -5 -3 -2 -3, -2 -4 -5 -4 -3. Dynamics include *p* and *pp*. A double bar line is at the end of measure 30.

Musical notation for measures 31-35. The treble staff starts with a *p* dynamic and contains a melodic line with fingerings: 0 0 0 0 0, 0 0 0 0, 0 0 0 0, 5 1 2 3, 0 0 0 0, 5. The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings: -1 -5, 5 1 2 3, 2 5 2 1 5. Dynamics include *p* and *pp*. A double bar line is at the end of measure 35.

Musical notation for measures 36-40. The treble staff contains a melodic line with fingerings: 1 2 1 4 5 4 2, 1 2 1 2, 1 2, 1 2, 5 2, 4 2. The bass staff contains a bass line with fingerings: -4, -2 -1 -2, -3, -4 0 0, b 0, 0 0, 0 0. Dynamics include *pp* and *p*. A double bar line is at the end of measure 40.

113.xml

Béla Bartók

mf

3 2 3 3 2 3 3 2 3

♩ = 343

4

f

mf *pp*

7

10

13

16

19

5 3 1 3 4

mf 2 1 3 4

mp pp -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3

23

5 4 3 1 5 4

-2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3 -2 -5 -2 -5 -2 -5 -3

27

3 2 3 3 2 3 3 2 3

p -2 -3 -2 -3 -2 -3 -2 -3 -2 -3 0

f 0

129.xml

Béla Bartók

This musical score is for a piece by Béla Bartók, identified as 129.xml. It is written for piano and bass. The tempo is marked as $\text{♩} = 160$. The score is divided into systems, with measures 7, 13, 19, 25, and 31 explicitly labeled. The music is in 2/4 time and features a complex rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. The piano part (top staff) uses a variety of fingering techniques, including double and triplets, and is marked with dynamics such as *f*, *mf*, *mp*, and *sf*. The bass part (bottom staff) also includes detailed fingering and dynamics, with a key signature change to two sharps (D major) starting at measure 31. The score includes numerous fingering numbers (e.g., 1-5, 2-4, 3-1) and dynamic markings (*f*, *mf*, *mp*, *p*, *sf*) to guide the performer.

37

$\text{♩} = 150$

p

42

48

54

$\text{♩} = 160$

pp

130.xml

Béla Bartók

1 2 1 2 3 4 5 4 3 4 3 5 2 3 1 1 2 1 2 3 4 5

$\text{♩} = 94$

6 4 3 4 3 5 2 3 2 2 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 4 0 0

1 -1 -3 -1 -2 -5 -1 -5 -1 -5 -1 -5 -1

10 0 0 0 0 5 1 4 5 *mf* 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2 1 0

-5 -1 -5 -1 -5 -2 -5 -1 -5 -1 -5 -1 -5 -2

14 *f* 0 0 0 0 0 5 4 3 2 1 5 4 3 2 1 5 4 3 2 1

-1 -3 -1 -5 -1 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -1 -2 -5 -4

18 5 3 1 3 2 1 2 1 3 2 5 4 1 5 3 2 1 5 3 1 5 3 1

-5 -5 -4 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -2 -1 -2 -3 -1 -2 -5 -4 -5 -4

22 5 4 3 2 5 4 3 2 5 4 3 2 1 4 3 2 1 5 3 4 3 5 4

-1 -2 -1 -2 -3 -4 -5 0 0 0 0 0 -1 -4 -3 1 -5

2
26

Musical notation for measures 26-29. Treble clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (2, 1, 5, 2, 2, 1, 3, 2, 3, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 2). Bass clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (-2, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -4, -3, -2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 5, 0, 0, 0). Dynamics: *p*, *f*.

30

Musical notation for measures 30-33. Treble clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (5, 4, 3, 1, 2, 4, 2, 3, 2, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 1, 5, 3, 4, 5, 2). Bass clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (-2, -3, -4, -5, -3, -4, -5, -1, -2, -3, -4, -1, -3, -1, -3, -1, -3, -4, -5, -2, -1, -2, -3, -4, -3, -1, -3, -3). Dynamics: *f*.

34

Musical notation for measures 34-37. Treble clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 4, 2, 4, 2, 3, 4, 3, 4, 5, 3, 5, 4, 3, 5, 2, 3, 0). Bass clef: notes with accidentals and fingerings (-1, -4, -5, -1, -4, -5, -1, -4, -5, -1, -3, -5, -3, -4, -2, 0). Dynamics: *f*.

139.xml

Béla Bartók

mf

$\text{♩} = 120$

1 2 4 1 2 4 1 3 5 2 1 1 2 1 4 1 2 3

0 -2 -4 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 -1 -2 -4

5 4 2 1 2 1 *p* 5 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 4 *f* 4 5

-5 -1 -5 -5 -5 -2 -3 -2 -1 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -5

5 5 5 5 5 4 3 2 5 3 2 3 4 5 4 3 5 3 5

-4 -2 -1 -4 -2 -1 -2 -1 -5 -2 -4 -3 -4 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3 -5 -4 -2 -1 -1 -2

3 2 3 4 5 3 1 2 3 1 2 3 1 2 1 2 4 3 5 4 5 4 5

-4 -2 -1 -2 -1 -3 -5 -5 -5 -2 -1 -5 -2

4 5 4 5 3 4 2 3 1 2 5 4 2 1 2 3 4 5 1 3 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

-2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2 -2

2 5 4 2 3 5 3 5 4 2 1 3 5 1 5 4 2 1

-2 -5 -1 -4 -1 -4 -1 -4 -1 -5

2

33

1 2 3 5 2 *p* 1 5 0

f 0 0 0 0 0 0 1

Detailed description: This system contains measures 33 through 38. The top staff is in treble clef with a 7/8 time signature. It features a melodic line with a triplet of eighth notes (1, 2, 3) followed by a quarter note (5) and a half note (2). A dynamic marking of *p* is placed above the first measure. The bottom staff is in bass clef and contains a bass line with various intervals and a dynamic marking of *f* above the first measure. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

-3 -5 -2 -4 -1 -5 -4 -2 -1 -2 -3

mf 5 4 5 5 5 5 5 *f* 5 4 3 2 b 5

Detailed description: This system contains measures 39 through 43. The top staff is in treble clef and contains a melodic line with a dynamic marking of *mf*. The bottom staff is in bass clef and contains a bass line with a dynamic marking of *f*. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

-2 -3 -4 -5 -3 -4 -5 -1 -2 -3 -5

3 2 3 b 4 5 4 3 b 5 3 b 4 2 4 2 3 1 2

-4 -5 -2 -4 -1 -2 -1 -2 -2 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 -1

Detailed description: This system contains measures 44 through 47. The top staff is in treble clef and contains a melodic line with a dynamic marking of *f*. The bottom staff is in bass clef and contains a bass line with a dynamic marking of *f*. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

44

1 2 1 5 1 2 1 2 1 3 5 b 0

p *f* 0

-2 -4 -3 -3 -3 -3 -3 -3 -3 0

Detailed description: This system contains measures 48 through 52. The top staff is in treble clef and contains a melodic line with a dynamic marking of *p*. The bottom staff is in bass clef and contains a bass line with a dynamic marking of *f*. Fingering numbers are provided for many notes.

42

Musical notation for measures 42-46. The top staff shows a melodic line with triplets and slurs. The bottom staff shows a bass line with fingerings and accidentals. The key signature has two flats and the time signature is 2/4.

47

Musical notation for measures 47-50. Measure 47 features a *mf* dynamic. Measure 49 features a *sf* dynamic. A tempo marking $\text{♩} = 160$ is present between measures 48 and 49. The bottom staff includes a sequence of zeros (0) representing natural harmonics or specific fingerings.

51

Musical notation for measures 51-55. This section contains several *sf* (sforzando) markings. The notation includes complex slurs and fingerings in both staves.

56

Musical notation for measures 56-60. Measure 56 starts with a *sf* dynamic. Measure 60 features a *f* dynamic followed by a *mp* dynamic. The notation includes various slurs and fingerings.

61

Musical notation for measures 61-67. Measure 61 starts with a *mp* dynamic. The notation features a melodic line with slurs and a bass line with fingerings.

68

Musical notation for measures 68-73. Measure 68 starts with a *p* dynamic. The notation includes slurs and fingerings in both staves.

74

Musical notation for measures 74-78. The notation includes slurs, fingerings, and accents in both staves.

79

Musical notation for measures 79-83. The top staff features a melodic line with a trill on the first measure, followed by a descending scale with various fingering numbers (1, 2, 3, 4, 5). The bottom staff provides a bass line with corresponding fingering numbers (-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5).

84

Musical notation for measures 84-88. The top staff continues the melodic line with a trill and descending scale. The bottom staff continues the bass line with descending scale and fingering numbers (-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4).

89

Musical notation for measures 89-95. The top staff features a melodic line with a trill and descending scale. The bottom staff features a bass line with a descending scale and fingering numbers (-4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -4, -3, -4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3).

96

Musical notation for measures 96-100. The top staff features a melodic line with a trill and descending scale. The bottom staff features a bass line with a descending scale and fingering numbers (-4, -5, -4, -3, -2, -3, -4, -5, 0).

6

Musical score for measures 6-10. The piece is in 2/4 time with a tempo of 88. The key signature has two flats. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff begins with a rest, followed by a series of eighth notes with fingerings 1, 2, 3, 4. The lower staff contains a complex sequence of notes with various fingerings, including -5, -4, -2, -1, -4, -3, -1, -2, -1, -4, -2, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -5, -3, -4, -5. A dynamic marking of *p* is present. A fermata is placed over the final measure.

11

Musical score for measures 11-15. The upper staff features a melodic line with fingerings 1 2, 3 5 4 3 2, 1 0 0 b 0, b 0 0 0, and 1 2. The lower staff continues with notes and fingerings such as -4, -3, -2, -1, -1, -2, -4, -5, -1, -4, -2, -1, -2, -5, -4, -2, -1. A dynamic marking of *p* is present.

16

Musical score for measures 16-20. The upper staff has fingerings 1 3 5 4 2 1, 1 2 3 5, 1 2 3 4 2 5, and 2 3 5 4 2 1. The lower staff includes notes with fingerings -1, -2, -3, -5, -4, -2, -1, -4, -3, -2, -1, -2, -3, -5, -4, -2, -2, -3, -5, -4, -2. A dynamic marking of *p* is present.

20

Musical score for measures 21-25. The upper staff contains notes with fingerings 3, 1, 4, 2, 1, 2, 3, 1, 5, 1, 4. The lower staff has notes with fingerings -4, -5, -4, -2, -1, -3, -1, -5, -4, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 3, 0, -5, -6. A dynamic marking of *p* is present.

48

Musical notation for measures 48-53. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 48 starts with a dynamic marking *mf*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 48-53. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 53.

54

Musical notation for measures 54-57. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 54 starts with a dynamic marking *mf*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 54-57. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 57.

58

Musical notation for measures 58-58. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 58 starts with a dynamic marking *mf*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 58-58. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 58.

59

Musical notation for measures 59-62. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 59 starts with a dynamic marking *mf*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 59-62. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 62.

63

Musical notation for measures 63-68. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 63 starts with a dynamic marking *mf*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 63-68. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 68.

69

Musical notation for measures 69-74. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. Measure 69 starts with a dynamic marking *p*. Fingerings are indicated by numbers 1-5 above notes. A slur covers measures 69-74. A fermata is placed over the final note of measure 74.

The image shows a musical score for guitar, consisting of two staves. The top staff is in treble clef and the bottom staff is in bass clef. The music is written in a key with one flat (B-flat major or D minor). The score includes various fret numbers and accidentals. The top staff starts with a whole rest, followed by a chord with frets 4, b, 5, 4, b, 5. This is followed by a sequence of notes with frets 0, b, 4, 0, b, b, b, 4, 5. The bottom staff starts with a chord with frets -1, -3, b, -2, b, -1. This is followed by a sequence of notes with frets b, 4, b, 2, a whole rest, #, and a final note with fret 0. There are also some dynamic markings like '<' and '>'.

0

$\text{♩} = 168$

p

f

6

sf

mf

sf

12

sf

sf

17

f

f

23

sf

28

f

mf

33

Musical score for measures 33-38. The piece is in D major (two sharps). The right hand features a melodic line with slurs and fingerings (1-2, 3-4, 5). The left hand provides a harmonic accompaniment with chords and fingerings (1-2, 3-4, 5). A dynamic marking of *sf* (sforzando) is present at the end of the system.

39

Musical score for measures 39-44. The right hand continues the melodic line with slurs and fingerings. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *sf* is present at the end of the system.

45

Musical score for measures 45-49. The right hand features a melodic line with slurs and fingerings. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and fingerings.

50

Musical score for measures 50-55. The right hand has a melodic line with slurs and fingerings. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *sf* is present at the end of the system.

56

Musical score for measures 56-61. The right hand has a melodic line with slurs and fingerings. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *f* (forte) is present at the end of the system.

62

Musical score for measures 62-67. The right hand features a melodic line with slurs and fingerings. The left hand accompaniment includes chords and fingerings. A dynamic marking of *p* (piano) is present at the end of the system.

68

68 69 70 71 72 73

74

74 75 76 77 78 79 80

81

$\text{♩} = 81$

81 82 83 84 85

86

86 87 88 89 90

91

91 92 93 94 95 96 97

98

98 99 100 101 102

103

103 104 105 106 107

142

5

147

152

$\text{♩} = 168$

157

162

166